

TRANSATLANTIC DATA SCIENCE ACADEMY PROJECT

Phase 1: Scoping
and Shaping

Transatlantic Data Science Academy Project

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Acronyms

ADHD	attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder
AfDSP	Alliance for Data Science Professionals
AFESP	Advancing the Frontiers of Earth System Prediction
AI	artificial intelligence
AMIMA	Associate Member of the Institute for Mathematics and its Applications
AMS	American Meteorological Society
API	application programming interface
APS	American Physical Society
ARITech	Advanced Registered IT Technician
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BAS	British Antarctic Survey
BBSTEM	Black British Professionals in STEM
BEAR	Birmingham Environment for Academic Research
BGS	British Geological Survey
BlueBEAR	University of Birmingham supercomputer
CDT	centre for doctoral training
CEng	Chartered Engineer
CERFACS	Centre Européen de Recherche et de Formation Avancée en Calcul Scientifique
CIMAS	Cooperative Institute for Marine and Atmospheric Studies
CITP	Chartered IT Professional
CoP	community of practice
CPD	continuing professional development
CRAFT	(Space) Competencies Recognition and Assessment Framework Tool
Csci	Chartered Scientist
CW3E	Center for Western Weather and Water Extremes (US)
DA	data assimilation
DARC	Data Assimilation Research Centre, University of Reading
DAS	data assimilation scientist
DDaT	UK Government Digital and Data Profession Capability Framework
DE	data engineer
DiRAC	UK's high performance computing facility (funded by the Science and Technology Facilities Council)
DISC	Data Intensive Studies Center (US)
DRI	digital research infrastructure
DS	data scientist
DSIT	Department for Science, Innovation and Technology
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts

EDI	equity, diversity and inclusion
EO	Earth Observation
EPSRC	Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council
ESA	European Space Agency
ETL	extract, transform, load
FAIR	findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability data principles
FIMA	Fellow of the Institute of Mathematics and its Applications
FTE	full-time equivalent
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	graphical information system
GPU	graphics processing unit
GSE	Government Science and Engineering Career Framework
HDF	Hierarchical Data Format
HND	Higher National Diploma
HPC	high performance computing
IDE	integrated development environment
IDSC	Institute for Data Science and Computing (US)
IEA	Institute for Environmental Analytics, University of Reading
IMA	Institute of Mathematics and its Applications
JCEEI	Joint Centre for Excellence in Environmental Intelligence
JCSDA	Joint Center for Satellite Data Assimilation (US)
JNCC	UK Joint Nature Conservation Committee
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany
IfATE	Institute for Apprenticeships and Technical Education
LGBT	lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender
LGBTQ+	lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer or questioning and more
LLM	large language models
MIMA	Member of the Institute of Mathematics and its Applications
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
ML	machine learning
MLOps	machine learning operations
MOAP	Met Office Academic Partnership
MOOC	massive open online course(s)
MPI	message passing interface
NASA	US National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NCAR	US National Centre for Atmospheric Research
NCAS	UK National Centre for Atmospheric Science
NCEO	UK National Centre for Earth Observation
NEODAAS	NERC Earth Observation Data Acquisition and Analysis Service

NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NLP	natural language processing
NOAA	US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NOC	UK National Oceanography Centre
NSF	US National Science Foundation
NWP	numerical weather prediction
PDE	partial differential equation
PDRA	post-doctoral research assistant
PML	Plymouth Marine Laboratory
QAA	Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education
RDF	Vitae Researcher Development Framework
RITTech	Registered IT Technician
RMetS	Royal Meteorological Society
RSE	research software engineer
RSS	Royal Statistical Society
ScotRSE	A network of research software engineers in Scotland
SENSE	Satellite Data in Environmental Science – Centre for Doctoral Training
SocRSE	Society of Research Software Engineering
SPIN	Space Placements in Industry
SQL	structured query language
STEM	science, technology, engineering and maths
STEMM	science, technology, engineering, maths and medicine
TDSA	Transatlantic Data Science Academy
UCL	University College London
UKCA	UK Chemistry Aerosol Model
UKCEH	UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology
UKNCSP	UK National Climate Science Partnership
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
UKSA	UK Space Agency
UM	Met Office Unified Model
UoR	University of Reading
VS	Visual Studio

Executive summary

This report was commissioned by the Met Office to scope and shape the Met Office Transatlantic Data Science Academy (TDSA). The proposed Academy aims to provide:

- technical training,
- learning and development, and
- career development

for UK-based:

- data scientists (DSs),
- data engineers (DEs),
- data assimilation scientists (DASs), and
- research software engineers (RSEs)

working in the field of Earth Observation (EO) (while maintaining alignment with US colleagues at NOAA and NOAA partner affiliates). Further aims are to increase the diversity of staff and students working in these areas, provide the necessary support to staff and students to sustain such an increase in diversity and provide motivating careers and career opportunities for staff and students throughout their early, mid- and late careers, while ensuring an effective balance between on-the-job learning, peer-to-peer learning and formal training.

Methodology

Equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) are central to the approach of the project team, both in our recommendations for shaping the Academy and in the way we have carried out the project. The team have **consulted as widely as possible** via the mechanisms of an online stakeholder workshop (56 attendees), by conducting interviews and by reviewing existing literature.

Learner personas and learner diversity

“Learner personas” are fictional TDSA learners. Personas can be used as an evaluation tool to check the TDSA plans are fit-for-purpose and accessible to a diverse audience. The personas reflect a **variety** of different career stages, sectors, aspirations, prior skills and experience, learning preferences and access to resources such as time and money.

We identified **barriers to training** faced by some groups: financial restrictions, time restrictions, employment status, travel restrictions, training venue access issues, lack of inclusive/accessible design, belonging and inspiration (under-represented groups).

Efficiently focussing the academy around the DS, DE, RSE and DAS roles

We examined DS, DE, RSE, DAS role **overlaps and alignments across multiple dimensions**: technical skills, transferable skills, and fluency in different technologies and methods.

- **All roles cover a broad range of EO skills**, though with different levels of proficiency. We recommend that early career staff are all offered a **foundational course in EO**, with more advanced learning activities for specific roles.
- **All roles should be provided with training in the basics of machine learning (ML)**, as this is now becoming pervasive in weather and climate science and operations.
- **Required skills in computer and data science are more disparate**. We suggest the TDSA **adopts a flexible modular framework** and **makes use of existing training** in the technology sector.

Existing capacity and gaps in training, learning and development

There is a **general lack of courses specifically tailored to the needs of TDSA disciplines**, particularly in EO and atmospheric science applications. National and international conferences, webinars, communities of practice and learning from experienced colleagues provide additional development opportunities for each role.

Data assimilation scientists

- Formal training is largely limited to short, intensive courses offered by operational centres and universities.
- Specific training gaps have been identified in numerical linear algebra, advanced data assimilation techniques, ML integration, and operational application.
- Opportunities include the development of updated textbooks and training programs and introduction of data assimilation modules into academic curricula.

Data engineers

- Training is offered through taught postgraduate courses in data science or ML, which can lack specific data engineering topics.
- Online courses provided by cloud computing companies and large learning platforms cover role-specific skills (e.g. data pipelines and managing databases).
- Gaps include a lack of in-person training and courses focused on EO and ML operations (MLOps).
- Opportunities include offering more balanced online courses incorporating both platform-specific skills and fundamental data engineering principles.

Data scientists

- Training options include taught postgraduate qualifications, online courses, bootcamps and apprenticeships.
- Training content typically covers core topics like programming, ML, and statistics, and often includes specialisations like natural language processing or computer vision.
- Data science programs with an environmental/meteorological focus exist but remain limited in number.
- Opportunities include developing degree apprenticeship standards for environmental data science.

Research software engineers

- Software Carpentry curriculum provides basic introductory material, but there is limited access to advanced training in specific tools and techniques.
- Lack of support for researchers transitioning to RSE careers.
- Opportunities include an exploration of RSE exchange schemes to facilitate skill sharing and collaboration.

Accreditation, certification and transferable recognition

Many relevant accreditation and certification schemes already exist. We suggest that the TDSA work within these existing structures, rather than creating its own schemes.

Accreditation and certification for individuals:

- Training certification can range from a simple certificate of attendance to a formally assessed, accredited qualification (e.g., a MSc degree, or industry-recognised platform certificate).
- Research skills can be certified through completion of an MPhil or PhD.

- The Alliance for Data Science Professionals (AfDSP) offers “*Advanced Data Science Professional*” certification that appears suitable for all TDSA roles, although there are other professional accreditations, certifications, registrations or designations that may be a better fit for some staff in the DA and RSE roles.
- It is important to consider whether accreditation would be valued by Academy learners and to balance that against the time involved in applying for and maintaining accreditation.

Accreditation of courses and course providers:

- Currently accreditation of courses in data science, data engineering, research software engineering and data assimilation is limited.
- The Alliance for Data Science Professionals (AfDSP) has developed an appropriate accreditation standard for university courses.

Individuals and employers are likely to **value the *quality of training***. We recommend the provision of a **TDSA Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue**, listing courses with a **TDSA “seal of approval”**.

Career frameworks

Existing career frameworks **do not capture the nuances** of the roles considered in the TDSA. We provide two options for adapting existing career frameworks:

Option 1: Career framework based on the Digital and Data Profession Capability Framework (DDaT).

- This framework captures the RSE, DE, DS roles but the DAS role requires adding.
- The framework could be augmented to include EO skills.
- Career progression via both technical and managerial routes could be utilised.
- Cross role progression needs adding.

Option 2: Career framework based upon the Government Science and Engineering Framework (GSE).

- The Met Office science framework (under development) uses this as a basis.
- All four TDSA roles would be classed within the GSE deep specialist job family.
- Reclassification of the job families and incorporation of the TDSA job skills would be required.

Learner journey options

The Academy needs to serve a diverse range of individual learners and employers. We recommend a flexible model for individual learning journeys, that can be adapted to fit with the existing structures and processes of each employer. The proposed learner journey cycle consists of:

Step 1: Learning needs analysis and personal goal setting, scaffolded by a bespoke TDSA Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue.

Step 2: Carrying out learning and development activities.

Step 3: Personal reflection on progress towards the goals, and on whether the goals are still appropriate, looping back to Step 1 at regular intervals.

Underpinning support mechanisms available to the learner, providing help and encouragement for their whole learning journey.

Career-stage recommendations

For each career stage we provide options and recommendations for formal training, accreditation and recognition, career development and support mechanisms.

16 to 18 year olds and undergraduates

- Summer schools, projects, placements, career webinars.
- Exposure to different job roles and career options; bursaries and apprenticeships for further study.
- Mentoring by project or placement supervisor.
- Opportunity for more advanced TDSA learners to develop by getting involved in outreach and placement supervision.

Early career stage 1 (new starters)

- TDSA foundation course, in-person/hybrid community building workshops, range of self-paced learning, technical upskilling.
- “TDSA approved” accreditation for training options.
- Exposure to career frameworks and accreditation options, workplace shadowing a variety of roles, regular training plan and review process.
- Peer-to-peer learning, communities of practice, mentoring.

Early career stage 2 (a few years’ experience)

- Deepen technical skills (or fast-track new skills), “train-the-trainer”.
- Modular continuing professional development (CPD), external accreditation (e.g., Advanced Data Science Professional), or qualification (e.g., PhD).
- Industrial or policy secondments, delivering training to others, supporting progression from fixed-term to open-ended positions.
- Peer support networks, technical mentor.

Mid-career

- Technical training and accreditation to support further specialisation or transition between roles, secondments (in-person/hybrid/virtual).
- Part-time training programmes.
- Management and leadership training to support preparation for promotion to more senior position.
- Mentoring from senior colleagues/coaching.

Late career (senior roles)

- Online training for specific skills or overview of topic; short, focused training (away from day job); practical workshops for new technologies/tools; breadth more important than depth.
- Recognition via prizes, honorary positions or degrees.
- Secondments, sabbaticals, exploration of different sectors (private vs. public).
- Peer-to-peer mentorship, supporting staff positions (administrative or research).

Conclusion

Addressing the identified gaps in learning, development, and career framework provision for TDSA roles requires a collaborative effort involving academia, research institutions, professional organisations, and funding bodies. By providing learners with ideas for personal development, signposting existing courses, developing specialised training programmes, improving accessibility, improving learner support mechanisms and establishing clearer career pathways, we can empower a diverse group of current and future TDSA professionals with the skills and knowledge necessary to excel in their fields and contribute to advancements in atmospheric science and EO.

1 Introduction

1.1 About this report

This report is produced in fulfilment of the requirements of Phase 1 of the Met Office Transatlantic Data Science Academy Shaping project. The report has been produced for the Met Office by a consortium led by the University of Reading, in collaboration with University College London; University of Birmingham, University of Edinburgh, University of Exeter, University of Leeds, Assimila Ltd and Send them Soaring between November 2023 and March 2024.

1.2 Background to the project

Data science is not a new development for weather and climate studies, which have always involved the production, storage, analysis, visualisation and interpretation of vast quantities of observed and modelled data. However, in recent years, modern machine learning (ML) techniques have begun to be deployed in weather and climate studies, with rapid developments and notable successes¹. These breakthroughs in data science may help us to tackle key issues related to climate change:

- a) improving predictions (e.g., for better response to hazardous weather, renewable energy applications and climate services),
- b) increased speed of predictions, giving more immediate insights and decision-support,
- c) reduction of the carbon footprint associated with weather and climate prediction and research.

However, there is a critical shortage of skilled workers in relevant disciplines.

Recent growth in the space industry has increased demand for professional, technical workers in Earth Observation (EO). In the UK, the 2023 Space Sector Skills survey² found that 52% of organisations reported skills gaps in their current workforce. Of these, 72% have a gap in software and data skills, particularly skills in artificial intelligence (AI) and ML (41%) and data analysis and modelling (36%). These gaps are a result of struggling to hire new staff (48%), new staff not having the right skills (45%), and existing staff leaving (34%). In response to these drivers, the UK Space Agency (UKSA) established the Space Skills Advisory Panel, bringing together experts from across government, industry and academia to address the talent issues collaboratively. Similarly, in the USA, the potential for further growth, and the need to address challenges such as climate change with Earth Observation, has led to a Federal Space STEM (science, technology, engineering and maths) Task Force working collaboratively with industry and academia to diversify and strengthen the workforce³.

In November 2022, the Met Office was awarded £2.5m by the UK Government to create a Transatlantic Data Science Academy (TDSA), in partnership with the US National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), UK and US Universities and NOAA partner organisations such as the Joint Center for Satellite Data Assimilation (JCSDA) and the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR). The funding was part of a wider £200m investment into the UK EO sector to protect UK talent and industry⁴.

The initial TDSA funding covers activities taking place between December 2022 and March 2025 aligned with three themes:

- *a training theme* offering apprenticeships and developing tailored courses on weather and climate data science subjects made available to all Met Office and NOAA staff, and students or researchers at partner universities, and building cohorts of data scientists (DSs),

- *an exchange theme* offering exchange opportunities to Met Office staff, and UK students or researchers at partner universities, to NOAA and NOAA partner affiliates,
- *a sandpit theme* offering a common platform for sharing datasets and AI and ML tools to enable innovation and expand communities of interest in weather and climate data science subjects.

The rest of this report relates exclusively to the TDSA training theme.

1.2.1 Aims of the Academy

The proposed Academy aims to provide:

- technical training,
- learning and development, and
- career development

for UK-based:

- data scientists (DSs),
- data engineers (DEs),
- data assimilation scientists (DASs), and
- research software engineers (RSEs) (sometimes known as scientific software engineers),

working in the field of EO (while maintaining alignment with US colleagues at NOAA and NOAA partner affiliates). The planned Academy will address each of these four roles in data science, data engineering, research software engineering and data assimilation. However, in the name of the Academy and in some other places *data science/data scientist* is used as umbrella terminology to increase readability.

Further aims are to:

- increase the diversity of staff and students working in these areas,
- provide the necessary support to staff and students to sustain such an increase in diversity and
- provide motivating careers and career opportunities for staff and students.

throughout their early, mid- and late careers, while ensuring an effective balance between on-the-job learning, peer-to-peer learning and formal training.

The following sections provide further discussion of these aims.

1.2.2 Key requirements of the project to shape the TDSA

The Met Office held a competitive bidding process open to UK universities who are members of the Met Office Academic Partnership (MOAP), for a project to shape the TDSA and provide a blueprint for how it could be implemented. The work has been structured to include: an initial scoping and shaping phase (Phase 1); a subsequent review and reflection period; and a phase that considers the implementation of the Academy (Phase 2). This report covers the **key requirements (KRs) defined by the Met Office for Phase 1:**

KR 1. Identify key learner personas against which we can test the outputs of Phase 1 to ensure that they support the aims of the Academy.

KR 2. Identify key gaps in the UK's training, learning and development, career framework and career development provision under the aims.

KR 3. Identify the existing and future opportunities that can be exploited to advance the aims, provide options and recommendations for the exploitation of these; and provide options and recommendations for how the gaps in point 2 above can be addressed.

KR 4. Explain how the roles of DS, DE, DAS and RSE align and overlap under the EO umbrella and recommend how the Academy can be efficiently focussed to support that alignment and overlap.

KR 5. Identify routes for how Academy learners can achieve relevant certification, accreditation or other transferable recognition of skills developed through the Academy throughout their career.

The report structure is laid out below in Table 1-1 with a mapping onto the key requirements of the project.

Report chapter/section	Key requirement (KR) covered
Executive summary	All KRs.
1. Introduction	
2. Learner personas	KR 1
3. Career frameworks, roles alignment and overlaps	KR 4 and KR 2 (career frameworks)
4. Existing capacity and gaps	KR 2 (training, learning and development, and career development)
5. Accreditation, certification and recognition	KR 5
6. Exploiting opportunities	KR 3
7. Recommendations	Pulls together recommendations from all KRs.

Table 1-1: The structure of this report showing how the report sections map onto the key requirements of the project (Phase 1).

1.2.3 Assumptions about Academy scope

The project team have made the following assumptions about the scope of the study. Our general assumption is that the study relates to job roles in EO for weather and climate. We interpret EO broadly to include: the use of observing technologies to gather information about the physical, biological and chemical systems of the Earth, and applications where these data may be interpreted and used, such as numerical modelling, development of process understanding and data assimilation.

We assume that the TDSA has a particular focus on careers at the Met Office and aligned organisations, such as UK universities, NOAA and its partners in the USA. Nevertheless, our intent is that the business model developed will provide enough flexibility to have potential to serve a broader portion of the EO sector and related fields. In particular, while the specific needs of learners from the commercial sector will not explicitly be taken into account, we expect that there may be some aspects of the Academy provision that will be useful to commercial sector learners. Furthermore, we anticipate that delivery of the Academy could involve commercial sector training and development providers. Similarly, while the Academy will be designed with UK and US learners in mind, considerations of the practicalities for transatlantic implementation of the Academy are likely to be similar to those required for a wider international audience.

The aims of the Academy address early, mid- and late careers. For core academy learners we have chosen to interpret *early career* as beginning with recent graduates (e.g., a holder of an honours

degree such as a Bachelor of Science (BSc) or another equivalent qualification – known as Level 6 in England, Wales, and Northern Ireland⁵, and Level 9 in Scotland⁶). Earlier career stages will not be covered comprehensively.

1.3 What is the difference between training, learning and development?

The Academy aims to deliver training, learning and development for careers in data science (see Section 1.2.1). These terms are often synonymous in common usage, but in the context of people development for an organisation they have specific meanings^{7,8}, summarised in Figure 1-1, along with other related terminology.

Figure 1-1: Terms associated with learning and development.

Different people and organisations have different learning needs and preferences, and there is no single learning method that can cater to all of them. The Academy aims for an effective balance between on-the-job learning, peer-to-peer learning and formal training. The 70-20-10 model is a widely used model that suggests a proportional breakdown of how people learn effectively at work. The model suggests that:

- 70% of learning comes from informal, work-based learning. This takes place during new tasks and challenging assignments.
- 20% of learning comes from developmental relationships. Employees experience social learning through interactions with peers and mentors.
- 10% of learning comes from training in a formal, educational setting.

The model has been criticised for lack of evidential basis and research protocol problems⁹, as well as for being too prescriptive. Thus, in our approach to shaping the Academy, we propose a range of different types of learning activities, without imposing specific ratios for individual learners. Common methods and support mechanisms for work-related learning are given in Table 1-2. These are further discussed throughout the rest of this report.

Type of learning	Description
Formal learning	Formal learning is instructor led with some learner interaction. It is typically a group situation and can take place in-person, online or in a blended format. Examples include lectures, classes, and seminars.
Informal learning	Informal learning is unstructured, and more self-directed. It may take place on-the-job through tasks, feedback, co-worker interactions, and through individual study. Examples include conversations, online forums, and reading books or doing research.
Experiential learning	Experiential learning allows people to try doing something and gain understanding from the experience. Examples include apprenticeships, internships, simulation exercises, and scenario-based role-playing.
Coaching	<p>The employee meets with a coach for open dialogue. The coach holds an impartial stance on the subject matter, and asks insightful questions, designed to get the coachee to see their world from a different perspective. The person being coached draws on their own experience to reach their objectives. There are several types of workplace coaching e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>1-2-1 coaching</i> to help individual employees achieve their goals by identifying their strengths and areas for improvement. 1-2-1 coaching is able to focus deeply on things relevant to that person and is confidential but expensive for large numbers of people. • <i>Group coaching</i> where colleagues collaborate to learn from one another, build skills, or solve work problems, working with a coach as facilitator. Group coaching gives less personal attention and more generic exercises and questions. It is more affordable and also builds a peer support network. • <i>AI-based coaching</i> uses artificial intelligence to support or complement human coaches, or to take ownership of the coaching relationship.
Mentoring	<p>Mentoring connects employees with someone they can learn from to grow professionally. The mentee receives guidance and advice, drawing on the experience of the mentor. Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Traditional mentoring</i> where the relationship is between a senior mentor and a junior mentee, and the aim is to help the junior person develop their career. The mentor acts as a sounding board and shares their own journey as to how to overcome barriers. • <i>Reverse mentoring</i> where the relationship is between a junior mentor and a senior mentee, and the aim is to help the senior mentee e.g., to understand the barriers faced by the junior mentor or to understand current trends and perspectives, or develop a new technical skill. • <i>Reciprocal mentoring</i> where the relationship is non-hierarchical and designed for the mutual exchange of information and perspective to understand one another and the challenges better.

Action learning sets	<p>Action learning sets are a group who meet to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand or solve a shared or organisational problem. • Listen to and learn from each other. • Develop a set of actions. <p>These are highly task focussed.</p>
Communities of practice	<p>A community of practice is an organised group of people with a common interest in a specific domain. They collaborate regularly to share information, improve their skills and actively work on advancing their knowledge in that area.</p>
Accountability buddies	<p>Accountability buddies are a partnership or group who hold each other to account for completing a task. Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Writing retreats</i>, that offer dedicated time and space to set aside daily responsibilities to focus on writing with a group of other individuals. • <i>Hackathons</i>, where people engage in rapid and collaborative software development over a relatively short period of time such as 24 or 48 hours. • <i>“Body doubling”</i>, where a pair or group of individuals work simultaneously, either in the same room or virtually. This can be helpful to keep focus and motivation, particularly for learners with attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) or other forms of neurodivergence.

Table 1-2: Common learning and development methods and support mechanisms¹⁰

The key requirements (see Section 1.2.2) also involve identifying routes for certification, accreditation and transferable recognition of skills for academy learners. These terms are summarised in Figure 1-2 and further discussed in Section 5.

Figure 1-2: Terms associated with forms of recognition.

1.4 What are data science, data engineering, research software engineering and data assimilation?

The TDSA is aimed at delivering training, learning and development for four job roles: DS, DE, RSE, and DAS. In this section we provide an introduction to these four disciplines and define some key terminology. Note that the job roles defined under the TDSA are not necessarily universal. Other organisations define data-related job roles in a range of ways, with considerable overlap, but not direct equivalence to the roles defined here (see Section 3).

Data science: Data science deals with vast volumes of data, using modern tools and techniques such as ML, to find patterns, make predictions and derive actionable information (Figure 1-3).

Data engineering: Data engineering is the design, construction, testing and maintenance of architectures for collecting, storing, and analysing data at scale, such as databases and large-scale processing systems.

Research software engineering: Software engineering is the design, construction, testing, documentation and maintenance of software. RSEs combine professional software engineering expertise with understanding of research.

Data assimilation: Data assimilation is a sophisticated mathematical technique that combines large datasets of heterogeneous observations with a dynamical model, taking into account the observation and model uncertainties. Data assimilation is a key component in numerical weather prediction and climate studies, with its main applications in forecasting and reanalysis.

The DS, DE, RSE roles are all included in the UK Government Digital and Data Profession Capability Framework¹¹, but the DAS role is specific to the environment sector. Even for the DS, DE and RSE, the additional technical and ethical challenges in working with weather and climate data (e.g., robustness for operational systems, data volumes and velocities, trust in predictions for decision-making, net-zero computing, see Section 4.3.3) motivate a bespoke Academy with tailored training, learning and development activities.

Figure 1-3: Data Science as defined in the Met Office data science framework.¹²

1.5 Equity, diversity and inclusion

It is well known that the STEM workforce lacks diversity and this is true across meteorology and the space sector. For example, women and minoritised ethnicities are significantly under-represented in both the UK and USA^{13 14 15}. The Academy cannot on its own rectify historic and systemic imbalances,

but we can ensure that this initiative does not perpetuate them, by sensitive design that takes account of equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) from the outset. More specifically, the Academy has a role to play in promoting and embedding an inclusive culture; ensuring career development opportunities are inclusive; and promoting activities to support building a diverse pipeline of future scientists. This is reflected in the Academy aims (Section 1.2.1).

Equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) are central to the approach of the project team, both in our recommendations for shaping the Academy and in the way we have carried out the project. Nevertheless, due to finite resources we have put a boundary on the lower level of core academy learners as beginning with recent graduates. We recognise that long-term increases in diversity require reaching school-age children, since school experiences shape life choices and outcomes¹⁶. However, there are already a number of initiatives working with teachers, schools and undergraduates, so we propose to limit the Academy's efforts in this direction to a few activities that will increase these groups' exposure to careers in the remit of the Academy (see Sections 2, 6 and 7).

1.5.1 Equity, diversity and inclusion principles

The following principles have been adopted by the TDSA project team:

- **“Everyone, everyday”**: Ensuring that the TDSA as an entity and as a project is equitable and inclusive and that decisions are made fairly and transparently, is everyone's responsibility.
- **“Active bystanders”**: Discrimination or harassment on grounds related to their personal characteristics or their background is unacceptable and will be challenged – project members will be supported to be active bystanders.
- **“Valuing and respecting difference”**: We recognise that creating equal opportunities and an inclusive environment brings together different perspectives, skills and backgrounds, all of which are valuable in achieving our goals.
- **“Challenging assumptions”**: We work to identify and challenge assumptions that may be limiting opportunities for those working within the project, and those accessing the Academy.
- **“Nothing about us without us”**: When considering activities or actions targeting specific groups, we adopt the “nothing about us without us” approach which requires us to seek lived experience or expertise (even if this is via our stakeholders or otherwise external to the project) to inform decision making.
- **“Accountability”**: We publicly state our commitment to equity, diversity and inclusion, including regular descriptions of actions taken, learning and achievements.

The project team also agreed the following practical steps:

- Use inclusive meeting techniques e.g., hybrid, transparent, sending papers in a timely fashion ahead of meetings, chairing meetings inclusively (ensuring everyone has opportunity to speak and discussion is respectful).
- Include EDI sections in all reports that detail how equity, diversity and inclusion have been considered and impacted on the work carried out and in the proposed actions.
- Include an EDI touch point as an agenda item (at the top of the agenda and not the end) for regular team meetings.
- Project members should draw on links to resources (e.g., at home institutions) around relevant EDI training and guidance (e.g., inclusive language, etc.) in order to build confidence and competence in discussing EDI.

1.5.2 Gathering information and opinions

The project team have sought to collate opinions and evidence to inform our recommendations by consulting as widely as possible via the mechanisms of an online stakeholder workshop and by conducting interviews (see Annex A1). The stakeholder workshop, held on 12th December 2023, was attended by 56 people including 40 based in the UK, 9 based in the USA and further representatives from Argentina, Brazil, China and France. As seen in Figure 1-4, 71% of participants identified as male, and 27% as female. This is comparable to the wider UK space sector where 70% of workers are male and 29% female¹⁴. In terms of ethnicity, the attendees of the workshop were more diverse than the sector as a whole (workshop attendees were 64% White, the space sector is 89% White). However, it is notable that there were no Black attendees. Black people make up only 1% of the UK space sector workforce but 3% of the UK population as a whole¹⁴. The workshop was attended by a good mix of career stages and roles. It is worth noting that some participants self-identified with more than one of the academy roles.

While we tracked demographics for the interviews carried out, we have not included statistics here due to the small number of formal interviews conducted.

Figure 1-4: Demographic information for participants in the stakeholder workshop.

1.5.3 Evaluating our findings

The Met Office required the team to develop a set of key learner personas that can be used to test the recommendations for the TDSA. The personas adopted by the team are intended to cover a diverse range of social groups and capture a range of different barriers to participation, with the aim of encouraging greater inclusivity in the training provision offered by TDSA. Nevertheless, the team have been conscious of the danger that building social identity into learner personas will accidentally rely on or perpetuate unhelpful assumptions and stereotypes, and have chosen an approach where we avoid making assumptions about the social group identities of our learning personas. For further information, see Section 2.

The Phase 1 report has been reviewed by the project team and the Met Office, and by external reviewers. We are grateful for their feedback and insights. In Phase 2, as we write the Implementation Plan, we will also seek further input from groups that specialise in improving access of under-represented groups to STEM.

¹ Bonavita, M., Schneider, R., Arcucci, R., Chantry, M., Chrust, M., Geer, A., Le Saux, B. and Vitolo, C., 2023. 2022 ECMWF-ESA workshop report: current status, progress and opportunities in machine learning for Earth System observation and prediction. *npj Climate and Atmospheric Science*, 6(1), p.87. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-023-00387-2> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

² Space Skills Alliance, 2023. Space Sector Skills Survey 2023, <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/space-sector-skills-survey-2023> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

³ National Science and Technology Council, 2022. Interagency Roadmap to Support Space-Related STEM Education and Workforce <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/09-2022-Interagency-Roadmap-to-Support-Space-Related-STEM-Education-and-Workforce.pdf> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

⁴ <https://blog.metoffice.gov.uk/2022/11/24/funding-boost-for-earth-observation-sector/> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

⁵ What qualification levels mean: England, Wales and Northern Ireland. <https://www.gov.uk/what-different-qualification-levels-mean/list-of-qualification-levels> (last accessed 26/02/24)

⁶ Scottish Credit and Qualifications Framework (2019) Qualifications can cross boundaries <https://scqf.org.uk/media/q3ji03tw/qualifications-can-cross-boundaries-aug-23.pdf> (last accessed 26/02/24)

⁷ Learning and Development: A Comprehensive Guide <https://www.aihr.com/blog/learning-and-development/> (last accessed 23/01/24)

⁸ How to develop a career progression framework <https://www.leapsome.com/playbooks/how-to-create-career-progression-framework> (last accessed 23/02/24)

⁹ Clardy, A., 2018. 70-20-10 and the dominance of informal learning: A fact in search of evidence. *Human Resource Development Review*, 17(2), pp.153-178. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484318759399> (last accessed 26/02/24)

¹⁰ Comparing Facilitation, Coaching, Mentoring and Teaching <https://www.scrum.org/resources/comparing-facilitation-coaching-mentoring-and-teaching> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

¹¹ Government Digital and Data Profession Capability Framework, 2023 <https://ddat-capability-framework.service.gov.uk/> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

¹² Met Office, 2022. Embedding machine learning and artificial intelligence in weather and climate science and services: A framework for data science at the Met Office 2022-2027 <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/binaries/content/assets/metofficegovuk/pdf/research/foundation-science/data-science-framework-2022-2027.pdf> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

¹³ Royal Meteorological Society, 2023. RMets EDI Survey 2023 <https://www.rmets.org/rmets-edi-survey-2023> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

¹⁴ Space Skills Alliance, 2021. Demographics of the UK Space Sector <https://spaceskills.org/census-demographics> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

¹⁵ Haacker, R., Vara, M., Sloan, V., Montañó, P., Davis, C., Landolt, S. and Briggs, S., 2023. Improving postdoctoral training programs through alumni perspectives and experiences-A study of NCAR's Advanced Study Program. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-22-0029.1> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

¹⁶ House of Commons Science and Technology Committee, 2023. Diversity and Inclusion in STEM. <https://committees.parliament.uk/publications/34531/documents/190060/default/> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

2 Learner personas and barriers to entry

2.1 Summary

We have developed fictional representations of individuals who could benefit from a future Transatlantic Data Science Academy (TDSA), known as “learner personas” (summarised in Table 2-1). The personas can be used as an evaluation tool to check that plans for the TDSA are fit-for-purpose and accessible to a diverse audience.

The personas we have developed reflect a variety of different features:

- **Career stages**, including recent graduates joining the workplace for the first time and those in mid- to late career stages who might have a broader range of learning needs, beyond deepening technical skills, to management, leadership, development, and strategy.
- **Interests**, including those that are already practicing in one of the TDSA roles who are interested in upskilling further in the same area, those who are keen to transition to a new area incorporating some of their existing skills and building new ones, and those who are interested in building or transitioning to a new career in Earth Observation (EO) without an existing data science background.
- **Sectors**, including academic, public and the private sector. Organisations across these sectors are active in the weather and climate domain, contributing across a spectrum from “blue-skies” research to highly applied research for the development of public and/or commercial products and services.
- **Aspirations**, whether that is to switch careers, requiring the development of new skills in novel (to them) areas, or to advance their careers in largely the same discipline.
- **Prior skills and experience**, for example, from a data background, an environmental background, a combination of both, or neither a data nor environmental background.
- **Learning needs**, often a combined reflection of career stage, interest, sector, aspiration and existing education and skills.
- **Learning preferences**, for example formal online or in-person training, informal on-the-job learning.
- **Access to resources**, for example new graduates may be able to access learning opportunities as part of a formal programme and may have fewer professional responsibilities, such as managing teams or meeting large project deadlines, enabling more freedom to manage their own time and to allocate more time to learning.

	Early career stage	Mid-career stage	Late career stage
Data engineering	<p>Sophia (persona 1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computer science graduate • Wants to work in weather /climate <p>Priya (persona 3)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PhD in computational chemistry • Wants to change career path 		
Data science	<p>Tim (persona 2)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geography master’s • Wants to build understanding of data science 		<p>Ridley (persona 7)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team leader • Wants to move from AI company to Earth system/climate domain
Research software engineering	<p>Arbor (persona 4)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computational physics master’s • Early career RSE wants to understand applications to EO 	<p>Alice (persona 6)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EO scientist • Wants to expand skills in RSE 	
Data assimilation		<p>Carlos (persona 5)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leads team in agricultural research • Wants to expand skills in EO/DA applications in agriculture 	<p>Raj (persona 8)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manager • Wants to broaden technical skills

Table 2-1: A summary of the learner personas we have developed (see Section 2.5.3)

A key issue that has informed our construction of learner personas is the lack of diversity in the UK science and technology workforce. One of the reasons for the lack of diversity in the wider science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) workforce is historic low rates of participation in higher education for some demographic groups, as well as barriers to training faced by some groups. Barriers include financial restrictions, time restrictions, employment status (e.g., precarious contracts), inability to travel to the training location, lack of inclusive/accessible design, belonging and inspiration (under-represented groups).

Our recommendation is that the TDSA offering should be flexibly designed to help learners overcome these barriers. Learners should be made aware of the range of learning options available to them and supported to prioritise the learning options that best suit their career aspirations, existing skill set, means to pay and ability to access.

2.2 Introduction

“Learner personas” are fictional representations of individuals who could benefit from a future TDSA. This section outlines a series of personas that reflect a wide range of factors which should be considered during the process of designing new products and services that could be delivered by the proposed TDSA. They are for illustrative purposes only, to demonstrate the complexity of learning needs, preferences, and potential barriers individuals face when trying to advance their data science-related careers in weather and climate.

The personas can be used as a tool to sense check whether existing learning provision available on the market is fit-for-purpose and accessible to a diverse audience, rather than focusing solely on

finding and filling gaps in specific knowledge areas and skill sets. The personas are in no way exhaustive and are designed to guide thinking around how the TDSA can facilitate learning and development and promote equality and diversity through careful design of delivery formats and consideration of other factors that could enhance accessibility.

Our personas have been designed to reflect findings from secondary data sources that highlight a need for learning opportunities across a range of topics, delivered via a variety of learning modes and mechanisms, to provide flexibility for individuals to fit around existing professional and personal commitments.

2.3 Methodology

The personas outlined in this section are depictions of fictional individuals based on the experience of academics working across the University of Birmingham, UCL, University of Edinburgh, University of Exeter, University of Leeds, and University of Reading. These academics have regular interactions with industry professionals and colleagues with backgrounds in climate and weather and/or data science, data assimilation, data engineering, research software engineering, and EO. The personas have also integrated insights from initial workshops (with participants from both academic and non-academic organisations) and interviews with stakeholders. Further research into learner personas was conducted via a survey circulated to a group of staff at the Met Office.

A non-exhaustive literature search of both academic and grey literature was conducted to gather insights from previous work related to training provision for relevant job families across the weather and climate industry. This literature search aimed to uncover factors affecting the learning needs of workers in the EO sector as well as potential barriers to participation.

Our learning personas are intended to cover a diverse range of social groups and capture a range of different barriers to participation, with the aim of encouraging greater inclusivity in the training provision offered by TDSA. Whilst personas are useful for bringing intended learners to life, there are decisions to be taken around which aspects to include; whether to focus solely on professional roles and activities, or to also include demographic/social indicators that are more related to identity. Consideration of identity is useful to help capture the different barriers to participation faced by different groups. However, there can be a danger that building social identity into learner personas will accidentally rely on or perpetuate unhelpful assumptions and stereotypes, particularly given the lack of diversity of those within the project leadership. We have chosen an approach where we avoid making assumptions about the social group identities of our learning personas, and instead consider that any or all the barriers we have identified from the literature described below could apply to any, or all, of our learning personas. In this way we focus on the barriers that we can influence, and do not risk alienating people or perpetuating stereotypes by assuming social group identities within the personas.

During Phase 2 we will seek input from our institutions' widening participation and awarding gap teams, as well as those involved in the Athena Swan gender equality charter and the Race Equality Charter to further inform our understanding of the barriers and evidence-based initiatives to remove them. In line with our equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) principle "nothing about us without us", we will also engage with organisations that specialise in improving access of under-represented groups to STEM including BBSTEM¹⁷, Black Girls Code¹⁸, In2Science¹⁹, and other organisations via the networks of our EDI consultant.

2.4 EDI landscape

2.4.1 EDI in EO and related subjects

The job families under consideration for the TDSA (data science, data engineering, data assimilation, research software engineering, and EO) are all strongly numerate and/or technical with an emphasis on mathematical and computational methods. Therefore, they share many of the general issues facing such roles across industry and public sector organisations, where there is high demand for skills and experienced workers, a lack of standardised role definitions and associated professional frameworks for training and career progression, and rapid change in the skills and technologies required by the workforce²⁰. The difficulty in hiring experienced workers increases the importance of workplace training to “skill up” existing employees, in addition to designing learning for individuals looking to start their careers in EO, climate and meteorology.

A key issue that has informed our construction of learner personas is the acknowledged lack of diversity in the UK technology sector workforce. Diversity is known to be beneficial to organisational performance²¹ but is generally lacking in the UK data and artificial intelligence (AI) ecosystem²². Diversity in the workforce has particular relevance when developing AI systems, where it can help avoid the incorporation of social biases into new applications²³. This type of embedded bias can be problematic beyond AI systems, and in general, in the design and development of any products and services to a diverse community of users.

One of the reasons for the lack of diversity in the wider technology workforce is historic low rates of participation in higher education for some demographic groups, as well as barriers to training faced by some groups. At the same time, there is evidence that individuals from particular social groups (e.g. women, minoritised ethnicities, disabled people, carers and more) face particular barriers to learning in STEM. These barriers arise in all parts of the education system including access to Triple Science and high-quality STEM teaching at school (ethnicity, disability, and social class)²⁴ and challenges in navigating different intersecting identities (gender, ethnicity, and social class)²⁵ throughout academic careers. Barriers to participation in higher education include financial restrictions (including cultural attitudes to loans and debt), geographical restrictions (related to financial limitations, caring responsibilities, cultural expectations that may have gender and age aspects) that are compounded by lack of appropriate STEM role models²⁶. Widening participation initiatives at universities tend to focus on socio-economic background, while attainment and awarding gap initiatives may focus on race and ethnicity and disability.

Focusing on the environmental sector, a 2023 study reviewed the experiences of postdoctoral researchers who were trained through the Advanced Study Program (ASP) of the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) in the US²⁷. The study concluded that the atmospheric sciences and geosciences, in general, suffered from a lack of diversity, and that minority groups could feel excluded (see also other sources²⁸). Mentoring and a deliberate focus on inclusion helped to counteract these effects and retain women and other under-represented groups within the workforce. The report also showed that most researchers in atmospheric sciences were initially trained in academic settings but went on to jobs in industry or other non-academic contexts, with a recommendation that training provision should consider these career outcomes in its design. Finally, the report suggested that many researchers valued “non-technical” training in project management, grant writing, writing and other transferable skills as key to their career success, with a recommendation that these skills should be explicitly taught during researcher training programmes. These findings are incorporated into our learner personas, which include learners in a variety of

organisational settings (academic and non-academic) and in roles requiring a mix of skills (technical and non-technical).

Looking at the EO workforce in the commercial sector, a 2020 report based on an industry survey stated that “employees in the EO services companies are highly qualified; 90% of them hold a university degree and around 60% hold a post-graduate degree. The gender balance of the sector seems to be essentially stable at 30% of women and 70% of men.”²⁹ However, anecdotal evidence from the UK’s Space Placements in Industry (SPIN) scheme since 2013 shows that for EO/environment roles there can be twice as many female applicants as male. This demonstrates that there is significant interest from women, but that this does not necessarily translate into the workplace.

2.4.2 Efforts to improve EDI

2.4.2.1 Meteorological organisations

The Met Office, for example, drafted a set of four equality objectives for the period 2020-24, which included:

- Objective 1 – Engaging with and understanding the diversity of our people and those we serve.
- Objective 2 – Advancing equality of opportunity.
- Objective 3 – Increasing representation of under-represented groups at all levels.
- Objective 4 – Zero tolerance to bullying, harassment and discrimination.

Supporting the achievement of these objectives, the Met Office have an ED&I Working Group, a Diversity Council, an ED&I Committee, and a range of staff networks³⁰ representing the interests of all nine protected characteristics. Better understanding of employee experiences with inclusive design being used to drive improvements, is one area of focus³¹, with specific relevance to the TDSA.

In the US, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), have drafted three goals outlined in their Diversity and Inclusion Strategic Plan 2020-2024:

- Goal 1 – Workforce diversity: recruit and attract a diverse, highly capable workforce.
- Goal 2 – Workplace inclusion: build a work environment that promotes inclusion.
- Goal 3 – Sustainability: build sustained and adaptive leadership commitment to a diverse and inclusive NOAA through accountability, data, and education.

Clear objectives and actions have been developed to support progress towards each of the goals³².

2.4.2.2 Professional societies

In the US, the American Meteorological Society (AMS) have a similar goal to create “*an inclusive, equitable and welcoming culture that fosters creativity, innovation, and collaboration because we seek to be equitable*”³³. The AMS have developed several supporting initiatives to make progress against this goal, including their Early Career Leadership Academy, scholarships, and developing a Framework for the Advancement of Inclusion, Equity, and Justice in the Weather, Water, and Climate Enterprise³⁴. The American Physical Society (APS) develop and implement a range of programs to improve physics education including promoting the recruitment and inclusion of under-represented minorities in physics, supporting the recruitment, retention, and career development of women physicists, and providing greater inclusion, engagement, and representation for lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) physicists³⁵.

In the UK, relevant professional societies are beginning to recognise EDI as an important area to be working on within their respective sectors following EDI concerns being raised to them through

member surveys. The Institute of Physics (IoP) have several initiatives to broaden diversity in the physics community including Project Juno, a gender equality award for university physics departments and related organisations to recognise actions they have taken to address gender equality and to foster a more inclusive working environment. The IoP are also piloting a scheme to support A-level students from non-traditional backgrounds into studying physics at leading universities³⁶ and are a member of the LGBTQ+ Physical Sciences Network³⁷. The Royal Meteorological Society (RMetS)³⁸ appear to be earlier in the process and not yet focused on designing more comprehensive programmes and sector wide initiatives to address EDI issues. However, efforts are being made to embed EDI thinking into their governance structures, strategies, and goals.

2.4.2.3 Higher education

In the UK higher education sector, a non-profit organisation, Advance HE, supports higher education providers to be more inclusive, to address systemic inequalities, and to advance education to meet the evolving needs of students and society. UK universities can apply to Advance HE to be awarded for their commitment to, and progress on, equality and diversity as outlined in Advance HE's equality charters³⁹. The Race Equality Charter aims to improve representation, progression and success of minority ethnic staff and students within higher education, which encourages institutions to reflect on, and actively attempt to remove, institutional and cultural barriers for minority and ethnic staff and students⁴⁰. The Athena Swan Charter supports gender equality within higher education and research and was originally established to advance the careers of women in science, technology, engineering, maths, and medicine (STEMM). The Charter now recognises work undertaken to address gender equality more broadly⁴¹. Notably, STEMM subjects are the most relevant for individuals looking to build a career in the EO sector.

Many UK universities are actively seeking to identify new ways to improve EDI within their organisations and to increase the number of students from under-represented groups accessing their education offerings and ensuring they feel safe and supported within their institution's environment. Similarly, within climate and meteorological related organisations and societies, there have been significant efforts to increase EDI within their organisations and the broader sector.

This section outlining the EDI landscape captures the key trends in the EO sector or related sectors pertaining to the experience of under-represented groups and efforts to improve EDI. The next sections capture the types of learning barriers that may be experienced by individuals from these groups, which may need to be addressed to increase EDI in EO careers within climate and weather organisations. We have however, in the following sections, made a conscious decision not to associate specific types of barriers with specific groups to avoid the potential risk of stereotyping.

2.5 Learner personas

2.5.1 Summary

2.5.1.1 Career stage

Learners are likely to be at different career stages. This might range from learners early on in their careers, studying undergraduate and postgraduate degrees, to being a recent graduate joining the workplace for the first time or commencing a PhD. Needs, interests, learning preferences and commitments will differ at different stages. Those in mid- to late career stages might have an even broader range of learning needs, beyond deepening technical skills, such as management, leadership, development, and strategy, or need a greater breadth of understanding across a range of topics and job functions to enable them to better manage different teams and new projects.

2.5.1.2 Interest

Five key interest areas were identified during the inception phase of the TDSA including data science, data engineering, data assimilation, research software engineering, and EO. There are three main groups of learners, those that are already practicing in one of the identified areas who are interested in upskilling further in the same area, those who are keen to transition to a new area incorporating some of their existing skills and building new ones, and those who are interested in building or transitioning to a new career in EO without an existing data science background.

2.5.1.3 Sector

Learners may come from different sectors, including academic, public and the private sector. Organisations across these sectors are active in the weather and climate domain, contributing to novel research, to highly applied research for the development of public and/or commercial products and services. Like interest areas, learners may be looking to transition between sectors. For example, finding ways to apply their predominantly research backgrounds to develop solutions for the public and private sectors. Whether a learner is looking to stay within the same sector, or move between sectors, it is important to think about how learning and training can support cross pollination of ideas and maximise knowledge exchange between sectors.

2.5.1.4 Aspirations

Learners will have a wide range of aspirations, whether that is to apply their existing data-related skill sets in the weather and climate domain with the promise of solving climate and environmental, social, or economic challenges; to develop more specialist skills and techniques to apply in their existing weather and climate-related roles; or to improve their understanding of colleagues work, and in so doing, improving their communication and engagement. Learners may aspire to switch careers, requiring the development of new skills in novel (to them) areas, or they may aspire to advance their careers in largely the same discipline.

2.5.1.5 Education, skills & prior learning

It is to be expected that potential learners will come from a range of educational and skills backgrounds, from a data background, an environmental background, a combination of both, or neither a data nor environmental background. The latter group has been omitted from the learner personas we have drafted, in part because a more effective learning route for this group may be to obtain a foundational understanding of data and/or environmental disciplines, prior to accessing learning offerings provided by the TDSA. As such, the personas below assume most learners will have at least a bachelor's level qualification in a related subject. That said, learners' technical competencies may range significantly from having a foundational level of knowledge, through to having a niche skill set used to execute distinct tasks and functions associated with a highly specialised job role.

2.5.1.6 Learning needs

Learning needs are generally a combined reflection of career stage, interest, sector, aspiration and existing education and skills. However, in general, learners will either need to improve their understanding of climate and weather science, and/or underpinning Earth system science; or to improve their data-science related skill sets; or a combination of both. At the most nuanced end of the learning spectrum, there are those who need to understand highly specialised data-science skills and techniques that have been developed in the context of climate and weather applications or have the most promising potential to be applied in this context. It is this group that might be of interest in the development of the TDSA as they are the most likely to be underserved by existing market offerings. This is examined in more detail in Sections 3 and 4.

2.5.1.7 Access to resources and learning preferences

Access to online resources is ubiquitous particularly when developing a foundational understanding of data sciences and environmental sciences. There are certain types of learning that may even lend themselves to being accessed online, particularly practicing the application of new data technologies and techniques. Despite the perception that online resources facilitate ease of access, it is important to consider that neurodiversity can be a factor in how effective and accessible online resources are to some individuals, with some preferring face-to-face learning opportunities. Disability could also be a significant factor shaping preferences for online or face-to-face learning opportunities.

Learners who have recently graduated, who are looking to transition between career pathways, or who work in the sector but are currently unemployed, are unlikely to have the support of an employer to provide financial support to access learning opportunities. Furthermore, many employers do not invest significantly in the professional development of their employees, and the onus to upskill is on the employee to use their own time and finances to invest in their development. Where learners are under real or perceived pressure to learn in their own time (such as evenings and weekends), personal commitments, such as caring for dependents, becomes a greater factor for consideration.

Career stage might affect the ability to access resources, or at least the perception, of being able to access resources and learning opportunities. On the one hand, those in the early stages of their career might be able to access learning opportunities as part of a formal programme. For example, an employer's graduate scheme. Similarly, those in their early career stages may have fewer professional responsibilities, such as managing teams or meeting large project deadlines, enabling more freedom to manage their own time and to allocate more time to learning. On the other hand, those learners who are more established in their careers may feel confident in their value to their employer and feel that they can ask for reduced working hours or flexible working, including sabbaticals, or for financial support to access learning opportunities. Furthermore, those in mid- and late career stages may, by the nature of their roles, be exposed to new knowledge through their day-to-day activities such as increased attendance at events and conferences, greater participation in networks that provide learning opportunities, or engagement with external stakeholders; albeit these might be more informal learning opportunities.

Those in later career stages, particularly if they are already experienced in their field and who are not looking to transition in their careers, might prefer more tailored and applied learning opportunities that can fulfil a specific project need or strategic priority. Whereas more broad-ranging and exploratory types of learning could be more suited to learners in early to mid-career stages who might be in the process of determining their career direction or looking to pivot slightly in their current career pathway.

Some learners, particularly early career professionals, prefer to receive formal recognition for the training and development they have undertaken through certification, accreditation, or the receipt of other types of awards; with a view to being able to provide evidence to their current and future employers.

2.5.2 Survey findings

A small group of twelve individuals, working at the Met Office, responded to a survey that sought to identify key learning and development needs. Of the limited sample, eleven identified as research software engineers (RSEs).

Ten individuals responded that they didn't know the types of relevant training and development opportunities that were available to them, half thought that there were limited opportunities to learn "on-the-job" and from colleagues, and more than a third (five individuals) perceived that there were financial constraints preventing them from being supported by their employer to access training.

Ten of the respondents indicated that they preferred to learn during working hours, with nine indicating that they preferred face-to-face workshops held at their work location. Two-thirds indicated a preference for peer-to-peer learning between colleagues and five individuals indicated they would like mentorship from senior colleagues. At least half indicated that they preferred online live classes (six individuals) or online self-paced tutorials (seven individuals); a slightly higher number than those indicating that they preferred face-to-face workshops offsite (five individuals).

Perhaps unsurprisingly, these responses point to a general preference for convenience with regards to learning. This is further supported by secondments and collaborative research projects with other organisations being poorly rated, with only two respondents favouring each respectively. Master's and PhD programmes were also less preferred with only one respondent indicating these as a preference. However, it should be noted that half of respondents indicated they already had a PhD, with the other half indicating that they held a master's degree.

2.5.3 Detailed personas

Persona 1: Recent BSc computer science graduate looking to further expand data engineering applications in weather and climate forecasting.

Name: Sophia | **Career stage:** Early | **Interest:** Data engineering | **Sector:** Academia

Aspirations: To apply their data management skill set to the data challenges in the weather and climate domain.

Education, skills, and prior learning: BSc in computer science. Sophia is skilled in deploying data processing pipelines in the cloud, data management systems, Python programming, data preprocessing. They have experienced formal training through coursework and hands-on experience through their dissertation.

Learning needs: Sophia needs to learn the fundamentals of weather and climate sciences, expand their cloud computing skills, gain experience with advanced big data technologies (Apache Spark and Google BigQuery), and to upskill in geospatial Python programming packages.

Access to resources and learning preferences: Sophia has access to online resources but would prefer a deep dive week-long course on the fundamentals of weather and climate sciences with an option of a hackathon. They would be keen to have accreditation at the end of their learning.

Persona 2: Recent MSc geography graduate enrolled in a graduate scheme at a national government agency providing weather and forecasting services.

Name: Tim | **Career stage:** Early | **Interest:** Data science | **Sector:** Public

Aspirations: To carve a niche within his organisation and to engage colleagues more confidently on the scientific aspects of their work.

Education, skills, and prior learning: MSc in geography. Tim has significant knowledge of the ecological and physical characteristics underpinning Earth systems and a basic level of understanding about geographical information systems (GIS) and principles of EO. Tim's current role involves rotating across divisions within his organisation every three months to understand different aspects of organisational delivery and he is regularly deployed to different projects.

Learning needs: Tim needs to build his understanding of data science, programming in Python and machine learning (ML) to be able to begin developing applications of weather and climate data in the real world.

Access to resources and learning preferences: Tim is adept at online learning. He would like to receive a certification for learning he undertakes that he can put down on his CV. He is working full time, but his employer wants to invest in his professional development, with a willingness to pay for learning and to provide flexibility in his work schedule to attend training.

Persona 3: Final year PhD student in computational chemistry looking to enter weather and climate forecasting domain.

Name: Priya | **Career stage:** Early | **Interest:** Data engineering | **Sector:** Academia

Aspiration: To change career pathways and apply her research and software engineering skill sets to weather and climate applications including speaking to people in the industry to help with their decision processes.

Education, skills, and prior learning: BSc and MSc in chemistry. Priya has skills in computational chemistry, C++, high performance computing (HPC), reproducible data processing pipelines, Docker, and database management (SQL). She has received formal training on C++ from the national HPC provider but otherwise learning has been largely self-directed.

Learning needs: Priya needs to learn more about climate data formats and geospatial techniques, and to broaden her data analysis skill set.

Access to resources and learning preferences: Priya attends conferences in the computational chemistry field and has access to resources through her university. She accesses online self-paced learning for more technical upskilling, but she would like to interact more with a community of people in the weather and climate space.

Persona 4: Early career RSE interested in learning more about EO and remote sensing.

Name: Arbor | **Career stage:** Early | **Interest:** Research software engineering | **Sector:** Academia

Aspirations: To become an expert in the computational aspects of EO and to make more effective contributions to the domain scientists he works alongside.

Education, skills, and prior learning: BSc physics and MSc computational physics. Arbor has skills in numerical methods, data analytics, and is a predominantly self-taught programmer. He has learned some fundamentals of EO “on-the-job”.

Learning needs: Arbor needs to understand the in-depth computational requirements of EO as he is slowly gaining responsibility for a wider range of activities within his university’s RSE team, across various domains.

Access to resources and learning preferences: Arbor would prefer to learn in-person, face-to-face, with lots of practical components (e.g. carpentries-style). His university employer provides a variety of formal and informal training. His immediate management are supportive of his ambitions and happy for him to spend up to 25% of his time on learning activities.

Persona 5: Senior data assimilation scientist, leading an agricultural research team, interested in advancing data assimilation techniques in agricultural applications.

Name: Carlos | **Career stage:** Mid | **Interest:** Data assimilation | **Sector:** Research

Aspirations: To optimise agricultural practices, reduce pesticide use, and to maximise crop yields through the integration of advanced data assimilation techniques and satellite observations.

Education, skills, and prior learning: BSc in agricultural sciences, PhD in agronomy. Carlos has skills in data assimilation, remote sensing techniques, satellite observations, crop yield modelling, agricultural optimisation, data analysis, and interdisciplinary collaboration. He has previously attended specialised courses and seminars in data assimilation, remote sensing, and crop yield modelling.

Learning needs: Carlos needs to advance his techniques in merging remote sensing data and satellite observations with crop yield models for more precise agricultural optimisation. He would like to keep abreast of cutting-edge developments in data assimilation and remote sensing within the agricultural sector to support collaborations with agricultural companies and government organisations. There is a limited availability of advanced courses specifically tailored to the integration of remote sensing and data assimilation techniques within crop yield models and Carlos has difficulty finding highly specialised training opportunities due to the niche nature of his work.

Access to resources and learning preferences: Carlos regularly attends agricultural conferences, collaborates within professional networks, and has access to research resources through his research institute and industry collaborators. He prefers specialised courses, seminars, and conferences that offer in-depth knowledge and practical applications, and enjoys collaborating with experts from diverse fields.

Persona 6: Mid-career EO scientist (0.8 FTE) at a national government lab looking to expand skill set in research software engineering.

Name: Alice | **Career stage:** Mid | **Interest:** Research software engineering | **Sector:** Public

Aspirations: To progress her career with more advanced RSE skills. She has had some thoughts about migrating into a more formal RSE-type role.

Education, skills, and prior learning: BSc in geophysics and meteorology, PhD in geophysics. Further to her academic background, Alice has skills in critical thinking, management, and some basic data analysis skills in Excel. She has undertaken some self-learning in her own time but has not taken any formal technical training since her PhD. She has, however, attended some management training as part of her job.

Learning needs: Alice needs to develop generic scientific computing skills (e.g. data analytics using Python, git, and bash). She lacks the overview to know what exactly she should be focusing on to maximise return on time investment.

Access to resources and learning preferences: Alice has been following online tailored courses to fit in around family life. She prefers studying in her own time as she does not want to impose on her employer who is accepting of her working remotely.

Persona 7: Data science team lead at an AI company looking to change careers and apply skills in Earth systems and climate science domain.

Name: Ridley | **Career stage:** Mid to late | **Interest:** Data science | **Sector:** Private

Aspirations: To deploy their skills and expertise in the Earth and climate science domain, potentially working for an Earth and climate science company or even setting up their own start-up in the area.

Education, skills, and prior learning: BSc in computer science and MSc in data science. Ridley has skills in advanced AI techniques, building machine learning functionality, MLOps and data flow pipelines, in addition to management and leadership experience. Formal training has been mainly formal through their undergraduate and postgraduate degrees, in addition to attending major AI conferences and managerial training courses throughout their career. Otherwise “on-the-job” has been the primary mode of learning.

Learning needs: Ridley is looking to expand their Earth and climate sciences expertise including exposure to Earth systems risks, the underlying physics, and data.

Access to resources and learning preferences: Ridley does not have immediate access to resources through their employer and would be undertaking learning in their free time. Their preference is for a mix of online and face-to-face activities with like-minded individuals. They would be willing to devote some evenings and weekends to learning over a period of a few months.

Persona 8: Manager of an atmospheric data assimilation group at an operational weather centre looking to further expand technical skills in data assimilation.

Name: Raj | **Career stage:** Late | **Interest:** Data assimilation | **Sector:** Public

Aspirations: To expand his technical understanding beyond his current area of expertise, enabling him to better support and guide his team and improve his organisation’s operational data assimilation system.

Education, skills, and prior learning: BSc and MSc in mathematics. Raj has skills in atmospheric data assimilation, operational weather systems, in addition to management, leadership, strategic planning, problem solving, and operational management. During the last fifteen years of his career, he has been working in a technical role at his organisation, specialising in developing its land surface data assimilation system.

Learning needs: Raj has had limited exposure to the finer technical details of other areas within data assimilation and would like to increase his knowledge beyond the land surface domain to be able to better guide and understand the work of his team. He has had difficulty finding structured learning programs tailored to his senior-level role with a focus on operational data assimilation.

Access to resources and learning preferences: Raj has access to internal resources within the weather centre, mentorship from experienced team members, and opportunities to collaborate with technical experts within and outside the organisation. He prefers comprehensive workshops, advanced seminars, and access to technical documentation or resources.

2.6 Learning barriers and solutions

2.6.1 Barriers

Types of barriers	
Cost/financial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost and financial constraints may be direct (lack of funding from employer, lack of funds if self-funding) or indirect (lack of funds to support travel and accommodation, lack of access to suitable technology, or lack of time due to needing to work for financial sustainability). • Financial capacity to undertake unpaid learning, forgo paid employment for a period, or pay for supplementary support to manage training around personal commitments may often be a significant determinant of individuals' decision on whether to proceed with learning opportunities.
Time	<p>Limited time availability can originate from multiple sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caring responsibilities may prevent access to learning during non-standard hours (evening, night, weekends) or times when caring needs are greater (e.g., school holidays). • Full-time employment with no support from employer can limit use of working hours to access learning. • Variable workload and deadlines may affect the ability to access learning in a sustained, consistent way. • Managerial responsibilities might limit ability to engage deeply in technical training or commit large blocks of time. • Individuals with health conditions or disability may find their overall capacity for work and activity reduced, limiting the amount of training that can be achieved in a given period. • Avoiding employee stress and burnout needs to be considered when designing learning formats to ensure expectations of individuals to manage sustained high workloads are not reinforced and facilitated.
Employment status	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Precarious contracts may have an indirect impact on access to learning due to real or perceived financial or time constraints. • Staff on fixed term contracts may not be able to commit to long duration training opportunities. • Managers may take a different approach to development of staff on fixed term, or other types of non-permanent contracts. • A dilemma for life partners (e.g., spouses or any other couple) where each has a specialist job role, relates to the difficulty of both partners obtaining jobs at the same institution or within a reasonable commuting distance from each other. Employees in this situation may be less committed to their current employer.
Physical location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many learner characteristics (e.g., citizenship status, caring responsibilities, disability, marital status, community involvement, financial situation) may restrict ability to participate in face-to-face learning away from the usual place of residence. This will likely be affected by location of training, public transport links etc.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some physical disabilities and health conditions can limit access to particular training locations (e.g., wheelchair access, hearing loops).
Belonging and inspiration (representation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of representation in the existing workforce and/or visibility of role models might affect members of some groups (e.g., women and members of minoritised ethnicity groups). • Lack of representation can reduce exposure of children and young people to potential careers and reduce diversity at the recruitment stage. • Lack of representation can reduce the sense of belonging for existing staff and lead to attrition. • Stereotypical assumptions may influence accessibility of learning leading to necessity of learning outside work or outside of the home.
Lack of inclusive/accessible design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online learning can be challenging for some individuals if not properly designed. • Some health conditions and disabilities can make learning materials difficult to interpret (e.g., fonts/colours for printed materials, electronic documents unsuitable for use with a screen reader).

2.6.2 Solutions

Types of solutions	
Financial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The financial burden of learning should be shifted away from the individual or financial support should be made available to those who can demonstrate limited financial resources to draw upon. • Employers should ensure learning costs are covered for existing employees, recognising that the benefits of learning reside with the employer, as well as the individual. This might include course fees, travel, and accommodation to access training, or carer's costs such as additional childcare. • Learning formats that can be delivered alongside employment may help overcome financial barriers, including but not limited to: "on-the-job" learning, degree apprenticeships, secondments, and part-time courses. Enabling individuals to maintain income while learning is another useful option.
Time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners should not be expected or required to access learning outside of their usual working hours. Courses, particularly in-person, should be available at a range of times to suit different learner needs. • Learning opportunities can be structured in a way that enables the learner to access in small instalments or modules to allow them to build into the working day or around other responsibilities. Appropriate support systems should be in place to enable this learning approach.
Tailored learning plans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners should be made aware of the range of learning options available to them and supported in their decision making to

	<p>prioritise the learning options that best suit their career aspirations, existing skill set, means to pay and ability to access.</p>
Mixed learning formats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning formats need to avoid reinforcing expectations of individuals to work for sustained periods of time with high levels of working and learning commitments to avoid stress and burnout. • Online learning resources can provide much needed flexibility, but consideration should be given to how individuals are accessing these resources in and around work and personal commitments. • Online resources and other static resources can often be useful for those who want to undertake self-paced learning. • Live online learning formats may be beneficial for those who find that they learn better from personal interaction with others. • In-person learning formats may be more appropriate for those who find their ability to concentrate severely diminished when accessing online learning resources, while online learning may be more appropriate for those who find social interaction challenging. • In-person learning can bring additional professional and wellbeing benefits from social interactions, engagement, networking opportunities, and “corridor conversation”. • If held during an individual’s working hours, learning may help to diminish the potential guilt felt by individuals who have caring responsibilities outside of work. Format may be important here. Learners might feel they should be accessing online learning formats available to them at any time of the day or night, as is often the case with online learning resources.
Learning support networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many learning offerings include some aspect of peer-to-peer support network which may or may not be facilitated by a trainer. These provide informal spaces in which to test ideas, resolve misunderstanding of content and allow access to support outside any “live” or face-to-face sessions. • Peer-to-peer support networks including any or all of communities of practice, writing retreats, hackathons, body-doubling work sessions (where people team up as accountability buddies for specific focus periods), group coaching for career development (facilitated) and online community fora, can extend access to learning and support feelings of belonging.
Mentoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mentoring has been shown to be particularly useful for those from under-represented communities – providing 1-2-1 access to a subject matter expert could provide opportunities to grow in confidence and broader understanding of the community i.e. learning the “unwritten rules” that members of under-represented groups may not be aware of otherwise. • For those individuals new or newly returned to learning, mentors focussed on the learning process itself would likely reduce the risk of drop out, and again build confidence, supporting the continuation of learning.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For mid- to late career learners, whilst it would undoubtedly be beneficial to join a broader learning community, this is not always practical in terms of time, or because of concerns of inhibiting the learning experience of e.g., early career scientists. With cohorts of learners mixed across different institutions this is less of a risk, but mentoring could be a useful alternative for late career learners.
Career outreach and experience programmes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities to increase the exposure and access of children and young people from under-represented groups to potential careers can provide a route to increase diversity in the talent pool. Examples include career events, work experience placements, internships and bursaries. Legal positive action measures such as targeted advertising or exclusive opportunities can encourage take up from a particular group⁴². To achieve success, it is important that these activities do not themselves create further barriers such as the direct or indirect costs of attendance
Inclusive design	<p>The application of inclusive design principles such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online resources being constructed with accessibility and useability in mind including subtitles for videos, built in ability to modify font size, colour way etc., accessibility guides used in production of learning materials. Beyond online resources alone, learning formats need to be tailored to account for neurodiversity. Diversity in human cognition and brain function will affect individuals' ability to effectively process and retain new skills and understanding (as acknowledged under "Mixed learning formats" section above).

¹⁷ Black British Professionals in STEM <https://bbstem.co.uk/>

¹⁸ <https://www.wearebgc.org/>

¹⁹ <https://in2scienceuk.org/> (last accessed 20/02/2024)

²⁰ Fearn, Harriss & Lally (2023) Data science skills in the UK workforce. POSTnote 697. <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/POST-PN-0697/POST-PN-0697.pdf>.

²¹ Dixon-Fyle et al (2020) Diversity wins: How inclusion matters. McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/diversity-and-inclusion/diversity-wins-how-inclusion-matters#/>

²² Fearn, Harris & Lilly. Ibid.

Young, E., Wajcman, J. and Sprejer, L. (2021). Where are the Women? Mapping the Gender Job Gap in AI. Policy Briefing: Summary. The Alan Turing Institute. https://www.turing.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2021-03/where-are-the-women_public-policy_summary-report.pdf (last accessed 27/02/2024)

²³ Centre for Data Ethics and Innovation (2020). Review into bias in algorithmic decision-making. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/957259/Review_into_bias_in_algorithmic_decision-making.pdf (last accessed 27/02/2024)

²⁴ Government report on Diversity and Inclusion in STEM, 2023, <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm5803/cmselect/cmsstech/95/report.html>

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- ²⁶ Moote, J., Archer, L., DeWitt, J., & Mac Leod, E. (2019). Comparing students' engineering and science aspirations from age 10 to 16: Investigating the role of gender, ethnicity, cultural capital, and attitudinal factors. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 109(1), 34–51. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jee.20302>.
- ²⁷ Haacker et al. 2023 Improving postdoctoral training programs through alumni perspectives and experiences - A study of NCAR's Advanced Study Program: <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-22-0029.1> (last accessed 27/02/2024)
- ²⁸ Berhe, A.A., Barnes, R.T., Hastings, M.G. *et al.* Scientists from historically excluded groups face a hostile obstacle course. *Nat. Geosci.* **15**, 2–4 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-021-00868-0>
- ²⁹ <https://space-economy.esa.int/article/72/a-closer-look-at-the-latest-earth-observation-services-industry-trends> (last accessed 27/02/2024)
- ³⁰ Met Office Equality, Diversity and Inclusion [Equality, diversity and inclusion - Met Office](#) (last accessed 27/02/2024)
- ³¹ Met Office Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Strategy January 2022 v1.2 [met-office-equality-diversity-and-inclusion-strategy-v1.2.pdf \(metoffice.gov.uk\)](#) (last accessed 27/02/2024)
- ³² NOAA Diversity and Inclusion Strategic Plan 2020-2024 <https://www.noaa.gov/sites/default/files/legacy/document/2020/Dec/NOAA%202020-2024%20Diversity%20and%20Inclusion%20Strategic%20Plan.pdf> (last accessed 27/02/2024)
- ³³ AMS Equity and Inclusion at AMS [Equity and Inclusion at AMS - American Meteorological Society \(ametsoc.org\)](#) (last accessed 27/02/2024)
- ³⁴ Tipton, E., L. White, and P. Higgins 2022: *Framework for the Advancement of Inclusion, Equity, and Justice in the Weather, Water, and Climate Enterprise*. An AMS Policy Program Study. The American Meteorological Society, Washington, D.C. <https://doi.org/10.1175/framework-for-equity-inclusion-justice-2022> (last accessed 27/02/2024)
- ³⁵ APS Programs [Programs Overview | APS Physics](#) (last accessed 27/02/2024)
- ³⁶ [Supporting Diversity and Inclusion through the Bell Burnell Graduate Scholarship Fund | Institute of Physics \(iop.org\)](#) (last accessed 27/02/2024)
- ³⁷ [LGBT+ Physical Sciences Network | Institute of Physics \(iop.org\)](#) (last accessed 27/02/2024)
- ³⁸ Equity, Diversity and Inclusion at RMetS <https://www.rmets.org/equity-diversity-and-inclusion-rmets> (Last accessed 20/02/2024)
- ³⁹ Advance HE About Us <https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/about-us#purpose> (last accessed 27/02/2024)
- ⁴⁰ Advance HE Race Equality Charter <https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/equality-charters/race-equality-charter> (last accessed 27/02/2024)
- ⁴¹ Advance HE Athena Swan Charter <https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/equality-charters/athena-swan-charter>
- ⁴² UK Government (2023) Positive Action in the Workplace (last accessed 27/02/2024) <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/positive-action-in-the-workplace-guidance-for-employers/positive-action-in-the-workplace> (last accessed 21/02/2024)

3 Career frameworks, roles alignment and overlaps

3.1 Summary

In this section we consider the alignment and overlaps between the roles being considered by the TDSA (data scientist (DS), data engineer (DE), data assimilation scientist (DAS) and research software engineer (RSE)) so that we can make recommendations about a training programme.

We aim to develop a clear skills requirements roadmap for each role and career stage to empower individuals to navigate career transition through self-directed skills gap analysis.

We have evaluated three **existing career frameworks for their relevance to the TDSA roles**:

- Government Digital and Data Profession Capability Framework (DDaT):
 - Offers the most detailed role and skill definitions for DS, DE and RSE roles. Does not include a DAS role.
 - Enables technical and managerial career pathways for software developers.
 - Skills are broad relative to the TDSA's specific technical needs.
- Government Science and Engineering Career Framework (GSE):
 - Categorises roles into four families based on science and engineering applications.
 - Offers less detailed skills compared to DDaT and TDSA, but highlights transferability between roles.
- Vitae Researcher Development Framework (RDF):
 - Designed for researchers in higher education, with broad categories and definitions of skills.
 - Domains such as “personal effectiveness”, “research governance and organisation” and “engagement, influence and impact” could be relevant for professional/transferable skills in TDSA.
 - Significant resources available for aligned learning needs analysis and personal development planning.

Overall observations:

- Existing frameworks are generic and lack domain-specific skills like EO, weather/climate, and computational skills.
- DDaT focuses on defining skills but lacks guidance on framework usage, unlike GSE and RDF.
- GSE emphasises transferability between roles.

To study the alignment and overlaps of the roles, we first analysed the **skills required for each of these roles** in a general sense.

- **Data scientist (DS):** Analyses data using computational and mathematical techniques, emphasising responsible data practices. Expertise includes data cleaning, visualisation, modelling and machine learning (ML). Collaboration with scientists from other domains and effective communication are crucial.
- **Data engineer (DE):** Builds and maintains data infrastructure, ensuring reliability and adhering to findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR) principles. Scripting skills are crucial for system integration and data access. Collaboration with DSs, assimilation scientists, and software engineers is essential.

- **Research software engineer (RSE):** Provides technical support, developing, reviewing, and maintaining code across various areas. In smaller teams, may also fulfil DS or DE roles.
- **Data assimilation scientist (DAS):** Applies expertise in data assimilation numerical methods and treatment of observations. Requires strong theoretical understanding, physical knowledge and coding skills. Knowledge of ML becoming increasingly important.

These definitions should not be regarded as prescriptive. We recognise a spectrum within each role, and note that there will be differences in emphasis for different organisations and people.

To evaluate the **alignment and overlaps of the technical skills** required by the different roles we use a skills matrix (Annex A2) and visualise the results using radar diagrams (Section 3.5). Our analysis looks at typical, key skills for each of the roles, but it is important to emphasise that every job is different and the TDSA should ensure it maintains flexibility.

For this analysis we concentrated on proficiency, alignment, and overlap across three categories of skills:

Earth Observation (EO) skills:

- Data assimilation scientists: highest requirement for proficiency, covering diverse and deep skills.
- Data scientists and data engineers: skills required vary depending on project focus.
- Research software engineers: lowest requirement for proficiency in diversity and depth.

Mathematical and statistical skills:

- Data scientists and data assimilation scientists: high skills requirements with complementary expertise:
 - Data scientists: Machine learning models and techniques.
 - Data assimilation scientists: Data assimilation theory, numerical analysis and uncertainty quantification. ML is becoming more important.
- Data engineers: moderate skills needed, lower depth than data scientists.
- Research software engineers: less proficiency required compared to other roles, but may be familiar with applications in specific areas.

Computer and data science skills:

- Data scientists, data engineers and research software engineers: highly skilled with distinct strengths:
 - Data scientists: exploration, modelling, visualisation, ML.
 - Data engineers: databases, querying, data pipelines, preprocessing.
 - Research software engineers: research software development, user interfaces, graphical processing unit (GPU)/ML code.
- Data assimilation scientists: proficient in visualisation, exploration and scripting, but overall depth less than other roles.

While focusing on technical proficiencies, we recognise the importance of professional and transferable skills as outlined in the Vitae Researcher Development Framework.

Recommendations

Academy focus:

- By building a bespoke career framework that highlights this granular division of the skill sets of each role, the TDSA will empower individuals embarking on any of these four career paths.

- The TDSA should capitalise upon the existing overlaps but also foster the key differences.
- Having one Academy for the four roles will enable cross-role mobility and upward progression.
- The TDSA should implement a modular training framework for flexibility and personalised learning.

Technical skills training:

- The TDSA should offer foundational EO training for all, with advanced modules for specific roles.
- The TDSA should provide basic ML training for all to address growing importance.
- The TDSA should emphasise targeted upskilling in computer and data science.

Professional and transferable skills training:

- The TDSA could offer core training for essential skills at the early career level.
- The TDSA could provide tailored training for more senior researchers.

3.2 Methodology

Our approach to building a coherent picture relating to the four TDSA roles underneath the EO umbrella has relied on a methodology involving different elements.

Review of relevant career frameworks:

We evaluated relevant career frameworks to understand whether these may adequately capture the different roles (and their overlaps) within the EO domain:

- the Government Digital and Data Profession Capability Framework (DDaT),
- the Government Science and Engineering Career Framework (GSE) and,
- the Researcher Development Framework (RDF)

We also compared the information gathered through this review with the currently implemented career structure at NOAA. We note that the Alan Turing Institute is developing a relevant competency framework: AI Skills for Business Competency Framework⁴³. We have not analysed this framework here as it was still draft at the time of writing this report. Furthermore, we excluded the Space Skills Alliance Space Competencies Recognition and Assessment Framework Tool (CRAFT) since it does not include any data science, data assimilation or data engineering competencies⁴⁴.

Development of a skills matrix:

To investigate the four roles, we produced an in-depth matrix covering various skills required for the different roles with input from the TDSA team and augmented by information derived from the stakeholder workshop.

- The different skills have been organised into subgroups (encompassing technical skills, transferable skills, and fluency in different technologies and methods).
- The skills for the different roles have also been scored using an integer scoring system ranging from 0 to 4. A score of 0 indicates no relevance. The integer scores of 1 to 4 mirror the four levels as defined within the DDaT Framework: awareness, working, practitioner and expert.
- To aid in the identification/visualisation of alignment, and common and distinguishing factors across the roles we have produced radar diagrams derived from this roles/skills matrix.

We recognise that the skills analysis we have provided can only represent the knowledge within the project team and the relatively small sample of stakeholders consulted, as well as the existing literature we have referred to. From an equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) perspective, it could be beneficial to sample opinions more widely.

3.3 Existing career frameworks

We have analysed and compared some relevant existing career frameworks to:

- Look at how the various data related roles are defined and categorised.
- Compare and contrast the existing frameworks and consider their pros and cons.
- Consider the relevance and applicability of the frameworks to the TDSA.

Our conclusions and recommendations based on this analysis of career frameworks are discussed more fully in Section 7.

3.3.1 Government Digital and Data Profession Capability Framework

The Government Digital and Data Profession Capability Framework (DDaT)⁴⁵ provides information about digital, data and technology roles in the UK Government and the skills needed to perform them.

Matching roles and descriptions.

The DDaT roles are categorised into groups, with the data roles and software development roles being of most relevance to the TDSA. The individual roles within these categories are shown in Table 3-1, where we have marked in bold where the DDaT role matches the roles defined within the terms of reference of the TDSA. Where the DDaT match the TDSA roles, the DDaT descriptions align with our descriptions in Sections 3.4 and 3.5. However, we have added additional detail in terms of technical skills typical of each TDSA role. The DDaT includes no DAS role. The DA discipline is not widespread outside of the EO sector.

DDaT data roles	DDaT software development roles
1. Data analyst	7. Development operations (DevOps) engineer
2. Data engineer	8. Frontend developer
3. Data ethicist	9. Software developer
4. Data governance manager	
5. Data scientist	
6. Performance analyst	

Table 3-1: Roles within DDaT which are of particular relevance to the TDSA. Bold shows roles which match those defined for the TDSA. Note a lack of data assimilation scientist role.

Skill levels and mapping

DDaT uses four skill levels: awareness, working, practitioner, expert (note these levels map onto the 4 levels we use in Section 3.5).

DDaT has an extensive list of skills associated with each role. Some of the skills relevant to the TDSA include: [data analysis and synthesis](#), [data development process](#), [data innovation](#), [data integration design](#), [data modelling](#), [metadata management](#), [problem resolution \(data\)](#), [programming and build \(data engineering\)](#).

While extensive, DDaT skills remain more generic than the skills we have defined in Section 3.5.

However, we also note a number of other relevant skills defined within DDaT such as: [communicating between the technical and non-technical](#), [technical understanding](#), and [testing](#).

Career stages and pathways

DDaT has varying numbers and definitions for career stages for each role (e.g., the DE role has 4 career stages, software developer has 9 stages). The software developer role has both technical and managerial career pathways, meaning that promotion can be pursued by taking on strategic technical

responsibilities, as well as by line-management of other staff. This dual pathway to more senior roles is not in the framework for the DE and DS roles.

3.3.2 Government Science and Engineering Career Framework

The Government Science and Engineering Career Framework (GSE)⁴⁶ sets out a standard for careers across GSE. It explains the technical skills, knowledge and experience required to be an effective scientist or engineer in government.

We note that the Met Office science profession career framework (currently under development) is based on the GSE framework.

The GSE presents 4 job families (see Figure 3-1) that describe the different GSE roles across government with suggested development pathways.

Figure 3-1: The four job families within the GSE Career Framework and where those families sit according to HOW (x-axis) and WHEN (y-axis) science or engineering knowledge is applied.

GSE job families	GSE skill categories	GSE skill levels	GSE career stages
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. GSE affiliate 2. GSE specialist 3. GSE cross-discipline 4. GSE deep specialist 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building and applying knowledge • Communication science and engineering (S/E) for government • Developing the GSE community • Technical oversight and management • Broad thinking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness: Understanding of how that skill could be developed and why it is required • Practitioner: Regular use of that skill • Leading: Ability to mentor others in developing this skill 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foundation • Emerging • Experienced • Leader

Table 3-2: A summary of the GSE Career Framework.

The GSE categorises skills into five groups (see Table 3-2) and although these break down with some added details, it offers considerably less detail compared to the DDaT framework, and substantially less than the skills we have defined within the TDSA project (discussed in Section 3.5).

We believe all TDSA roles would likely fit within the GSE “deep specialist” job family. This family encompasses roles that require a high level of science or engineering training in a specific area and the core element of their role is to utilise and develop that knowledge and experience daily.

The GSE highlights transferability and flexibility between roles more than the DDaT and RDF.

3.3.3 Vitae Researcher Development Framework

The Vitae Researcher Development Framework⁴⁷ (RDF) has been developed for researchers in higher education (not those in full-time training). It is intended to be used by researchers, managers, trainers etc. and is independent of role. It defines four broad skill domains (see Figure 3-2) with progression across phases from 1 to 5.

Figure 3-2: The RDF defines four domains and twelve sub-domains, encompassing the knowledge, intellectual abilities, techniques and professional standards to do research, as well as the personal qualities, knowledge and skills to work with others and ensure the wider impact of research.

Clearly, the categories and definitions of skills under the RDF are broad compared with the other frameworks. The knowledge and intellectual abilities are extremely broad compared with our discussion of technical skills in Section 3.5. Nonetheless, RDF Domain B (Personal effectiveness), Domain C (Research governance and organisation) and Domain D (Engagement, influence and impact) are potentially of relevance for professional/transferable skills under the TDSA.

3.3.4 Discussion

All the frameworks we have considered are generic (i.e., relevant for data related roles in general). Of the career frameworks we evaluated, DDaT has the most detail in terms of defining roles and skills, although there is no data assimilation role within DDaT (or within the other frameworks considered). None of the frameworks reference domain specific skills such as EO, weather/climate, computational and mathematical/statistical skills and knowledge.

Specific notable features of the frameworks that the TDSA may wish to adopt include:

- Career progression along dual pathways (technical path and managerial path) – DDaT.
- Transferability between roles – GSE
- Aligned resources for learning needs analysis and career planning – RDF

The DDaT framework focusses on defining the skills associated with a job role and provides little guidance on using the framework in practice. In contrast, the GSE and RDF have extensive guidance and tools for individuals and managers using the career framework.

In terms of US transferability, NOAA has revoked its career framework in 2023⁴⁸. Line/Staff Officers have been following their own local evaluation procedures. An interview with a NOAA/university-based DS in February 2024 highlights the fact that there is no prescribed nomenclature of professions nor detailed work tasks. Hence the NOAA and university frameworks enable transferability from the UK due to their flexibility.

Based on this analysis we discuss options for career development framework appropriate for the TDSA in Section 7.

3.4 The roles of data scientist, data assimilation scientist, research software engineer and data engineer.

A detailed analysis of the skills required for the different roles follows. These are our interpretation of the core skills required by people working in each role. These are not intended to be prescriptive. We recognise that there are likely to be differences in emphasis across different organisations and across teams within them. Career stage is recognised as another dimension but is not explicitly considered in this section. We provide some more discussion regarding how skills are expected to vary with career stage in Section 3.5.

3.4.1 High-level summaries of the roles (basic/essential technical skills)

3.4.1.1 *Data scientist*

A DS applies a range of computational and mathematical techniques to derive insight from data. They have a strong understanding of the scientific method, experiment design and how data acquisition, analysis, and processing can be responsibly and robustly used in this context. They are able to select and combine a range of core techniques including data cleaning and pre-processing; exploratory data analysis; data visualisation; statistical modelling; ML; and software development. They will have working knowledge of some specialised topics including natural language processing; artificial intelligence; computer vision; optimisation; simulation; high-performance computing; and application design/deployment. They should be comfortable collaborating with scientists from other domains and gain sufficient domain knowledge to guide their work effectively. They should be able to communicate with stakeholders from different backgrounds, clearly explaining methods, outcomes and limitations/biases in data analysis. They should always work in a responsible and ethical manner, respecting best practice in data governance and responsible innovation.

3.4.1.2 *Data engineer*

A DE combines skills of infrastructure developers and data stewards, and is typically responsible for developing, implementing, testing and maintaining infrastructure solutions such as databases and large-scale processing systems. They are responsible for building extract-transform-load (ETL) workloads, data acquisition, querying, processing, and modelling pipelines, as well as data APIs. They may be required to write scripts in several programming languages to enable integration and communication of several systems, as well as linking data from disparate sources. They are expected to recommend ways to improve data reliability, efficiency and quality, and ensure data meet the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR). They would work closely with DSs and DASs to provide datasets suitable for operational and research and development purposes, as well as with Software Engineers to ensure the usability of data APIs.

3.4.1.3 *Research software engineer*

A RSE is required to work closely with both researchers and operational staff providing technical support. They may be involved in the development of new code or the review of others' code (e.g., peer reviewing a researcher's code or helping optimise and migrate code so that it is suitable for use

in a production environment), at any point of the software development lifecycle. They may support a range of development activities (e.g. model development, desktop user interfaces, web-development). In teams not large enough to require specific DSs or DEs, an RSE may additionally fulfil these roles.

3.4.1.4 Data assimilation scientist

A DAS can work in the development of new data assimilation (DA) methods, the application of DA to different systems and in the development of observation operators and observation processing systems. For those developing DA methods they need a good grounding in the theory of DA and relevant mathematics, as well as the ability to develop, implement and test computational methods, sometimes within operational systems. Knowledge of the properties of the observational data is also important, e.g., developing quality control systems, quantifying uncertainty, building observation operators. They also need knowledge of physical modelling processes, in order to evaluate and improve the impact of the data assimilation systems on model forecasts. There is currently a lot of research on combining ML with DA, so knowledge of ML methods is expected to become increasingly important.

3.4.2 Professional and transferable skills

These high-level descriptions emphasise the **technical skills** required for each role, but professional and transferable skills are also a common requirement. The Vitae Researcher Development Framework (see Section 3.3.3) details the behaviours and attributes of successful researchers and provides a useful resource for defining the professional and transferable skill set of the roles considered here. The professional and transferable skills of the TDSA roles are encapsulated in domains B, C and D (lower right, lower left and upper left quadrants in Figure 3-2).

3.5 Alignment and overlap

We have conducted a detailed analysis of the technical skills of the different roles to understand (i) the level of proficiency required in different areas, (ii) the alignment between roles, and (iii) the potential overlaps. We have organised our analysis into four dimensions encompassing:

- EO skills
- Mathematical and statistical skills
- Computer and data science skills
- Technological skills

We acknowledge that individual skill proficiency within a role can vary depending on career stage, the nature of a specific job role, projects and interests. Hence, our main analysis has focused on typical skills possessed by people working in hands-on roles. Further discussion about variation with career stage is provided in Section 3.5.3.

We consider many EO, mathematical and statistical and computer and data science skills (see Table 3-3) as stable, i.e., not changing rapidly over time. Technological skills on the other hand *are* changing rapidly and we discuss those currently relevant in Section 3.5.1.4. We recommend that the Academy would need to review their relevance every few years.

EO skills	Mathematical and statistical skills	Computer and data science skills
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satellite platforms • Radiative transfer • Retrieval (<i>also intended to encompass other related techniques</i>) • Other observation platforms (e.g., weather radar, ground based remote sensing, and other commonly used observing systems) • Atmospheric physics • Dynamical meteorology/oceanography • Land surface dynamics • NWP/NWP parameterizations • Ensemble forecasting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty quantification • Bayesian statistics • Design of experiments • Regression, classification, clustering • Deep-learning/transformer models • Graph neural networks • Normalising flows • Generative models (e.g., large-language models (LLMs), diffusion models) • Computer vision • Natural language processing (NLP) • Data assimilation theory • Numerical linear algebra • Spatial grid generation • Numerical methods for partial differential equations (PDEs) • Numerical optimisation of functions • Nonlinear dynamical systems • Computational fluid dynamics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Database management • Database querying (SQL/noSQL) • Data transfer; extract, transform, load (ETL) • Data linkage • Building data pipelines • Data preprocessing/wrangling • Data understanding/exploration • Data visualisation • Statistical modelling • Training machine learning models • Deploying machine learning models (MLOps) • High performance computing (HPC) • Cloud infrastructure • Shell scripting • Preparing code for GPU/ML-stack porting • Developing user interfaces • Develop, maintain, extend research software

Table 3-3 The technical skills for which we have analysed alignment and overlap between the roles. See also Annex A2 which shows a skills matrix for these technical skills.

We have used **radar diagrams to visualise skill alignment and overlap** between the roles for the EO, mathematical and statistical, and computer and data science skills:

- The various skills (see Table 3-3) are shown around the circumference of the diagrams (Figure 3-3 to Figure 3-5).
- The level of skill for each role is depicted by the distance away from the centre of the circle (on a scale of 0 to 4: 0 for not relevant, 1 for awareness, 2 for working, 3 for practitioner and 4 for expert). These levels match the DDaT framework (see Section 3.3.1).

The roles of DS, DE, RSE and DAS are shown in different colours with some transparency to help display the overlaps.

Aside from the technical skills is the added dimension of **professional and transferable skills**. The requirements for these skills are expected to be broadly similar across each of the roles (see Section 3.5.2).

3.5.1 Technical skills

3.5.1.1 EO skills

Our analysis has taken into account a range of typical EO skills (see Table 3-3). Following the methodology outlined above we have produced a radar diagram in Figure 3-3 which allows us to understand the proficiency requirements, alignment and overlap of different roles in EO. See also the EO skills matrix in Annex A2.

In terms of proficiency, it is clear that DASs have the highest skill requirements in EO, both in terms of diversity and depth of skills. DSs and DEs may also be skilled in EO, but this may depend on the exact project they engage in. Research software engineers seem to have the least skill requirements in EO, in terms of diversity and depth of skills.

Figure 3-3: Radar diagram showing EO skills (see Table 3-3). The various skills are shown around the circumference. The level of skill (proficiency) for each role is depicted by the distance away from the centre of the circle (on a scale of 0 to 4: 0 for not relevant, 1 for awareness, 2 for working, 3 for practitioner and 4 for expert). The roles of data scientist, data engineer, research software engineer and data assimilation scientist are shown in different colours.

In terms of alignments and overlaps, it appears that there is (or there could be) some alignment between DASs, DSs, and DEs since they all seem to cover a broad range of EO skills, although with different levels of proficiency. However, it appears there is little alignment between the RSE role and other roles in terms of data observation skills.

3.5.1.2 Mathematical and statistical skills

Our analysis has considered a wide range of mathematical and statistical skills that could be relevant to the TDSA (see Table 3-3 and Annex A2) and we show their levels of proficiency, alignment and overlap for the different roles in Figure 3-4.

It is clear that both DAS and DS have high skill requirements in mathematics and statistics, both in terms of the diversity and depth of skills. Note however that DAS skills seem to lie primarily on data assimilation theory, numerical linear algebra, numerical optimisation, numerical methods for PDEs, and uncertainty quantification, whereas DS skills lie instead on ML models and techniques. The landscape is changing for DA scientists who will be expected to require more ML skills in the future. DEs may need a set of mathematical and statistical skills, but the required level of depth appears to be much lower than that of a DS or a DAS. Finally, the RSE role seems to be less proficient in mathematics and statistics compared with the other roles, but RSEs may be nonetheless highly familiar with mathematical/statistical models underlying the software that they are developing.

Figure 3-4: Radar diagram showing mathematical and statistical skills (see Table 3-3). See Figure 3-3 for more details.

3.5.1.3 Computer and data science skills

Our analysis has also considered a wide range of computer and data science skills that could be relevant to the TDSA academy (see Table 3-3 and Annex A2). As before, our analysis focused on the computer and data science skills typically exhibited by a person exercising one of the four different roles. We have also produced the radar diagram in Figure 3-5 based on our rating methodology (see also computer and data science skills matrix in Annex A2).

In terms of proficiency, it appears that DSs, DEs, and RSEs require high skills in computer/data science, in terms of diversity and depth of skills. DSs' core strengths are on data exploration, data modelling, data visualisation, and training and deploying ML models; DEs' strengths are on database management, database querying, data linkage, data transfer, data preprocessing/wrangling, and building data pipelines. The RSE specialises on maintaining, developing, and extending research software; developing user interfaces; and preparing code for GPU/ML-stack porting. The DAS role appears to require some data visualisation, data exploration/understanding, shell scripting, and HPC skills; however, the level of computer/data science skills depth of a DAS does not appear to need to be on par with the level of other roles (in an aggregated sense).

In terms of alignment and overlap, it is interesting to note once again that the three most skilled roles in data/computer science appear to be highly complementary. As shown in Figure 3-5, the core strengths of a RSE do not overlap much with those of a DE, and those of a DE also do not overlap much with those of a DS.

Figure 3-5: Radar diagram showing computer and data science skills (see Table 3-3). See Figure 3-3 for more details.

3.5.1.4 Technological skills

Technological skills are skills related to a specific technology that DS, DE, DAS, and RSE roles use in their daily work. These technologies include: databases (e.g., SQL), code environments (e.g., Visual Studio (VS)), coding languages (e.g., Python), etc. The use and application of these technologies can change over time, as new technologies appear that offer a better solution or service. For that reason, we have not developed radar diagrams to show overlap and alignment, but have included our

findings in the skills matrix (Annex A2). The matrix provides an indication of the current situation regarding these technical skills. The matrix shows that RSE, DE and DS roles need at least an awareness of almost all of these technologies, with different levels of proficiency required for different roles. For the DAS role, the main technologies required are coding and scripting technologies, and code development environments.

3.5.2 Professional and transferable skills

Requirements for professional and transferable skills are expected to be fairly consistent across the roles, with the depth of understanding and application increasing with seniority level. We have identified the following professional and transferable skills needed by the roles, loosely listed in the order of their importance as the seniority level increases:

- project and time management,
- communicating information in different formats,
- collaboration,
- grant writing,
- data governance, data privacy and regulatory concerns,
- responsible innovation (including sustainability, ethics and EDI),
- leadership

The Government Digital and Data Profession Capability Framework (DDaT) can also be considered when developing a program for developing transferable skills.

3.5.3 Variation in skills with career stage

It is expected that proficiency in technical and transferable skills will vary with career stage.

Recent graduates and new starters (called early career stage 1 in Section 7) are likely to join the TDSA with a STEM qualification. As such their understanding of TDSA-relevant topics is likely to be highly theoretical, with little hands-on experience of technical skills. If this is their first role after completing an undergraduate degree, they may not have much experience in professional personal effectiveness skills such as time management, project management and working effectively in collaborative environments.

Those early career staff with a few years' experience in their field (called early career stage 2 in Section 7) are likely to be considered knowledgeable (i.e. at least "practitioner", perhaps "expert", from the DDaT terminology) in at least one given technical field. In terms of transferable skills, they may be ready to explore skills leading to further responsibility (e.g., planning, management, leadership) setting the stage for promotion to a mid-career level.

Mid-career staff are typically well-established in their role, having deep technical skills in their area. A mid-career individual may need to deepen their technical skills further to specialise in specific areas within their job-domain or to broaden their skills with a view to potentially switch to adjacent job roles (e.g., from a data engineering role to a data science one). In terms of transferable skills, they may have various job responsibilities requiring managerial and leadership skills.

Many senior roles involve either management of a team or strategic leadership across a broad area. At this level, breadth of knowledge and technical skills may be more important than depth. The senior staff member needs sufficient understanding of an area in order to lead a team of practitioners working in a specialism/establish a specialist strategy, but they also need to be able to scan across disciplines and integrate ideas from several areas. They are expected to have high proficiency in leadership and management skills.

3.5.4 Summary of alignment and overlap

In this section we defined the skills needed by the different roles. This is not intended to be prescriptive, but to provide a useful guide to help identify how the Academy can be efficiently aligned and focussed. We acknowledge that individual skill proficiency within a role can vary depending on career stage, the nature of a specific job role, projects and interests. Hence, our main analysis has focused on typical skills possessed by people working in hands-on roles.

EO Skills: Our study suggests that DAS, DS, and DE all seem to cover a broad range of EO skills, though with different levels of proficiency, depending on a number of factors as alluded to in Section 3.5.1. Our study reveals that DASs are likely to have had the greatest need for EO skills, whereas RSEs are likely to have the least exposure. Indeed, it appears there is little alignment between the RSE role and other roles in terms of EO skills.

Mathematical and statistical skills: Our analysis suggested that the two highest skilled roles in mathematics and statistics – DS and DAS – appear to be highly complementary. DASs expertise appears to be primarily in data assimilation theory, numerical linear algebra, numerical optimisation, numerical methods for PDEs, and uncertainty quantification, whereas a DS expertise concentrates instead on ML models and techniques. However, in the future the DS and DAS roles may align more closely as both ML and DA methodologies become more closely aligned in the weather and climate sector. The other remaining roles typically have lower exposure to mathematical and statistical skills.

Computer and data science skills: Our analysis also suggested that the three highest skilled roles in computer and data science – DS, DE, and RSE – have distinctive skill sets. In particular, the core strengths of a RSE do not overlap much with those of a DE and those of a DE also do not overlap much with those of a DS. The DAS role typically has less exposure to computer/data science skills compared with the other roles.

Technological skills: The use and application of technologies can change rapidly over time, as new technologies appear that offer a better solution or service. We analysed specific technologies including databases, code environments and coding languages. We found that RSE, DE and DS roles need at least awareness of almost all of these technologies, with different levels of proficiency required for different roles. For the DAS role, the main technologies required are coding and scripting.

Our findings have immediate implications for possible training provision since different roles will likely benefit from more exposure to some areas than others, for up-skilling purposes. This analysis and granular look at the breakdown of skills by role also provides a blueprint for those who wish to transition across roles and/or will be managing a team of diverse roles.

3.6 Recommendations for Academy focus

Our analysis provides a detailed understanding of the skill sets required for each TDSA role, highlighting both similarities and differences. A bespoke career framework for the TDSA, which highlights this division of skill sets, will provide a valuable roadmap. Having one academy for the four roles will enable cross-role mobility and upward progression.

In terms of developing its training provision, the TDSA should capitalise upon the overlaps in skill requirements between roles, but also foster the key differences. A modular framework within the academy is recommended to ensure flexibility, allowing different people to engage with relevant training as needed.

A breakdown of recommendations per skill area follows.

3.6.1 Technical skills training

In relation to EO skills, it is recommended that a foundational course is offered to all early career staff across the different roles. This is based upon the finding that all roles display a need for awareness of the individual areas of EO. Progression modules which go deeper into specific areas could then be offered/signposted to the DAS, DS and DE roles. In particular, NWP training for the DA scientists and DS would be beneficial.

In the area of mathematical and statistical skills it is recommended that all roles are provided training in the basics of ML. This contrasts with our findings above, as currently only the roles of DS and DE showcase high levels of proficiency in this area, but ML is becoming pervasive in weather and climate science and operations. A key proficiency area of the DAS is the mathematical foundation skills, therefore training provisions in these areas are essential. Existing training provisions could be signposted (see Sections 4 and 7).

Based on our findings, training needs in the computer and data science skills across the roles will need to be more disparate. This is the technical skill area where high levels in proficiency are role specific, particularly for the DEs, DS and RSEs. A recommendation for the Academy is to emphasise a modular framework so as to enable people to upskill in certain computer and data science skills and make use of existing offerings (see Sections 4 and 7).

The recommendations laid out here can be considered as a first pass on the easy wins for the Academy. A more structured learning framework which knits together the various training provisions for each role will require a decision to be made on a TDSA career framework (see Section 7).

3.6.2 Professional and transferable skills training

As outlined, professional and transferable skills are considered to be common across the four roles. This could enable the Academy to focus on a core offering for early and mid-career staff, with tailored training required for those at a more senior level. On the other hand, the Academy could choose to focus solely on technical skills and leave the professional and transferable skills to be provided by Academy partners' usual programmes.

⁴³ https://iuk.ktn-uk.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/Final_BridgeAI_Framework.pdf (last accessed 25/03/2024)

⁴⁴ <https://craft.spaceskills.org/> (last accessed 19/03/2024)

⁴⁵ <https://ddat-capability-framework.service.gov.uk/> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

⁴⁶ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/government-science-and-engineering-career-framework> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

⁴⁷ <https://www.vitae.ac.uk/researchers-professional-development/about-the-vitae-researcher-development-framework> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

⁴⁸ <https://www.noaa.gov/organization/administration/nao-202-511a-position-classification-of-scientific-research-positions> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

4 Capacity and gaps in UK training, learning and development, and career development provision

4.1 Summary

This section summarises the findings from our analysis of existing capacity and key gaps in the UK's provision of:

- training, learning and development, and
- career development

for data assimilation scientists (DASs), data engineers (DEs), data scientists (DSs), and research software engineers (RSEs) within the remit and aims of the TDSA. Note that we discuss career frameworks in Section 3.

This section identifies existing provision, highlights key gaps, and proposes potential opportunities to address these deficiencies. We focus on training to develop technical skills. Professional/transferable skills are discussed in Section 3.

4.1.1 Overall findings

- An extensive list of existing training provision can be found in Annex A3.
- While various training options exist for each role, there is a general lack of courses specifically tailored to the needs of TDSA disciplines, particularly Earth Observation (EO) and atmospheric science applications.
- Other key knowledge gaps: some mathematical techniques and elements of ML.
- The rapid development of technologies poses a challenge for training provision/providers.
- There is a need for an appropriate computing infrastructure to facilitate hands-on training.
- Career development pathways, particularly for DEs, RSEs and DSs working outside of industry, remain unclear and require standardisation.
- It is important to ensure career pathways that support deep specialist routes, as well as managerial routes.
- Funding limitations and other barriers can hinder access to training (see discussion of learning barriers and solutions in Section 2).

4.1.2 Role-specific findings and recommendations

Data assimilation scientists

- Existing capacity in training, learning and development:
 - In-person training limited to non-accredited, short, intensive courses offered by operational centres and universities.
 - Online resources are available, but focus on introductory topics.
 - Regular international conferences and learning from experienced colleagues provide additional development opportunities.
- Career development/progression: Often move from junior to mid-level by gaining expertise in a specific domain, then progress to senior roles via technical or managerial pathway.

- Gaps: knowledge/skills in numerical linear algebra, limited training in advanced data assimilation techniques, ML integration, and operational application.
- Opportunities: Develop updated textbooks and training programs, advocate for dedicated funding, introduce data assimilation modules into academic curricula.

Data engineers

- Existing capacity in training, learning and development:
 - Formal training offered through taught postgraduate courses in data science or ML, which can lack specific data engineering topics.
 - Online courses provided by cloud computing companies and large learning platforms cover role-specific skills (e.g., data pipelines and managing databases).
 - Professional DE exams and certificates are offered by cloud companies.
- Career development/progression: typically well-defined within industrial sectors. Career development in atmospheric science/EO sector is less defined, with the Academy potentially supporting development through collaboration and specialised programmes.
- Gaps: Lack of in-person training, courses focused on EO data and MLOps, and an overemphasis on platform-specific skills over foundational knowledge.
- Opportunities: Offer more balanced online courses incorporating both platform-specific skills and fundamental data engineering principles, explore alternative learning opportunities prioritising foundational understanding, and consider the Academy's role in supporting career development for atmospheric science/EO DEs. Consider whether the Academy should get involved in a new Level 5 Data Engineer Apprenticeship scheme being developed by BPP group.

Data scientists

- Existing capacity in training, learning and development:
 - Wide range of formal and informal training options, including taught postgraduate qualifications, online courses, bootcamps and apprenticeships.
 - Training content covers core topics like programming, ML, and statistics, and often includes specialisations like natural language processing or computer vision.
 - Emerging data science programs with an environmental/meteorological focus exist, but remain limited in number.
 - Practitioners leverage ad hoc and online training opportunities like MOOCs, online platforms and conferences.
- Career development/progression: Data science roles and entry routes are varied. Senior management roles less common for DSs, potentially requiring additional training for effective leadership.
- Gaps: Relatively few specialised training programs for environmental/meteorological applications, lack of standardisation in career pathways and progression within the EO/environmental sector.
- Opportunities: Increase the number of specialised data science programs with an environmental/meteorological focus, develop degree apprenticeship standards for environmental data science, create a community-supported platform for knowledge sharing, and explore opportunities for improving career development through standardised role definitions and certification programs tailored to the environmental sector.

Research software engineers

- Existing capacity in training, learning and development:
 - Carpentries curriculum provides basic introductions to software engineering topics but may be too introductory for most RSEs.

- Higher-level topic-specific technical training available, but suitability depends on individual needs.
- Introductory courses on EO, weather and climate available, but finding the right one can be challenging.
- Society of Research Software Engineering (SocRSE) offers an annual conference with workshops and additional satellite events, fostering networking and knowledge sharing.
- Regional RSE networks and regular webinars provide further learning opportunities.
- Career development/progression: Depends on institution and individual role (central versus embedded RSE). Efforts exist to clarify progression.
- Gaps: Limited access to advanced training in specific tools and techniques, lack of support for researchers transitioning to RSE careers, difficulty finding relevant training on EO domain expertise.
- Opportunities: Develop “deep dive” courses for specific tools/techniques, create targeted training programs for researchers transitioning to RSE roles, offer dedicated EO-focused training, improve accessibility and advertisement of existing training opportunities, address funding and time constraints through flexible funding models and workload management strategies, and explore RSE exchange schemes to facilitate skill sharing and collaboration.

4.1.3 Conclusion

Addressing the identified gaps in training provision for TDSA roles requires a collaborative effort involving academia, research institutions, professional organisations, funding bodies, and the TDSA (partners, learners and potential employers). By developing specialised training programs, improving accessibility, and establishing clearer career pathways, we can empower current and future TDSA professionals with the skills and knowledge necessary to excel in their fields and contribute to advancements in atmospheric science and EO.

4.2 Methodology

The information presented in Section 4 has been gathered through:

- Consulting existing reports on skills gaps in the EO and wider space sector.
- A wide search of web resources to identify existing opportunities.
- A stakeholder workshop (see Section 1) to explicitly identify existing capacity, opportunities, perceived gaps and barriers for making use of current training opportunities.
- Interviews with some stakeholders to provide more details on the findings from the other methods of data gathering.

In terms of equality, diversity and inclusion (EDI), the demographics of attendees at the stakeholder workshop are discussed in Section 1.5.2. We gathered further input to Section 4 from literature, interviews and from across the project team whilst adhering to the project EDI principles (Section 1.5.1).

4.3 Cross-role issues

4.3.1 Quality and trust in training provision

The current set of data-science related courses available can feel overwhelming, described by one stakeholder as “a bit like the Wild West”. Courses offer a wide range of quality and depth, making it difficult to determine their value beforehand. Attendees at the stakeholder workshop also noted a lack of awareness of what courses are available and which would be most appropriate for them.

Potential mitigation solutions for quality and trust include:

- Courses that follow a recognised curriculum (e.g., the Carpentries (see Annex A3)) provides a level of quality assurance.
- Implementing standardised accreditation processes could help identify high-quality training options (see Section 5).
- Community-driven insights: encouraging the sharing of experiences and reviews within the data science community can aid informed decision-making.

In Section 7 we recommend the development of a TDSA Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue (see Section 7.4)

4.3.2 General barriers for exploiting existing training opportunities

In the workshop some general difficulties were identified that are not specific to any particular role. Many workshop attendees felt that either lack of time or limited financial resources prevented them from making use of existing opportunities. Other reasons for not attending in-person courses were caring responsibilities and also a limited carbon budget for travel. The advantage of hybrid courses was recognised, though it was noted that from the trainer’s point of view this did not always provide an ideal environment for training.

We discuss such barriers and potential solutions more fully in Section 2.

4.3.3 General gaps in knowledge identified

- **Machine learning (ML):** this emerged as a key training gap, with topics like MLOps and combined data assimilation (DA) and ML lacking adequate coverage in existing offerings.
- **Mathematics:** knowledge of topics like numerical linear algebra was seen as beneficial for DAS in particular.
- **Data visualisation:** a lack of in-depth training in data visualisation for science students was highlighted.

The rapid development of new technologies often outpaces the creation of mature training materials. This presents a challenge for training providers and emphasises the need for adaptable solutions. Furthermore, there is a need for an appropriate computing infrastructure to facilitate hands-on training in the latest technologies. This may need to include a variety of GPU, HPC and cloud facilities.

Weather and climate sector issues

There are specific additional technical and ethical challenges in working with weather and climate data that are not covered by more general courses and may require bespoke approaches. For example:

- **Operational systems:** Provision of services 24 hours a day, 365 days a year, requires robust, efficient and reliable algorithms, compute infrastructures, workflows and tooling.
- **Data volumes and formats:** Most ML algorithms and data infrastructures are not equipped to deal with the vast amounts of EO and model data that are typically used in weather and climate. Datasets are not typically structured in formats that can be easily consumed by ML algorithms and data sharing (interoperability) is difficult.
- **Trust:** For weather and climate predictions, trust is critical, both for the scientific community and the public. Issues of bias, explainability and physical interpretation of data science and ML models require weather and climate domain knowledge alongside the data science techniques.

- **Net-zero:** Net-zero policies require measurement and reduction of the carbon footprint of data and compute resources. This is a high priority for the weather and climate sector, but is an emerging trend with little in the way of widely taught, accepted practice.

Potential role for the Academy to address these gaps

- Develop or support the development of targeted training courses in identified gap areas as above.
- Facilitate connections between experts and training providers to ensure up-to-date content.
- Promote and disseminate training resources to ensure widespread awareness and accessibility.

4.3.4 Other forms of training, learning and development

Annex A3 lists existing provision of a range of relevant training courses. A further broad catalogue is maintained by the Space Skills Alliance⁴⁹ which also includes some courses relevant to the TDSA. We have also identified other training, learning and development which we would like to highlight as important for the Academy.

On-the-job learning

On-the-job learning (informal, work-based learning and learning from peers and mentors) is recognised as key for learning and development (see Section 1.3) and is mentioned below in Section 4.5 in a number of areas.

At our stakeholder workshop, there were some mixed views on the value of on-the-job learning:

- It may be time-efficient in the short-term, and individuals will learn skills and tools needed to fit into their current team.
- However, it risks the team missing out on opportunities to bring in outside knowledge about new tools, or updated practices and skills that may be difficult to acquire via self-learning.

Train-the-trainer

In Section 4.8.1 below we discuss the development of a “train-the-trainer” approach within software and data carpentries. We feel this approach has application across all the roles we are considering within the TDSA. We highlight this within the early career stage 2 (those with a number of years’ experience in their field) in Section 7. The Data Science and AI educators programme developed by the Alan Turing Institute is highly relevant here.⁵⁰

4.3.5 Research degrees

Annex A3 focusses on training opportunities and does not have extensive information on research degrees, which provide key foundational training for many people entering the roles we are considering under the TDSA. We discuss research degrees further in Section 5.4.3.

We also discuss apprenticeships below in Section 4.6 and as a potential alternative route to a degree in Section 5.5.3.

4.3.6 Career development/progression of deep specialists

The career progression of deep technical specialists versus those transitioning into management can be very different. While management roles often lead to faster advancement, technical skills can stagnate due to time constraints.

- Current system: many organisations consider management a prerequisite for promotion, potentially hindering technical progress.

- Alternative pathways needed: explore models where technical specialists progress through upskilling, training, and external engagement instead of focusing solely on management responsibilities.
- Improved communication: clearly communicate these alternative pathways to early- and mid-career professionals to encourage advancement within technical specialties.
- Benefits of specialisation: Emphasise the value and reward of advanced technical expertise.

Recommendation: Implement and actively promote alternative career advancement paths for technical specialists to retain and reward expertise within the organisation (see further discussion in Section 7).

4.4 Capacity and gaps analysis for data assimilation scientists

4.4.1 Existing capacity

The existing capacity of training on data assimilation is centred on a handful of courses that are well known within the community. In-person training is limited to a small number of events that are organised by operational centres and universities and these tend to be intensive courses over a short period (of the order one or two weeks), with set dates each year, and so attendance may be difficult. In addition, there are online resources available but these lean more towards introductory topics covering only the basics of data assimilation.

The data assimilation community is relatively small and outside of the in-person and online training opportunities, personal development is restricted to regular international conferences, seminars, webinars and learning gleaned from other more experienced colleagues. Even in these cases though it has been noted that members of the community often feel they have no time to learn new technologies or to develop training materials for others.

To be promoted from junior to mid-level or even senior positions, a DAS requires a solid foundation of the underlying maths skills on which data assimilation techniques draw and a strong understanding of the data assimilation equations and how they are formulated. They also require a knowledge of the specific domain of the Earth system to which they are applying data assimilation (e.g., atmosphere, ocean, land), as well as an understanding of the available observations and their uncertainties. Importantly, they must also be able to implement appropriate techniques operationally, usually on HPC systems.

DASs will often gain expertise in a particular field within which that promotion is achieved, at least up to mid-level roles. This type of learning is not readily available and is often passed through colleagues with experience, either through line management or separate mentoring. For more senior roles, DASs can remain in technical positions, either developing and implementing new approaches or introducing new observation types into the system, or they can move into more management positions, overseeing the development of whole data assimilation systems.

4.4.2 Gaps analysis

A common theme raised in our workshop when talking about gaps in the provision of data assimilation and related courses, was the lack of basic knowledge and skills in numerical linear algebra to provide a base on which to apply advanced data assimilation skills. Following on from this, even where there is adequate prior knowledge, there is a lack of practical application in the form of training courses or structured activities that enable theories learned to be linked to operational usage.

Data assimilation faces the following **challenges**:

- Data assimilation is a rapidly evolving field with increasing data types, algorithms, and applications.
- Educational resources (textbooks, training) are lagging behind, particularly in areas like ML integration.
- Funding structures limit research opportunities for new DASs:
 - Competitive PhD funding often focuses on specific topics, excluding data assimilation.
 - Data assimilation rarely appears in MSc or undergraduate courses.
- Limited exposure discourages potential candidates from pursuing data assimilation careers.
- Many existing scientists come from backgrounds such as maths and physics requiring later training on EO and atmospheric science.

Potential **opportunities**:

- Strengthen educational resources:
 - Develop updated textbooks and training programs covering new data types, algorithms, and applications.
 - Integrate ML and its impact on data assimilation into training materials.
- Improve funding opportunities:
 - Advocate for dedicated funding for data assimilation research and PhD studentships.
 - Encourage broader funding schemes that include data assimilation within relevant thematic areas.
- Increase exposure in academic programs:
 - Introduce data assimilation modules into existing MSc and undergraduate curricula.
 - Offer specialised data assimilation programmes or short courses.

In summary, whilst there clearly is capacity for DASs to learn both basic and advanced techniques, those opportunities are few and far between. Gaps can be identified readily in how those techniques are applied in an operational context, and the funding required for updated resources, both in terms of physical documentation and training, is not available.

Overall, addressing the data assimilation skills gap requires collaborative efforts in education, research funding, and curriculum development to attract, train, and retain the next generation of specialists.

4.5 Capacity and gaps analysis for data engineers

4.5.1 Existing capacity

The existing training capacity for DEs is centred either on formal training as part of taught postgraduate courses or online training as provided by cloud computing companies (Google Cloud, AWS, Azure and IBM) and large online learning providers (Coursera, Udemy and DataCamp). The formal training as part of taught coursework traditionally falls within existing MSc programs in Data Science or ML. This is often covered by a generic “HPC and data architecture” module. However, these data science programmes do not include other data engineering aspects as these are often platform specific and few academics have the relevant skill/experience to teach them e.g., “cloud HPC with AWS”. The various online courses available do provide a good coverage of role specific skills as outlined in Annex A3, such as designing and building data processing pipelines, managing databases and programming in Python.

There are various professional DE examinations and certificates offered by the same cloud computing companies and the various online learning courses are geared towards preparing a candidate for

these certificate examinations. This is a general finding with regards to some of the online offers - often, these courses are narrowly focused on the chosen cloud infrastructure, neglecting broader data engineering fundamentals.

Recommendations:

- More balanced online courses: Incorporating fundamental data engineering knowledge alongside platform-specific skills.
- Alternative learning opportunities: Exploring independent platforms or educational institutions that prioritise foundational understanding over cloud-specific certifications.

Overall, while current offerings provide valuable training, fostering well-rounded DEs demands a blend of platform-specific skills and strong foundational knowledge.

4.5.2 Career development opportunities:

The career progression of a DE within the industrial sector is well defined with deeper knowledge of the underlying technology stack and organisational abilities required to progress. Emphasis is often placed on developing scalable and reliable data infrastructure. However, the career progression of a DE in the atmospheric science / EO sector is less well defined. The Academy could support data engineering development potentially through collaboration within the community and promoting or developing specialised programmes that address the progression gap. At the early career stage, a new Data Engineer Level 5 standard apprenticeship is being developed by BPP Education group⁵¹, and could provide a route into the profession, especially if the apprentices could be trained in weather and climate organisations.

4.5.3 Gaps analysis

While there are numerous training provisions provided by the various cloud computing companies and online providers there are few in-person offerings. Further to this there is a lack of courses which focus upon EO data. An existing gap is therefore training in the data formats and standards which are common to the EO field.

Based on findings from our workshop there is also a lack of training provided in ML operations (MLOps)⁵² which is essential to the next generation of weather and climate modelling endeavours. Another need identified is training in the differences between development work on cloud computing infrastructure as opposed to traditional high performance computing environments, for example the usage of GPUs in the cloud versus traditional HPC clusters.

4.6 Capacity and gaps analysis for data scientists

4.6.1 Existing capacity

Data science in general is well-served by formal and informal training provision.

Data science is a very broad field and widely recognised across all sectors. There are many training options, catering to different levels, backgrounds and application domains. The standard entry route is a taught postgraduate qualification and there are many MSc Data Science and variant programmes, as well as undergraduate programmes offering BSc Data Science or variants. Some of these are available for online-only study. Beyond MSc level, there are many PhD programmes related to data science, including those associated with UKRI-funded Centres for Doctoral Training (e.g. the UKRI artificial intelligence CDTs funded in 2018 and 2023⁵³).

Outside the standard academic routes, there are numerous data science bootcamps, short courses and certified programmes of diverse formats and durations. These are offered by universities, further

education colleges, and commercial training providers. Online delivery is well served and there are many MOOCs and online certificates available. Combining academic and professional routes, there are also six IfATE⁵⁴-approved degree apprenticeships at different levels, including degree apprenticeships at both BSc (Level 6) and MSc (Level 7).

Content delivered in a data science programme typically consists of core topics (e.g. programming, ML and statistics) and specialisms (e.g. natural language processing, computer vision, high performance computing). Application domains are varied and many programmes have a topical theme (e.g. social data science, medical data science, environmental data science). Increasingly, these same topics are often labelled as “artificial intelligence”.

Data science training for environmental/meteorological applications is an emerging area.

ML is increasingly applied in climate and weather modelling, to process environmental sensor data (including EO), and for a wide range of other applications. However, there are relatively few specialised training programmes for environmental data science.

Two satellite-focused data science MSc programmes are offered by U. Strathclyde and U. Leicester with the University of Reading offering one on Climate Change and AI. Several environmental data science MSc programmes are now offered at (e.g.) Imperial, Exeter, Leeds, Bristol, and Plymouth. There is a degree apprenticeship standard in “Geospatial Mapping and Science Specialist” at Level 6 and a new standard in “Spatial Data Specialist” is being developed at Level 7. Beyond this, no standards appear to exist that cover remote sensing, EO, satellite or environmental data science. The emerging data science programmes with an environment/weather/climate focus vary in the environmental topics included and in the balance of material dedicated to the different aspects.

There are also a number of doctoral programmes focused on environmental data science, e.g. the UKRI CDT in Environmental Intelligence at Exeter, SENSE – Centre for Satellite Data in Environmental Science, DREAM – Data, Risk and Environmental Analytical Methods.

Practitioners currently make widespread use of ad hoc and online training opportunities. Workshop participants identified a range of short courses and online training providers and platforms that were useful in their roles as environment-facing DSs: PluralSight, Google Europe ML Bootcamp, Youtube, OpenAI documentation, “learning from the internet”, MOOCs from ECMWF and Coursera, Royal Statistics Society conference, etc.

Data science career pathways in environment/meteorology are varied.

Many DSs moved into the area from adjacent roles (e.g. scientific software engineers, data analysts) and often do not have the title of “data scientist”. When DSs are recruited, the entry qualification is often MSc Data Science or similar. High demand means that alternative qualifications or work experience are often accepted.

Some large organisations are trying to standardise DS role definitions and career progression pathways. But many DSs work within pathways/processes designed for other career types. Progression is often determined by experience and technical expertise or specialism. Relatively few senior managers are DSs and data science teams may be managed by senior leaders with different expertise. This need not be problematic but can create a need for senior-level training to enable effective management.

4.6.2 Gap analysis

There is an opportunity to increase the number of specialised data science programmes for environmental and meteorological scientists. This could be both specialised programmes at MSc

level (combining specialised content with more generic content from existing programmes) and smaller “add on” training packages aimed at those in doctoral, postdoctoral or industry research roles. Training provision could focus on remote sensing, satellite observations, environmental data science, and related topics. They would be differentiated from mainstream data science by their application domain and the nature of the techniques used to analyse environmental data.

There is an additional opportunity to develop degree apprenticeship standards for environmental data science, which could use parts of existing apprenticeship programmes but offer greater specialism to the environmental sector.

Workshop attendees agreed that specialised training, where it already exists, could be offered more widely. A coordinated effort to publicise and expand existing provision might be fruitful.

Workshop attendees were favourable towards the idea of community support for DSs working in the environmental sector. Commonly used platforms like Stack Overflow could be adapted or mimicked for this purpose, to allow specialists to provide community guidance on advanced topics, techniques and platforms. This would support an effective “community of practice” that existed across organisations and geographies.

4.6.3 Opportunities to improve career progression.

Career progression for DSs in EO or other environmental sector organisations depends on the processes of those organisations. Some standardisation and role definitions are being developed (e.g. by the Alliance for Data Science Professionals⁵⁵ and UK Government Digital and Data Profession Capability Framework⁵⁶) which might assist organisations in the creation of progression processes and benchmarks. The extent to which these standards are being adopted or used with reference to career progression is currently unclear; it seems likely that professional standards and certification will take time to become established within the wider industry and the current high demand for skills means that organisations are often unable to restrict their recruitment on this basis. Also, generic standards might not cover the specialised skills/competencies in demand in the environmental/meteorological sectors. Additionally, since many DSs are employed in other named roles (but using data science within their role), progression based on data science competence alone might be inappropriate or hard to implement fairly.

Certification for specialised competencies, if approved by a trusted source, might have value within the environmental sector and create a recognised “currency” to support career progression. There is therefore an opportunity for badged/certified training courses to be developed, perhaps within the framework of the TDSA or via affiliated organisations (e.g. Met Office, NOAA, Met Office Academic Partnership (MOAP) universities).

4.7 Capacity and gaps analysis for research software engineers

4.7.1 Existing capacity

There are very few courses aimed directly at RSEs, but some courses aimed at upskilling researchers in technical topics may be relevant to RSEs. At a very introductory level, the Carpentries curriculum (Software Carpentry and Data Carpentry workshops) provides a basic introduction to software engineering topics (e.g. Git, Bash, Python and R). Carpentries courses are mostly at too introductory a level for RSEs, but the course materials are open source, and the Carpentries have pioneered a successful “train-the-trainer” approach which means that many RSEs have completed both the introductory training and the teacher training and thus are qualified to teach the material, so can pass on the knowledge to others. However, this informal teaching is often not recognised. Recently more advanced courses have been added to the Carpentries framework, but it is likely that even

these would only be useful to fairly junior RSEs early in their career (e.g., if they have recently moved into the RSE role from a science background).

The majority of courses suitable for RSEs are higher-level topic-specific technical training (e.g. HPC, parallel programming, GPU programming). The suitability of these courses depends on the particular work and training needs of the RSE. Other, more advanced, general software development training is available commercially, but it may be difficult in advance to determine how cost effective these courses are, and their value for money. There are quite a number of introductory courses in EO / Weather and Climate, which could provide RSEs with a basic understanding of the science, which would help them to place their work in context and feel more confident communicating with researchers in this field, but with many courses to choose from, and a very wide subject area, the challenge is knowing which would be most suitable.

The Society of Research Software Engineering (SocRSE)⁵⁷ has built an engaged community of RSEs working across all research domains (>700 members). SocRSE runs an annual academic conference (~350 attendees) which, in addition to talks and panel discussions, also provides one full day of practical workshops across a wide range of technologies, which are useful for personal development and increased awareness of new tools. Additional satellite events associated with the conference provide some further opportunities. There are a number of regional RSE networks (e.g. ScotRSE, RSLondon) that encourage networking opportunities. Recently, work has begun to develop a community of practice that links RSEs and Met Office Scientific Software Engineers (who have a RSE type role) across the MOAP universities to share knowledge and expertise. Regular webinars provided by a range of organisations (e.g. by University of Edinburgh under the ARCHER2 banner) also help individuals gain knowledge of tools they are either less familiar with, or the application of tools in other domains.

4.7.2 Career development opportunities

RSE group structure and career progression is dependent on the institution where the RSE is employed, though efforts have been made to clarify the requirements for progression. The Society of Research Software Engineering has a repository of RSE job adverts⁵⁸ which helps understand role expectations at different stages. Some groups have published details of the job roles for different career stages. While useful, these general descriptions can be difficult to apply to embedded RSEs who are more towards the researchers end of RSE spectrum, which is likely to be the case for many RSEs working within the TDSA remit. Some MOAP universities have done work on role profiles to support promotion criteria for RSEs and allied roles.

4.7.3 Gaps analysis

While introductory software engineering courses exist, advanced training for RSEs presents several crucial gaps:

- Deep Dives for Specific Tools/Techniques - RSEs lack advanced training opportunities to gain deeper expertise in specific tools or techniques relevant to their roles. Difficulty arises due to the highly individual training needs for each RSE position.
- Bridging the Researcher-RSE Gap - scientists transitioning to RSE careers require upskilling in diverse tools to navigate this career path. Supporting this transition is crucial for RSE recruitment and would enhance the available pool of RSE.
- EO Domain Expertise – Introductory courses on EO research are available, but finding the right one is challenging. Dedicated training on EO-specific knowledge may help some RSEs with putting their work into context for effective outcomes.

- Accessibility – although training may currently exist, the availability is patchy (especially if they are only run as internal courses) and it is difficult to advertise such courses to everybody for whom it may be relevant.

Many RSEs lack access to funds and time to attend training. RSEs within a central RSE team are normally costed onto multiple projects and in some groups there is a lack of clear structure for payment of courses and time for RSEs to attend training. This context switching, and the need to balance time commitments between projects, may also mean that RSEs struggle to attend training, or have disproportionate impact on different projects. There have been some attempts to setup RSE exchange schemes to allow RSEs to work temporarily at different institutions to share skills and build connections, but these are often hampered by the large administrative overheads.

The role of RSE is relatively new, and while much progress has been made to recognise the role there is still much work to be done. Embedded RSEs with good domain knowledge and a (relatively) large research component to their role can be caught between academic and RSE promotion criteria. Central RSEs generally have clearer career structure but few organisations have a promotion structure for RSEs who want to follow a technical, rather than management, track. There is some evidence that this is leading to a brain-drain as academia loses RSEs to industry. Access to accredited courses, and better communication between organisations, may help RSEs in getting promoted.

⁴⁹ <https://training.spaceskills.org/> (last accessed 19/03/2024)

⁵⁰ <https://www.turing.ac.uk/data-science-and-ai-educators-programme> (last accessed 25/03/2024)

⁵¹ <https://www.bpp.com/> (last accessed 25/03/2024)

⁵² ML Engineers are primarily focused on building, training and optimising machine learning models, while MLOps Engineers are mainly concerned with testing, deploying and monitoring ML models in production environments.

⁵³ <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/how-we-work-in-ai/ukri-artificial-intelligence-centres-for-doctoral-training/> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

⁵⁴ Institute for Apprenticeships and Technical Education, <https://www.instituteforapprenticeships.org/> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

⁵⁵ <https://alliancefordatascienceprofessionals.co.uk/> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

⁵⁶ <https://ddat-capability-framework.service.gov.uk/data-scientist.html> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

⁵⁷ SocRSE <https://society-rse.org/> (last accessed 28/02/2024)

⁵⁸ <https://github.com/RSE-leaders/evidence-bank> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

5 Accreditation, certification, and recognition

5.1 Summary

In this section we explore how learners in the TDSA might achieve relevant certification, accreditation or other transferable recognition of their data science, data engineering, data assimilation or research software engineering skills developed through the TDSA and throughout their career.

Certification is given to an individual as proof of completion of training and as a form of recognition of achievement. Accreditation provides an endorsement of quality which can be given to an individual; a training course; or a training provider. We note that these terms are often used inconsistently, with a lack of clear distinction between accreditation and certification. Where a provider consistently adopts a particular terminology, we have also adopted this. Transferable recognition is an umbrella term for broad acknowledgement of individual or organisational achievements/competencies through various mechanisms.

Accreditation and certification can both play important roles in validating skills, knowledge, and educational quality by providing assurance to both learners and employers, but both can be potentially costly and cumbersome, so it is important to evaluate their costs and benefits (see Section 5.5 and 5.6).

[Many certification and accreditation mechanisms already exist – we suggest the TDSA works within these.](#)

Many accreditation and certification schemes already exist that are relevant to the TDSA (see Section 5.4). We suggest that the TDSA work within these existing structures, rather than creating its own scheme(s).

For individuals, certificates of attendance or completion are offered by many training courses from providers as diverse as online learning platforms and universities (see Section 5.4 and Section 4). Certification can range from simple attendance certification to a more formal accredited certificate indicating proficiency.

A number of relevant accreditation schemes for individuals exist which are run by a range of professional bodies (see Section 5.4 and Annex A4). Less formal types of recognition are also discussed, for example a GitHub portfolio of programming skills (see Section 5.4.6).

Courses and course providers may also be accredited, although currently accreditation of courses in data science, data engineering, research software engineering and data assimilation is somewhat limited. The Alliance for Data Science Professionals (AfDSP) has developed an appropriate accreditation standard for university courses.

We do not feel that the TDSA itself should pursue formal accreditation as a provider of training, since the reputation of the TDSA partners brings its own recognition/form of accreditation. Furthermore, gaining such accreditation is complex, time consuming and potentially inflexible in the fast paced/rapidly developing landscape of data science, data engineering, data assimilation and research software engineering.

[Individual accreditation and certification through a professional society – Alliance for Data Science Professionals seems a good fit.](#)

The Alliance for Data Science Professionals (AfDSP) offers a Data Science and Advanced Data Science Professional certification and appears particularly applicable to the TDSA. The AfDSP certification process and skill standards appear to be sufficiently broad as to apply to all four roles we are considering for the TDSA (although there are other professional accreditations that may be a better fit for some staff in the data assimilation and research software engineer roles). Individuals apply for accreditation through one of the AfDSP members which is most relevant to their area of work.

An option to consider is for the TDSA to encourage a professional body within the weather, climate or EO field, such as the Royal Meteorological Society, to join the AfDSP. That body could then offer certification, under the AfDSP scheme, to TDSA participants (and others). The inclusion of such a body within the AfDSP would also help to ensure that the skills standards, certification and accreditation process developed by the Alliance consider the specific data science related skills necessary for those working in the EO, weather and climate domain (see Section 3). Additionally, the Met Office itself might wish to consider becoming a supporter of the Alliance.

It is important to consider whether such certification would be valued by TDSA learners and to balance that against the time involved in applying for and maintaining certification and registration (see Section 5.5). The stakeholders we consulted (although only a relatively small sample) gave little indication that such personal certification and accreditation is currently felt to be of value for career progression. Personal accreditation and certification may become more pertinent in the future as communities and markets get larger, and may have a role in reducing bias. This needs further investigation.

Some stakeholders also expressed concern about the cost of personal certification and accreditation. Covering such costs for Academy learners is an issue to be considered more fully in Phase 2 of the project.

[Important for TDSA to signpost to quality, relevant and up to date training resources](#)

A clear message that emerges from our analysis is that individuals and employers are likely to value the *QUALITY* of training that they take, offer to their staff or advertise to potential new employees.

In Section 7, we discuss the provision of a TDSA Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue, which would provide information about relevant training courses, for example. Our stakeholder engagement suggests that this type of catalogue would be valuable to help people find appropriate and quality training from the huge range available (see Section 5.5 and Section 3).

The TDSA would need to ensure that any courses included in the catalogue (whether that be existing courses or courses that the TDSA develops) are of high quality, relevant and up to date. Using accredited courses/providers could help to ensure such quality, although the TDSA would need to consider how courses/course providers are accredited and by whom. An element of review by learners who have previously taken the course is seen as a useful addition by some stakeholders. This process of how to assess quality of signposted training needs further consideration within Phase 2 of the project.

[New recognition mechanisms needed for some types of training](#)

There are some types of training, learning and development which are important for the TDSA to consider, and which may not be recognised by existing mechanisms.

For example:

- Train-the-trainer (see Section 5.6 and Section 4.3.4)
- Apprenticeships (see Section 5.5.3 and Section 4.6)

- On-the job learning (see Section 5.5.2)

International transferability of accreditation, certification and recognition

The transatlantic recognition and transferability of certification and recognition present a mixed picture.

Postgraduate academic qualifications for individuals such as master's and doctoral degrees have broadly equivalent standards between the US and UK. Such degrees are widely recognised internationally.

Industry platform certificates are typically provided by companies with a global market, and as such are recognised all around the world.

The professional accreditation landscape is different in the US. To the best of our knowledge, a US equivalent to Chartered Scientist does not exist. However, the American Statistical Association is a member of the AfDSP, and therefore we would suggest that there could be scope for the development of a US equivalent standard for Advanced Data Science Professional.

Short- and long-term recommendations

A quick win:

- Create a catalogue of suitable accredited training courses – which we envisage as part of our suggested TDSA Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue (discussed further in Section 7).

Longer term:

- Consider certification for learners through the AfDSP, potentially bringing in a suitable EO/weather/climate Alliance member.

Overall:

- Ensure that any accreditation, certification, and recognition mechanisms co-ordinated through the TDSA have real value/motivation for individual Academy learners and tie in with career frameworks (see Section 7).

5.2 Methodology

The methodology for evidence gathering was carried out in three stages:

- **Review** - an initial scoping stage in which existing certification and accreditation schemes within the domain were identified; this forms the basis of the table shown in Annex A4.
- **Stakeholder workshop** - The workshop brought together a wide range of training providers, representatives of professional bodies, and staff working in technical and research roles. We used breakout sessions to gather diverse perspectives on certification and accreditation. This format ensured a wide range of views and fostered fruitful discussions among different stakeholders.
- **Stakeholder interviews** – Six representative stakeholders were interviewed to gather a deeper understanding of some of the issues raised at the workshop (some had also been involved in the workshop). Interviewees included Degree Programme Directors (who tend to have an academic background) and Education Managers (who tend to have a business or managerial background). In particular we interviewed:
 - Four individuals from academic and research institutions to represent varying opinions from experienced educators.

- One member of technical staff to represent a typical “learner”, and
- One representative from a Professional Society.

Demographic information on the stakeholder workshop can be found in Section 1.5.3. We gathered a range of sometimes quite disparate views and we have reflected that in the chapter, following the EDI principles laid out for the project, in particular: “valuing and respecting difference” and “challenging assumptions”.

5.3 Definitions

Accreditation and certification are distinct mechanisms, yet their similarities often lead to confusion, so it is worth clarifying the differences. In some instances, providers adopt a different convention to the definitions given here. Where a provider does this consistently, we have tried to use the same terminology as the provider and use qualifying text for more clarity.

5.3.1 Accreditation

Accreditation is given to a training provider or training program, as well as to individuals as professional accreditations. It is an, ideally independently and impartially assessed, endorsement that the provider adheres to recognised standards in terms of curriculum, faculty qualifications, facilities, and overall educational quality. Accreditation can be awarded at a national or international level. One example of an accreditation body is the QAA¹ (Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education), which provides quality accreditation to higher education bodies across the UK as well as internationally.

Membership of a learned institution is a form of personal accreditation which requires the holder to have attained certain standards (e.g. a degree and some years of relevant experience). Chartership is similar but normally more senior and typically requires an ongoing commitment to continued professional development and proof of commitment to ethical standards. An example of this is the Chartered Statistician award⁵⁹, issued by the Royal Statistical Society, which provides formal recognition of a member’s statistical qualifications and professional training and experience. Fellowship can be obtained by those of senior professional standing based on demonstrable achievement and competence, e.g. Fellow of the Institute of Mathematics and its Applications⁶⁰.

5.3.2 Certification

Certification is given to individuals who successfully complete a specific training course, providing recognition of their achievement. Certification does not necessarily need to come from an accredited body (one example would be a certificate of course attendance), however, if it does, this gives a guarantee of a minimum level of competence in the covered subject matter (e.g., degree certificate from a UK university). Different types of certificates include:

- *Attendance Certificate*: Issued for attending all sessions.
- *Participation Certificate*: Awarded for active engagement and participation in course activities.
- *Completion Certificate*: Given upon successful completion of the training program.
- *Skills Recognition Certificate*: Acknowledges the development and improvement of specific skills during the course. Would involve some continuous testing or potentially an exam.
- *Accredited Certificate*: Certifies that the participant has undergone training that is accredited by an external body.

5.3.3 Transferable recognition

Transferable recognition implies that an individual or organisation's achievements and competencies can be recognised and understood by a broad audience. This may include recognition that transcends role, discipline, organisation or national borders. Examples include the certification and accreditation that are the subject of this section and promotion to a more senior role in a well-defined career framework (career frameworks are discussed in Sections 3 and 7).

5.4 Existing schemes

5.4.1 Alliance for Data Science Professionals

The Alliance for Data Science Professionals (AfDSP) was setup in 2021 as a collaboration between the Royal Statistical Society (RSS), BCS (The Chartered Institute for IT), the Operational Research Society (ORS), the Institute of Mathematics and its Applications (IMA), Alan Turing Institute, National Physical Laboratory (NPL) with support from the Royal Society and the Royal Academy of Engineering. Two further members joined the Alliance and its Governance Board in early 2024: the American Statistical Association and the Wellcome Sanger Institute. The AfDSP aims to define common standards for training, certification, and accreditation in data science so that there is an ethical and well-governed approach and the public, organisations and governments can have confidence in how their data are used. All members contribute to the development of standards but only the four inaugural learned society members currently award certification.

The AfDSP has two levels of professional certification: the Data Science Professional and the Advanced Data Science Professional. It is planned for the Advanced Data Science Professional certification to become a Chartered designation in the future. The Certification Guidance and Process for the Advanced Data Science Professional⁶¹ lays out the criteria and an example path through. They define five key skills areas:

- Data privacy and stewardship
- Definition, acquisition, engineering, architecture, storage, and curation
- Problem definition and communication with stakeholders
- Problem solving, analysis, statistical modelling, visualisation
- Evaluation and reflection

These skill categories can be compared to those discussed in Section 3.

Within the AfDSP scheme, individuals can apply to be certified based on evidence they supply covering education, work experience, continuing professional development (CPD) and evidence that they meet the competencies in a number of the skill areas above, plus their level of responsibilities. Individuals apply through the most appropriate Alliance member organisation and fees are dictated by that member. For example, the Royal Statistical Society charges an annual fee of £48 for certification, in addition to its usual membership fees.

The AfDSP website⁶² specifically mentions the roles of data scientist (DS), data engineer (DE), data analyst and data steward. It is our interpretation of the criteria that the other roles within the TDSA (research software engineer (RSE) and data assimilation scientist (DAS)) would also be in scope, although other types of accreditations may be more suitable for some of these staff (see Section 5.4.2).

The AfDSP is an exciting development which is relevant for many TDSA learners. Certification through this route is relatively new, having been launched in July 2022. The AfDSP is open to new partnerships and is keen to work with the TDSA. They provided us with the following quote:

Professor Paul Glaister CBE from the Alliance for Data Science Professionals said:

“Following the successful launch of the standard leading to the Advanced Data Science Professional certificate for individuals in 2022, the Alliance are pleased to announce the introduction of the university standard for accrediting UK-based degree programmes. With applications planned to be accepted in the first half of 2025 and the planned recognition of the Advanced Data Science Professional certification as a Chartered title, there is now a clear pathway of standards and competencies at every level within the field of data science. The Alliance see these next steps as key to achieving their original goal of helping to shape the profession of data science. We are excited about working with the Transatlantic Data Science Academy Scoping Project.”

5.4.2 Other professional bodies

There are also a range of accreditation options not directly targeted at data science, but which may be relevant to TDSA members, especially those in DAS and RSE roles that do not fit the profile for the AfDSP so closely.

Many professional bodies offer *memberships* at different levels to reflect career stage, these are often priced accordingly with discounts for early career/students. Although these memberships are not particularly significant in terms of enhancing CVs, they do offer access to engaged networks of researchers and knowledge exchange and could potentially be used as evidence supporting application to accreditation. For example, the Institute for Mathematics and its Applications (IMA) has different membership options (including Affiliate, Student, Associate (AMIMA), Member (MIMA) and Fellow (FIMA)).

Several organisations also offer a separate programme of *registration*, typically at two levels, Registered and Chartered, with broadly similar criteria, although the details differ between schemes. Once granted, awardees must maintain their status through meeting CPD requirements each year. More details of these schemes are included in Annex A4. Some examples that are particularly relevant for the TDSA are included below.

For RSEs, the British Computer Society offers an IT pathway consisting of Registered IT Technician (RITTech), Advanced Registered IT Technician (ARITTech), Chartered IT Professional (CITP) and a similar engineering pathway culminating in Chartered Engineer (CEng). For DA, a number of bodies in the UK offer a Chartered Scientist (CSci) accreditation (including the Science Council, Institute of Physics (IoP) and the IMA).

Another scheme relevant to the TDSA is that of the Royal Meteorological Society (RMetS) who have a formal accreditation scheme with two levels (Registered and Chartered). While it is most often taken by people pursuing a career as a meteorologist, it is also suitable for researchers working in the wider climate and Earth Observation field. Registered meteorologist is an early career level whereas requirements for the more senior Chartership level include a relevant degree, 5 years of professional experience, subject knowledge, and a commitment to continued professional development. The application process includes a peer reviewed application and a panel interview. The process takes approximately 4 months and costs £202 application fee and an annual fee of £50 (in addition to the RMetS membership fee).

Standards for Chartered titles in the UK are set between the professional bodies and relevant national government departments, whereas in the USA professional registration is carried out on a state-by-state basis for professions where regulation requires professional standards (such as professional engineers). To the best of our knowledge, a US equivalent to Chartered Scientist does not exist.

5.4.3 Research degrees as a form of certification/personal accreditation

Many participants in the TDSA will have an element of research included in their job-role (although the proportion of time spent on research will vary). Research skills can be certified through completion of a research degree such as an MPhil or PhD. Such degrees can be completed at academic institutions around the world and are internationally recognised to have broadly equivalent standards.

There are several routes to obtain a PhD in the UK that may be relevant to TDSA learners at different career stages:

- **Full-time PhD.** This is the traditional route to obtain a PhD by full-time study, supervised by university academic staff. In the UK, the PhD is usually expected to take 3-4 years. The expected length of time taken can vary in other countries. Typical arrangements for full-time PhDs can be quite flexible. For example, if appropriate, they can allow the student to spend much of their time studying at a location away from the university campus, and align the research topic with their day-job.
- **Part-time PhD.** This is similar to the full-time PhD, but allows the student to work part-time on their research, and to have a longer registration period in which to submit their PhD thesis.
- **PhD by published works** is intended for candidates who have developed their knowledge and independent research skills to doctoral level and who already have a body of publications produced during the course of their careers. The registration period for PhD by published works is typically around 1-2 years, i.e., much less than for a traditional PhD. Although the format of the thesis may differ, the expected quality of outputs, and the candidate's understanding of the wider field of knowledge, is equivalent to that for the more traditional PhD by thesis.

5.4.4 Industry-recognised certification platforms

Industry-recognised certification platforms offer the opportunity to access training and validate their expertise in a wide range of topics, including those relevant to TDSA (e.g. IT, project management, data science). These certifications provide tangible evidence of proficiency and competency however there are a lot of options and learners may find it difficult to know which would be of most use and to evaluate how attractive different courses are to employers.

Some may be of broad interest to TDSA members e.g. Microsoft Learn which focuses on Microsoft technologies or Cisco which focuses on cybersecurity. In addition, there are some schemes that may be of direct interest:

- *Amazon Web Services (AWS) Training and Certification*: AWS offers certifications including AWS Certified Solutions Architect, AWS Certified Developer, and AWS Certified Data Analytics which may be of interest to people using cloud computing. Certification is fairly rigorous and exam costs range are approximately £100-£250 per exam but are well recognised by employers.
- *Google Cloud Certification*: Google Cloud provides certifications such as Google Cloud Professional Data Engineer, Google Cloud Professional Machine Learning Engineer, and more. Similar costs and rigour to AWS.
- *Tableau Certification*: Tableau provides certifications in Tableau Desktop and Tableau Server, validating proficiency in data visualisation and analytics. Tableau certifications can enhance career prospects in data analysis and visualisation roles. However, Tableau exams may require practical experience with Tableau software and advanced data analysis skills.
- *SAS Global Certification*: SAS offers certifications in various analytics and data science-related fields, including SAS Certified Data Scientist. SAS certifications validate expertise in SAS software and analytics methodologies, enhancing career opportunities in data science and analytics roles. However, SAS exams may require proficiency in SAS programming languages and statistical analysis techniques.

The TDSA may be able to help people identify which training, available through industry-recognised certification platforms, would be of most benefit to those wishing to progress, either by signposting learners to resources or by collecting reviews of courses to identify which are of most potential use.

While some learners within the TDSA might benefit from taking some of the above courses this is likely to be to address a specific learning need for individual learners, rather than a core element of training across the TDSA. We did not find examples of training specifically relevant to the DA role amongst the commonly used certification platforms (see Section 4 for more information on DA training courses).

5.4.5 Certificates provided by online platforms

Several online platforms offer certificates of learning upon completing courses or programmes. These are often self-paced so offer a high degree of flexibility, but do not generally have rigorous assessment. Some may have some continuous assessment (e.g. short quizzes), but they do not evaluate understanding or proficiency as fully as the platforms above.

Here are some prominent ones:

- *Credly*: Offers digital badges for various skills and achievements, providing a portable and verifiable way to showcase expertise. These are lighter and less well regarded than other schemes.
- *Coursera*: Offers certificates of completion for individual courses as well as specialisation certificates for completing a series of related courses. Certificates can be shared on LinkedIn and other social media platforms.
- *Udemy*: Offers certificates of completion for courses in various subjects, including technology, business, and personal development.
- *LinkedIn Learning*: Provides certificates of completion for a very wide range of courses. Some Universities have institutional access.

- *Pluralsight*: Provides certificates of completion for courses in technology and software development.
- *FutureLearn*: Offers certificates of achievement for completing short courses which are provided by universities and institutions. Certificates can be purchased and shared as proof of learning.
- *Codecademy*: Offers certificates of completion for completing coding courses in programming languages such as Python, JavaScript, and HTML/CSS.
- *DataCamp*: Provides certificates of completion for completing courses in data science and analytics.

Some participants in the stakeholder workshop shared positive experiences of learning through these platforms. Again, the volume of courses and the lack of clear information about course quality and value can be daunting and the TDSA may be able to help learners navigate (e.g. recommending courses, providing a platform for learners to share reviews). Conversely, at least one participant stated that informal certificates (particularly for learning programming languages) can be perceived as relatively meaningless.

5.4.6 Online repositories

Most TDSA learners will be familiar with using GitHub (or a similar platform) for version control and collaborative working. Those learners that work on open-source projects will have potentially built up a portfolio of work on GitHub that could be used to demonstrate their skills. While this is a robust way for a technically minded reviewer to get an overview of a person's experience it requires some effort. It must also be noted that it is not suitable for people that work on projects that are not open source as they cannot share their code to demonstrate their skills.

In addition, there is potential to use online tools to track course attendance (for example LinkedIn or GitHub), so people can build up a repository of evidence of course completion. If the TDSA suggested a semi-standardised format and recommended people to populate it, it would help people to share their skills, and if people were willing to make them open, it may help early career learners see what training others had benefited from.

5.4.7 Accreditation of courses

Professional societies also have a role in accrediting bachelor's and master's level courses, for example the Institute of Physics offers an accreditation scheme for physics degrees. Similar accreditation is offered in other relevant topics e.g. by Royal Statistical Society or the Royal Society of Chemistry. This provides an independent assessment of degree programs to ensure high standards across different providers.

In general, continuous professional development courses attended by people working in research are not accredited in this way. The AfDSP is working towards offering an accreditation option for data science degrees but does not plan to offer accreditation for CPD courses.

There is growing understanding in the key characteristics of high quality short course training⁶³ but there appears to be a gap in guidance to support organisations looking to commission training, and to develop a common language with which to discuss their needs.

5.5 Learner and provider perspectives

This section is based largely on input from stakeholders through the workshop and interviews. We emphasise that this represents a limited sample of stakeholders.

5.5.1 Varying value of certification and personal accreditation

Value of academic qualifications

- A small survey of Met Office staff (see Section 2.5.2) revealed a highly educated workforce. Notably, half held PhDs, and the other half possessed master's degrees. Nine workshop attendees identified as students, highlighting further the emphasis on academic qualifications. This shows a strong cultural value placed on academic qualifications, particularly within early career stages.
- Individuals with a strong academic background (such as a PhD) and employers (especially in academia) tend to value those qualifications as "proof" of accreditation at an appropriate level (see Section 5.4.3) and may see further certification/personal accreditation as less important. This translates to mixed views on the need for additional certification for training course attendance or other accreditation.

Value of additional certification / accreditation

- Individuals considering career changes, particularly from academia to the commercial sector, emphasise the value of certification as a way to showcase transferable skills and enhance employability across a wider range of employment sectors. Certification is seen to be important for industry-used topics/tools or accredited by specific companies for their own products (e.g., Certified Java Programmer; Certified Azure practitioner; AWS Certified Solutions Architect).
- Research scientists generally place less weight on other certified courses, compared to attendance-only ones, unless pursuing a career shift. Their focus lies primarily on research outputs and winning grant income for internal promotion within academia, translating into a mix of views on whether certified or accredited courses were of value for internal promotion prospects.
- Attendance only (rather than the requirement of significant amounts of pre- or post-course work and/or administration) was also seen as generally preferable by most workshop participants, with perhaps the exception of PhD students. PhD students may need evidence of additional training to meet CDT (Centre for Doctoral Training) requirements, or evidence that will support them in gaining a post-PhD job in the commercial sector, where external training or accreditation is often more important than in the academic sector.
- For training specifically developed or targeted by an employer for a particular cohort of employees, participants stated that they are less likely to care about recognition, but their employer is likely to want the course to be accredited.

Career progression

- The requirement for higher-level accreditation, such as Chartered status, does not currently hold much sway for career progression within TDSA roles, with promotion decisions more heavily influenced by research/technical achievements and leadership and management potential. This is especially the case when there are costs associated with a course or accreditation.
- Employers may require specific training and accreditation for certain domains due to regulatory purposes, highlighting the need for flexibility and responsiveness to industry demands.
- In the future, as the communities and markets grow, personal accreditation and certification may become more pertinent, and will assure that there is less scope for bias.

5.5.2 Reputation and accreditation challenges

Individuals and employers value high-quality training. Universities are widely recognised as providers of such training, given that their courses are accredited, and the teaching is formally assessed through the Teaching Excellence Framework. Universities accredit all courses they teach, whether they are *credit-bearing* (i.e. can be used to contribute to an awarded degree programme, with a formal assessment), or *non-credit-bearing* (i.e. learners typically gain a certificate of attendance, without formal assessment). University courses typically have external examiners and undergo formal periodic review by external parties, such as the UK Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education (QAA), and professional societies who assess professional qualifications.

Importance of the certification provider. A certification issued by a university may be more valuable than a certification issued by other learning platforms that offer free online courses. Most popular online learning platforms offer certificates that are not accredited, but some employers may recognise the value of online learning and may be willing to consider those certificates as evidence of skills and knowledge.

Accreditation by professional bodies on a particular domain. For example, professional bodies in data science (e.g. British Computing Society, Royal Statistical Society) have not formally adopted course accreditation yet in the data science domain, but ongoing discussions with research and teaching organisations (e.g. Alan Turing Institute) suggest potential future developments in this area.

Concerns regarding gaining course accreditation for education providers. While certification and the reputation of the issuing body are important factors for learners, education providers share the following concerns associated with gaining accreditation:

- the constraints and inflexibility that are imposed,
- the cost of maintaining accreditation, and
- the administrative burden that this can place on a training provider.

This can limit program distinctiveness and adaptability to the rapidly evolving technical landscape. Non-accredited courses allow much more flexibility in changing the topics taught at short notice depending on the requirements of the cohort.

Importance of accredited courses. Accredited courses might not always keep pace with the fast-changing technological environment, raising concerns about outdated content and its practical relevance. However, some stakeholders see course accreditation as a way to assure quality, particularly for learners with limited resources, time constraints or concerns about course legitimacy. One interviewee raised a concern that the pursuit of accreditation might prioritise fulfilling accreditation scheme requirements over student needs. This suggests that accreditation or formal certification may be less crucial when the course provider is well known and respected within the field as is the case with courses taught through CDTs or academic collaborations / institutions.

Recognition for other forms of learning and development. In Sections 1 and 4 we discuss the importance of on-the-job learning, however such learning may not be covered by traditional certification.

In-house training is seen as highly valuable but is under-recognised. While not formally accredited, in-house training holds value as a way to contribute to the community. However, technical staff often see this as an extra activity, lacking formal recognition or dedicated time for execution.

5.5.3 Beyond traditional routes of entry – apprenticeships

While a traditional academic route (computer science degree, possibly with a PhD) is common for RSE, DS and DE roles, other options should not be discounted. Apprenticeships, for instance, can be a strong fit for learners who excel technically but may not have a strong academic background. Our research shows no evidence that such apprentices would perform less effectively in these roles than those staff with a traditional academic background.

Data assimilation is not widely taught at undergraduate or master’s levels. Many existing DA professionals have learned their deeper DA skills through a PhD degree or on-the-job. The interdisciplinary nature of the role and the spectrum of activities (from developing physical understanding of observations and models through to development of accurate and efficient numerical mathematical/statistical computational algorithms) means that individuals need strong foundational skills across a broad curriculum of physical and mathematical sciences. Thus, any apprenticeship route into DA would need to be a higher-level apprenticeship (at master’s or PhD level).

Recognising and promoting alternative routes like apprenticeships could encourage employers to be more open to diverse backgrounds and contribute to greater equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) within the workforce.

The role of training through an apprenticeship is also discussed in Section 4.6.

5.6 Options for certification, accreditation, and other forms of recognition for Academy learners

There is a wide body of literature^{64 65 66 67 68 69} which comments on the role of certification and accreditation in teaching and learning. Both have advantages and disadvantages that should be considered in a general context (see Table 5-1), it is important to carefully weigh the benefits against downsides, first generally and then specifically for the TDSA.

	Benefits	Downsides
Accreditation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training provider / program/individual is independently assessed to check quality • Impartial endorsement adds credibility • Provides confidence to recipients/employers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time-consuming and expensive to achieve • Maintenance requires ongoing assessment and quality assurance
Certification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence of completed training program • Guarantees competence and expertise if from accredited body • Can aid career progression 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informal certification (not linked to an accredited provider) has less value than an assessed one • Formal certification requires accreditation of issuing body • Linking certification to accreditation may complicate setup process.

Table 5-1: A summary of the advantages and disadvantages of accreditation and certification.

Throughout the preparation of this section, we have seen some lack of alignment between what is published in the literature (summarised in Table 5-1), and views gained via our stakeholder engagement. The literature states what is often regarded as best practice but may only be relevant to either one domain or one cohort of learners. Where there is a significant divergence between the

literature and the stakeholders we have engaged with, we have added greater weight to the views of our stakeholders (particularly if given by multiple stakeholders), given that they better represent our intended end user of the Academy.

As highlighted in Section 5.5, it is difficult to provide a small set of concrete recommendations, given that different types of courses, and their certification, are valued differently by a large number of different cohorts, depending on career stage, short-to-medium term ambition, and previous academic background.

Although we can identify some perceived gaps in the accreditation of courses (for example, upskilling courses in data science specifically for the EO domain) we do not feel it would be valuable for the Academy to accredit external courses, nor gain specific accreditation for any courses it may provide. We feel there are better uses of the resources within the Academy. We would recommend that the Academy should instead signpost towards accredited and certified courses. It should work with Professional Bodies, many of whom will already have Training and Accreditation officers, to ensure that training opportunities are relevant for both learners and employers. Learners should not feel they are sent on training courses for the sake of it. The Academy should also recognise that non-accredited courses are also valuable in many situations, but should apply some due diligence to any such courses it signposts to. It could undertake a periodic review of the quality of such courses, using learner feedback, an assessment of the materials presented by TDSA partners, or a more thorough review involving the trainers.

Directed signposting could improve take-up of new accreditation schemes, such as the one provided by the Alliance for Data Science, which none of our interviewees were aware of.

The Academy should be aware of differing routes into the job roles covered by the Academy, and highlight where external courses may be applicable to people from different backgrounds.

Signposting of courses could be done via a comprehensive course catalogue, with appropriate metadata – including whether the course is accredited or awards certification, and if so, at what level; the catalogue could include courses for both technical and the soft-skills likely to be required at different career stages (see Chapter 7 Recommendations). It may also help learners if courses were mapped against the standard UK qualification levels, so that they are better informed as to whether they are learning at, for example, HND, degree, or postgraduate degree level. However, we recognise that for some non-university courses accredited by external professional bodies, this mapping may be difficult.

One concern raised was that by raising the profile of certified courses, which are more valued by individuals looking to leave the sector, this could increase the number of people who then do subsequently leave – adding to the “brain drain” that is already prevalent because of the higher salaries available in the private sector. This should be monitored and to try to mitigate this the Academy may wish to consider putting some effort into:

- Signposting courses which are valued in academia rather than industry (e.g. train-the-trainer, or other courses focusing on pedagogy)
- Encouraging academic and research institutes to provide alternative career pathways to a senior level for individuals interested in a technical career progression rather than the more traditional management route to more senior levels (see Sections 4.3.6 and 7).

Additionally, there is an opportunity for modular CPD training. The modular approach could build towards a greater accreditation. For example, there are some interdisciplinary degree programmes that effectively allow students to build their own degrees.

The Academy could also consider how individuals' skills can be assessed or recognised without them undertaking formal training e.g. producing a high-quality git repository (in effect a portfolio of work), or a recognition of their programming skills, so it can be acknowledged that they are proficient in certain areas.

⁵⁹ Chartered Statistician <https://rss.org.uk/membership/professional-development/chartered-statistician/> (last accessed 27/02/24)

⁶⁰ Institute of Mathematics and its Applications: Fellow. <https://ima.org.uk/membership/membership-grades/fellow/> (last accessed 27/02/2024)

⁶¹ Certification Guidance and Process: Advanced Data Science Professional https://alliancefordatascienceprofessionals.co.uk/documents/AfDSP_Guidance_June22.pdf (last accessed 27/02/24)

⁶² Alliance for Data Science Professionals <https://alliancefordatascienceprofessionals.co.uk/> (last accessed 27/2/2024)

⁶³ Williams JJ, Tractenberg RE, Batut B, Becker EA, Brown AM, Burke ML, et al. (2023) An international consensus on effective, inclusive, and career-spanning short-format training in the life sciences and beyond. PLoS ONE 18(11): e0293879. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0293879> (last accessed 25/03/2024)

⁶⁴ <https://mplaza.training/articles-and-guides/advantages-and-disadvantages-of-certifications/> (last accessed 27/2/2024)

⁶⁵ Michael H. Romanowski & Ibrahim M. Karkouti (2022) United States accreditation in higher education: does it dilute academic freedom?, Quality in Higher Education, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13538322.2022.2127165> (last accessed 27/2/2024)

⁶⁶ https://www.rsb.org.uk/images/accreditation_home/Benefits_of_International_Degree_Accreditation.pdf (last accessed 27/2/2024)

⁶⁷ Kumar, Pradeep and Shukla, Balvinder and Passey, Don (2020) Impact of Accreditation on Quality and Excellence of Higher Education Institutions. Revista Investigacion Operacional, 41 (2). pp. 151-167 <https://eprints.lancs.ac.uk/id/eprint/141916/> (last accessed 27/2/2024)

⁶⁸ Andresen, B.B. (2019). Sustainable E-Learning – A Case Study on the Pros and Cons of Certification. In: Tatnall, A., Mavengere, N. (eds) Sustainable ICT, Education and Learning. SUZA 2019. IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology, vol 564. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-28764-1_5 (last accessed 27/2/2024)

⁶⁹ Lee Harvey (2004) The power of accreditation: views of academics, Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management, 26:2, 207-223, DOI:[10.1080/1360080042000218267](https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080042000218267) (last accessed 27/2/2024)

6 Exploiting Opportunities

6.1 Summary

This section highlights key opportunities and potential activities for the TDSA that have emerged from our analysis and discussion in Sections 2 to 5. We pull these opportunities together here in order to lay the foundation for our recommendations in Section 7.

Key opportunities

Quick wins/shorter term

- Build on and tailor existing provision/mechanisms for training, learning and development.
- Develop a catalogue of available training provision – ensuring a mix of learning formats to reduce barriers to learning.
- Engage in activities that encourage people into careers in data science, data engineering, data assimilation science and research software engineering – by engaging TDSA partners/participants in existing activities/mechanisms.

Longer term

- Develop a bespoke career framework for the TDSA.
- Fill gaps in training – in particular, training tailored to Earth Observation (EO)/weather and climate.
- Address barriers to learning and apply equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) principles to all TDSA activities throughout.

We have also compiled a list of collaborations (Annex A5) which could provide opportunities for the TDSA, and we begin to consider longer term funding for the Academy.

6.2 Methodology

In this section we identify key opportunities for the Academy and consider possible mechanisms (including resources being offered by partners) that could be used by a future TDSA. In order to achieve this, we have made use of various sources of information.

We draw on outcomes from Sections 2 to 5 to identify opportunities and the expertise, knowledge and links brought by the project team to identify existing partnerships that provide platforms which could support rapid and effective development of a TDSA. By consulting with the project team, we have created a list of existing collaborations between universities and institutions that may be useful from a TDSA perspective and suggest collaborations that could be expanded in future.

Furthermore, we draw on outputs from the virtual stakeholder workshop held in December 2023, which included breakout groups focused on “exploiting opportunities”. We recognise that workshop attendees and interviewees represent a small sample. The demographics of attendees at the stakeholder workshop show a good range of career stages and roles, but with some lack of diversity in gender and ethnicity (see Section 2).

6.3 Key gaps and opportunities for the TDSA

This section highlights possible opportunities and potential activities for the TDSA that have emerged from our analysis and discussion in Sections 2 to 5. We pull these opportunities together here in order to lay the foundation for our recommendations in Section 7.

6.3.1 Encourage people into careers in data science, data engineering, research software engineering and data assimilation

Gap/issue/need: There is a lack of diversity within higher education science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) subjects which contributes to a lack of diversity in data science, data engineering, research software engineering and data assimilation (see Sections 2 and 3). Undergraduates and 16 to 18 year olds may be unaware of career opportunities in the EO field.

Opportunity: TDSA partners/participants take part in career outreach activities and offer opportunities for work experience, placements and sponsorship. It would be beneficial if such activity, and its contribution to career and personal development, could be recognised within the TDSA career framework.

Mechanisms:

- Existing outreach/work experience/placement schemes and apprenticeships, such as those listed in Table 6-1. We recommend that the TDSA explore similar organisations within the US as well as other opportunities within the UK.
- TDSA partners/collaborators could offer and promote:
 - Undergraduate projects
 - Virtual seminars
 - Summer research placements
 - Year-long "sandwich" placements (e.g., students working for the Met Office for a year in the middle of their degree)
 - "Sponsoring" students to do undergraduate/master's degrees (degree apprenticeships or bursaries).
- Seek out members of the Academy who might be willing to act as a coach, mentor or STEM ambassador and maintain a list of these.
- Create web materials showing profiles of a diverse range of people working in TDSA roles. These could be hosted by the TDSA, by TDSA partners or by external organisations e.g., "WISE My Skills My Life" role model profiles⁷⁰.
- Provide TDSA learners with activities/resources to use in outreach with schools. Provision of resources reduces the barriers for TDSA learners to participate and ensures high quality activities pitched at the right level. Many such resources exist already e.g., Space Resources collated by STEM Learning⁷¹.
- The TDSA could provide access to databases of available MScs, PhDs, and jobs in the EO field. The TDSA could develop its own database or provide input to other websites such as spacecareers.uk⁷².

Outreach and placement schemes

- **Nuffield** (<https://www.nuffieldresearchplacements.org>) provide research and experience placements for UK Year 12 students (around 16-17 years old) in STEM subjects.
- **In2science** (<https://in2scienceuk.org>) promotes social mobility and diversity in STEM, by offering collaborations with researchers and industry professionals to young people from low-income and disadvantaged backgrounds.
- **STEM Ambassadors** (<https://www.stem.org.uk/stem-ambassadors>) and **Climate Ambassadors** (<https://www.stem.org.uk/ccep/climate-ambassadors>) support volunteers to visit schools, colleges, and youth groups to deliver activities linking STEM subjects to the world of work.

- **Space Placements in Industry (SPIN) Placements** (<https://sa.catapult.org.uk/spin/>) offers undergraduate placements in the space sector.
- **10,000 interns foundation** (<https://10000internsfoundation.com/>) runs two programmes: 10,000 Black Interns programme, and the 10,000 Able Interns programme, both offering university students and recent graduates paid internship opportunities across a range of UK industries.
- **Spectris Foundation** (<https://spectrisfoundation.com/>), a UK-based charity who recently received funding to expand opportunities to students and training for teachers in STEM subjects in the USA.
- **IRIS** (<https://researchinschools.org/>), the Institute for Research in Schools, provides opportunities for young people in the UK, to participate in cutting-edge STEM research and collaborate with leading universities and research institutions while still at school.
- **SEPnet Summer Placements** (<https://www.sepnet.ac.uk/for-students/sepnet-summer-placement-scheme-information-students/>), the South East Physics Network arranges for undergraduates at SEPnet partner universities to carry out eight-week paid placements
- **White Rose Industrial Physics Academy** (<https://wripa.ac.uk/>) organises physics work experience, workshops and conferences throughout the year for physics students.
- **ESA Academy** (https://www.esa.int/Education/ESA_Academy/) offers short summer schools, conferences and other opportunities for undergraduate students.

Table 6-1: Examples of existing UK-based outreach and placement schemes

We discuss the way such opportunities would support people at the 16 to 18 year old and undergraduate stages in Section 7.5.

6.3.2 Clarify career frameworks and career development

Gap/issue/need: Unclear career progression within the EO field for data scientists (DSs), data engineers (DEs), research software scientists (RSEs) and data assimilation scientists (DASs) (see Section 4 and Section 5).

Opportunity: to clarify career frameworks and provide clear pathways, increasing standardisation or employee experience, reducing bias and improving transparency about career growth

Mechanisms:

- Develop a bespoke TDSA career framework, drawing on existing relevant frameworks (see Sections 3 and 7.2).
- Consider the value of a personal accreditation scheme for TDSA learners (see Section 5)

We consider how the TDSA could support career development, and the potential role of personal accreditation in Section 7. We recognise that the value and applicability of a personal accreditation scheme for Academy learners (such as Data Science /Advanced Data Science Professional) needs to be considered further.

6.3.3 Develop a catalogue of available training provision

Gap/issue/need: It is not always clear what training or resources are available, which are the most appropriate and what the quality of training is (see Section 4).

Opportunity: TDSA collate information on what is available, together with feedback from users. This would involve producing and maintaining a catalogue of training resources.

Mechanisms:

- Begin by building on the information collated in Annex A3.
- Ensure mixed formats (online/in person/formal/self-led etc.) to reduce barriers to learning (see Section 2.6)
- Consider how to develop the catalogue, gather learner feedback, keep the catalogue up to date.

In Section 7 we discuss how such information would form part of the proposed TDSA Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue and how it might be used by learners for their career development.

6.3.4 Fill gaps in training

Gap/issue/need: gaps in course provision and skills/knowledge have been identified (see Section 4), in particular:

- There is a general lack of domain-specific courses tailored to the needs of TDSA disciplines, particularly EO and atmospheric science applications.
- Machine learning (ML) – this is a rapidly developing area (see Sections 3 and 4).
- Some mathematical skills (see Section 4)
- Gaps in training provision for individual TDSA roles are summarised in Section 4.1.
- Common training needs looking across the TDSA roles are discussed in Section 3.6.

Opportunity: the TDSA could adapt/develop training to fill the above gaps.

Mechanisms:

- Use the expertise and existing network of staff at universities within the Met Office Academic Partnership (MOAP) to either modify existing courses or create new courses – small modifications to existing courses could represent a “quick win”.
- The prestige of the MOAP universities as course providers would be suitable recognition.
- For face-to-face or online training, the TDSA should make use of existing university graduate courses (see Annex A3). This would involve universities making their courses available to outsiders – this includes both taught content from undergraduate and master’s, and content taught through CDTs. It would also be beneficial for flexibility which allows access to individual modules of BScs/MScs, rather than requiring the whole course to be taken.
- Draw on existing collaborations (see Annex A5).
- Consider how to keep training abreast of technological and other developments. A new process from Innovate UK, called “Workforce Foresighting” shows promise to significantly reduce the time and effort required to identify and define capability statements for new courses including apprenticeships by applying AI to a developing data cube and comparing the statements with those from other countries⁷³. Furthermore, there is a need for a computing infrastructure that keeps pace with technological developments, to facilitate hands-on training.

6.3.5 Certification/accreditation of TDSA training offering

Gap/issue/need: it can be difficult for learners to assess the quality of the numerous training courses available (see Sections 4 and 5)

Opportunity: Consider the benefits of developing certification/accreditation for existing/future training, although we found very mixed views about what certification/accreditation is needed (see Section 5).

Mechanisms:

- Consider what specifications training resources would need to meet in order to be given “TDSA-approved” status, thereby giving credibility for those who make use of them.

- Perhaps the fact that a course is recommended by a future TDSA is a compromise between no certification/accreditation and having to go through the process of getting courses accredited.

We discuss options for course accreditation and certification within the Academy in Sections 5 and ways in which it might be applicable at different career stages in Section 7. However, we recognise that this is still a very open question which will be considered further in Phase 2 of the project.

6.3.6 Support mechanisms

Gap/issue/need: All learners should be supported in their learning and development journeys. This need is particularly acute for those from under-represented groups and those who face particular barriers (see Section 2).

Opportunity: The TDSA should consider developing a variety of support mechanisms, recognising that different support mechanisms may be beneficial for different learners, for example for different learning styles and career stages. In selecting which mechanisms to develop, addressing the following questions may be helpful:

- What does the learner need to do (a technical task, master a skill, set goals, plan steps to achieve a goal, build a network, develop relationships, become more effective)?
- Would the learner likely benefit from hearing from others in some way?
- Who would be most useful to the learner?
- Does the TDSA need to learn something from the process too?
- Is there a clear cohort who might come together?
- If a group situation – how can the TDSA ensure that the group dynamics are supportive of the learning aims?

Mechanisms: Various possible support mechanisms are discussed in Section 1.3 and Section 2.6. In many cases, TDSA partners already have some support schemes available (e.g., mentoring schemes, communities of practice etc). A quick win for the TDSA would be to draw on these existing schemes, and add information on these to the TDSA Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue (see Section 7). In addition, the TDSA may need to develop additional support mechanisms for TDSA learners. We provide further recommendations on support mechanisms appropriate for each career stage in Section 7.

6.3.7 Address barriers to training, learning and development

Gap/issue/need: a range of barriers to learning (such as time, cost, ability to travel) are discussed in Section 2.6

Opportunity: Incorporate solutions to these barriers within the design and operation of the TDSA

Mechanisms:

- Section 2.6 provides a range of solutions to overcome barriers to learning.
- When designing new services in the TDSA, these should pass through a series of EDI checks e.g. Equality Impact Assessments, to make sure that these do not result in barriers to some members of the learning community.

6.4 Exploiting collaborations

The TDSA Project team have already demonstrated a significant partnership between 6 Universities, their academic and professional services, and two small businesses. The TDSA should build on this success. The wider MOAP provides an existing framework for activities such as training, secondments, visits, communities of practice, shared seminars and PhDs. The Met Office has further

partnerships with the NERC Centres (the UK National Climate Science Partnership) and with international meteorological centres (the Momentum partnership, formerly known as the UM Partnership). These partnerships also offer further opportunities for training, learning and development exchanges and experiences, building on established relationships.

We have identified further collaborations (Annex A5) that were declared in the stakeholder workshop and from surveys with TDSA team members. We highlight in Annex A5 potential opportunities/benefits for the TDSA such as exchanges of staff and students, shared projects or data, opportunities for on-the-job training, or face-to-face or online training courses.

During the stakeholder meeting it was noted that there were opportunities for increased collaboration with industry partners (for example, by offering industry/executive training) and secondments between TDSA partners.

Industry collaborations, as well as a potential source of funding, would likely lead to a greater number of applied science projects which can provide significant learning opportunities for individuals.

Collaborations may also provide a source of potential students for the TDSA which in the long-term could increase uptake and therefore the viability of the TDSA.

6.5 Longer term funding for the TDSA

The implementation and business model for the TDSA will be considered in Phase 2 of the project. As part of the business model, there will be a need to consider funding mechanisms for sustainability of the Academy beyond the initial funding from the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT). It seems likely that in the longer-term, the academy may need to access funding from a variety of sources, which may include fee paying individuals and companies. However, to ensure access for a diverse group of learners additional funding may be required. Potential funding bodies in the UK could include:

- **UK Research Innovation (UKRI) funding bodies** such as the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC), Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) and Innovate UK have strategic themes where they target their investments that are reviewed on a regular basis.
 - NERC Centres – each have a training budget and provide training for early career researchers.
 - Doctoral Training – NERC and EPSRC each make strategic investments in doctoral training centres, which also have their own training programmes.
 - Strategic programmes (e.g., NERC’s Digital Research Infrastructure) may also provide funding for targeted training activities.
 - Fellowships support the development of individuals at postdoctoral levels (and in some cases more senior levels). The early career Future Leaders Fellowships⁷⁴ are not restricted to researchers in university environments but can also be held in research and innovation environments in industry.
 - UKRI and the US-based National Science Foundation (NSF) have an agreement and process for funding UK-USA collaborative research grants.
 - Innovate UK provides grants supporting research in industry and Knowledge Transfer Partnerships between academia and industry.
- **Space agencies and programmes** such as the European Space Agency (ESA), European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT), Copernicus and the UK Space Agency (UKSA) invest in training and development initiatives that can include the

development of specific training programmes (e.g., ESA training opportunities⁷⁵) or fellowships (e.g., EUMETSAT fellowships⁷⁶).

- **Sponsorship by the private sector** (for example, the Royal Meteorological Society CPD Masterclasses⁷⁷ have sometimes received sponsorship from Fleet Weather).
- **Philanthropic foundations and charities**
 - Investment in initiatives to help combat climate change that are related to the TDSA roles (e.g., the Bezos Earth Fund has a science and data programme⁷⁸)
 - Investment in initiatives to improve access to higher education (e.g., The UPP Foundation offers support to increase access and retention to higher education and improve student employability⁷⁹)
 - Investment in initiatives increasing percentage of under-represented groups in STEM (see Table 6-1).
- Universities typically fund courses through tuition fees, but may be prepared to invest in initiatives aligned with their strategic priorities.
- **National Academy for Mathematical Sciences⁸⁰** In November 2023, the UK Government announced its intention to support and fund the establishment of a National Academy focused on the mathematical sciences. This Academy is also at a scoping and shaping phase and while it is unclear what role it may have as a funder, the TDSA is clearly aligned with its mission and vision.
- **Other UK Government funding opportunities** such as the AI Upskilling Fund⁸¹ (This particular fund provides support for small and medium-sized enterprises, so the TDSA itself would not qualify but participating organisations may qualify).

Additional uptake, and potential funding, could come from the private sector and through the envisaged transatlantic collaboration.

⁷⁰ WISE My Skills My Life <https://www.wisecampaign.org.uk/my-skills-my-life/> (last accessed 19/03/2024)

⁷¹ Inspiring space resources for secondary teachers <https://www.stem.org.uk/esero/secondary/resources> (last accessed 19/03/2024)

⁷² Space careers UK <https://spacecareers.uk/home> (last accessed 19/02/2024)

⁷³ Innovate UK Workforce Foresighting <https://iuk.ktn-uk.org/programme/workforce-foresighting/> (last accessed 19/03/2024)

⁷⁴ UKRI Future Leaders Fellowships <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/developing-people-and-skills/future-leaders-fellowships/> (last accessed 27/02/2024)

⁷⁵ ESA Training Opportunities https://www.esa.int/Education/ESA_Academy/Training_Future_opportunities (last accessed 27/02/2024)

⁷⁶ EUMETSAT research fellowships <https://www.eumetsat.int/research-fellowships> (last accessed 27/02/2024)

⁷⁷ RMets Meteorological Masterclasses <https://www.rmets.org/news/meteorological-masterclasses> (last accessed 27/02/2024)

⁷⁸ Bezos Earth Fund: Monitoring, Data and Accountability Programme <https://www.bezosearthfund.org/our-programs/monitoring-data-accountability> (last accessed 27/02/2024)

⁷⁹ About the UPP Foundation <https://upp-foundation.org/about-us/> (last accessed 27/02/2024)

⁸⁰ National Academy for the Mathematical Sciences <https://www.acadmathsci.org.uk/> (last accessed 27/02/2024)

⁸¹ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/flexible-ai-upskilling-fund> (last accessed 25/03/2024)

7 Recommendations

7.1 Summary

This section provides options and recommendations for how the Academy can address the key gaps in the UK's training, learning and development, career framework and career development provision for data scientists (DSs), data engineers (DEs), research software engineers (RSEs) and data assimilation scientists (DASs) working in the atmospheric sciences and Earth Observation (EO) sectors. It draws on the evidence and analysis reported in the earlier sections. While many of the previous sections were organised by TDSA role, this section integrates across the roles, exploiting the alignment and overlaps between them. It provides:

- options and recommendations for establishing a suitable career framework,
- a flexible approach to learner journeys that facilitates individually tailored learning plans,
- options and recommendations for formal training, accreditation and recognition, career development and support mechanisms, for each career stage in scope.

7.1.1 Summary of career framework options

Existing career frameworks do not capture the nuances of the roles considered in the TDSA. We provide two options for adapting existing career frameworks:

Option 1: Career framework based on the Digital and Data Profession Capability Framework (DDaT).

- This framework captures the roles of RSE, DE, and DS, but effort would be needed to map the DAS role to the framework.
- The framework could be augmented to include EO skills.
- Career progression via both technical and managerial routes could be utilised.
- Transferability and cross role progression could be implemented using ideas from the Government Science and Engineering framework.

Option 2: Career framework based upon the Government Science and Engineering Framework (GSE).

- The Met Office science framework (under development) uses this as a basis.
- All four TDSA roles would be classed within the GSE deep specialist job family.
- Reclassification of the job families and incorporation of the TDSA job skills would be required.

7.1.2 Summary of learner journey options

The TDSA needs to serve a diverse range of individual learners. At the same time, the Academy needs to be suitable for the requirements of different employers. Hence, we are recommending a flexible model for individual learning journeys, that can be adapted to fit with the existing structures and processes of each employer. The proposed learner journey cycle consists of:

Step 1: Learning needs analysis and personal goal setting, scaffolded by a bespoke TDSA Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue.

Step 2: Carrying out learning and development activities.

Step 3: Personal reflection on progress towards the goals, and on whether the goals are still appropriate, looping back to Step 1 at regular intervals.

Underpinning support mechanisms available to the learner providing help and encouragement for their whole learning journey.

7.1.3 Summary of career stage specific options

For each career stage we have provided options and recommendations for formal training, accreditation and recognition, career development and support mechanisms.

Figures 7-3 to 7-8 provide a further visual summary of the career stage specific options.

16 to 18 year olds

- Summer schools, online learning
- Exposure to different job roles and career options
- Placements and mentoring via academia or industry
- More advanced TDSA learners develop by contribution to outreach or placement supervision

Undergraduates

- Undergraduate projects, summer schools, placements, career webinars
- Bursaries and apprenticeships for further study
- Work experience can be added to CV
- Mentoring by project or placement supervisor

Early career stage 1 (new starters)

- TDSA Foundation course, in-person/hybrid community building workshops, range of self-paced learning, technical upskilling
- “TDSA approved” accreditation for training options
- Exposure to career frameworks and accreditation options, workplace shadowing a variety of roles, regular training plan and review process
- Peer-to-peer learning, communities of practice, mentoring

Early career stage 2 (a few years’ experience)

- Deepen technical skills (or fast-track new skills), “train-the-trainer”
- Modular CPD, external accreditation (e.g., Advanced Data Science Professional), or qualification (e.g., PhD)
- Industrial or policy secondments, delivering training to others, supporting progression from fixed-term to open-ended positions
- Peer-support-networks, technical mentor

Mid-career

- Technical training and accreditation to support further specialisation or transition between roles, secondments (in-person/hybrid/virtual)
- Part-time training programmes
- Management and leadership training to support preparation for promotion to more senior position
- Mentoring from senior colleagues/coaching

Late career (senior roles)

- Online training for specific skills or overview of topic; short, focussed training (away from day job); practical workshops for new technologies/tools; breadth more important than depth
- Recognition via prizes, honorary positions or degrees

- Secondments, sabbaticals, exploration of different sectors (private v public)
- Peer-to-peer mentorship, supporting staff positions (administrative or research)

7.1.4 Outlook

Implementing the TDSA requires cooperation between academia, research institutions, professional organisations, and funding bodies. It will provide motivating careers and career opportunities for a diverse group of learners.

7.2 Career framework options

Having assessed different career frameworks in Section 3.3, we summarise their pros and cons in the context of the TDSA in Table 7-1.

Framework	Pros in context of TDSA	Cons in context of TDSA	Adapt to needs of TDSA?
DDaT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DS, DE and RSE roles exist • RSE has technical AND managerial pathway 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No DA role • Little guidance on using the framework in practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt DDaT for DS, DE, RSE roles? • Develop a DA role based on DDaT skill definitions? • Domain specific skills: EO/ weather/climate?
GSE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Framework emphasises flexibility/transferability for cross-role progression • Clear progression of skill levels across career stage • Highly visual presentation /user friendly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical skill definitions are generic /very broad • Of the four job roles only the deep specialist applies to TDSA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build on the flexibility of cross-role progression but bring in our skills matrix? • Adopt our job role definitions and redefine the technical skill levels scale to match the TDSA's range?
RDF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generic and comprehensive • Includes a lot of professional transferable skills • Comes with a lot of support/ resources • Aligned with European Charter for Researchers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vague – does not specify skills, or knowledge standards for particular roles • Aimed at higher education • Research focused (e.g. does it work for software engineers?) • Many skills are hard to assess, could be tricky for accreditation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt the RDF principles? • Use the RDF as an “outer framework”? • Create an additional “inner framework” for specific skills associated with the four TDSA roles.

Table 7-1: A summary of the career frameworks we have looked at with pros and cons.

Based on the analysis in Section 3.3 it can be clearly seen that existing career frameworks do not capture the nuances of the roles considered in the TDSA. Therefore, two potential ways of incorporating existing career frameworks are presented as options for the academy. The adopted TDSA framework should be made available for all TDSA learners.

7.2.1 Career framework option 1

Build a career framework based upon the existing Digital and Data Profession Capability Framework (DDaT). This framework captures the roles of RSE, DE and DS but lacks the EO focus. Therefore, it could be augmented to include the EO skills outlined in Section 3.5. Further, efforts would be needed to map the role of DAS to the framework. The career progression of both technical and managerial routes could be utilised and improved upon by incorporating the professional and transferable skills outlined in the Researcher Development Framework. To emphasis transferability and cross role progression within the resultant framework, implementation ideas could be borrowed from the Government Science and Engineering framework. In summary this resultant framework would incorporate the EO, technical and professional skills of the four roles and would have a built-in career progression pathway that would emphasis flexibility for cross role progression and two career tracks (technical and managerial routes).

7.2.2 Career framework option 2

An alternative approach is to build a career framework based upon the Government Science and Engineering (GSE) Framework. We understand that this is the case for the science Met Office framework which is currently being developed. Commonality across frameworks within the Met Office would have some clear benefits. However, as outlined in our analysis of the career frameworks (Section 3.3) a drawback of the GSE framework is the generic roles and skills encapsulated. We found that all four data roles would be classed within the GSE deep specialist job family. Therefore, efforts would be needed to reclassify the job families and incorporate the job skills presented in Section 3.5.

7.3 Learner journey options

In this report we have identified that the Academy needs to serve a diverse range of individual learners with different barriers to access learning and development, different backgrounds in terms of existing knowledge and skills, different levels of seniority in their current role, and different personal career goals (Section 2). At the same time, the Academy needs to be suitable for the requirements of different employers. Hence, we are recommending a flexible model for individual learning journeys, that can be adapted to fit with the existing structures and processes of each employer (see Figure 7-1). The proposed learner journey cycle consists of

Step 1: Learning needs analysis and personal goal setting, scaffolded by a bespoke TDSA Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue.

Step 2: Carrying out learning and development activities.

Step 3: Personal reflection on progress towards the goals, and on whether the goals are still appropriate, looping back to Step 1 at regular intervals.

Underpinning support mechanisms available to the learner providing help and encouragement for their whole learning journey.

We now describe the elements of the learner journey cycle in more detail, discussing implementation options and the pros and cons of different approaches.

Figure 7-1: Schematic of the proposed learner journey cycle.

7.3.1 Overall process

Many of the organisations involved will already have an induction process in place for new staff and a periodic review process (often an annual development review) for existing staff that carries out learning needs analysis, goal setting and personal reflection. The Academy learner journey cycle could be integrated into this process without need for a large additional overhead of staff-time, subject to buy-in from employers. Indeed, it is critical that employees and managers do not find themselves needing to follow two completely separate induction and annual review processes, one for their own organisation, and one for the TDSA, as this will be seen as burdensome rather than beneficial.

There may also be a category of TDSA learners where there is no existing annual review process in place (for example, those working for very small enterprises or those participating in the TDSA as an individual). For these learners, the process should be flexible enough to be completed independently, or with the help of an external mentor or coach (see personal goal setting).

7.3.2 Learning needs analysis

Learning needs analysis should be completed by the learner with input from their line manager. This ensures that the analysis can fit the career goals of the TDSA learner, and the performance learning needs of the employer (e.g., technical or transferable skills). This should include identification of any core compulsory training required by the employer.

Learning needs analysis should be linked to the career frameworks (Section 3.3) adopted by the Academy (and by their employer, where these are different), to enable employees to be able to understand potential career paths open to them, to properly identify the gaps in their CV and to progress towards their own career goals.

Options for developing learning needs analysis tools include:

- **Using the Vitae Researcher Development Framework Planner App** (available by subscription⁸²). This is based on the Researcher Development Framework and is particularly useful for

transferable skills for early- to mid-career staff. However, it is a generalist tool and does not include any specific technical skills.

- **Building a bespoke TDSA learning needs analysis tool** based around the career frameworks and skills discussed in this scoping report. This would not include any organisation-specific requirements and may not be fit for purpose for all TDSA-member employers and could remain unused.
- **Each TDSA-member organisation builds its own learning needs analysis tool.** This could potentially build on a generic TDSA template with changes where needed by each organisation. However, this may limit the TDSA's ability to exploit synergies and work effectively across multiple employers.

7.4 TDSA Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue

The Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue will provide a “one-stop-shop” listing

- Formal training courses on technical and scientific topics (this will include existing courses as well as courses that the TDSA develops as suggested in Section 4.
- Ideas for other ways to learn and develop technical and scientific skills (informal learning, peer-to-peer learning, hackathons etc.).
- A directory of support mechanisms and how to access them.
- Key contacts for getting involved in some personal development activities (e.g., public engagement, schools outreach, supervision of placement students etc.).
- Optionally, it could also include professional and transferable skills training courses and ideas prompts.

Development of a suitable platform for the catalogue would be required. Various learning platforms, such as the Totara-based system used at the Met Office, should make managing this straightforward. Learning opportunities can be summarised as a "course" title, with details and access information stored underneath, with tags enabling filtering and various keyword searches. The catalogue should be browsable, enabling TDSA learners to see what is available and deal with the problem of “not knowing what they don't know”. It should also be easily searchable and enable learners to filter by topic, format (in person/online/self-paced/self-driven), career stage, relevance to different roles, time commitment and cost. If some activities are not available to all TDSA learners (e.g., activities only open to staff from a particular employer or country) then this should also be made clear. Groups of "courses" can readily be assembled and promoted together, and such information shared between people.

Options in the catalogue implicitly have a TDSA “seal of approval” so should be chosen carefully. A mechanism should be developed so that external organisations can submit their training products/services for inclusion in the database. Annexes in this report would provide a starting point for the catalogue. Over time, TDSA learners who had taken a given course or activity could also provide reviews for the catalogue. Subsequently, there would be a requirement to maintain the catalogue and keep it up to date.

7.4.1 Personal goal setting

Building on the learning needs analysis and drawing on the TDSA Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue, learners should set goals. These should include short-term measurable targets, incorporating any training required by the employer. However, employees can also consider longer term goals (for example achieving a qualification such as a PhD, accreditation by a professional society, promotion, or a sideways move to a new role). Provision of guided paths could simplify the

process for learners and assist in managing the Academy offering, but these should not be too prescriptive to reflect the diversity of career paths (Figure 7-2).

Longer-term goal setting could be carried out:

- By the individual – this enables confidentiality of the goals, but may result in lack of engagement and reduced commitment, depending on the learner.
- In conjunction with the line manager – this should ensure that the goals are aligned with the organisation’s strategy, but may inhibit open discussion.
- In discussion with a coach or mentor - this could enable additional support, encouragement, and accountability for achieving objectives, but its success is dependent on the coaching or mentoring relationship. In addition, there are cost implications for coaching and time implications for mentors.
- In a pair or group with peers, with or without a facilitator to lead the group. This has the advantage that peers can act as “accountability buddies” and has a smaller financial cost per learner than working one-to-one with a coach, but openness of discussion will depend on the relationships in the group. This could work well for new Academy learners and help with building a cohort identity.

Different goal setting approaches may be appropriate for different career stages.

Figure 7-2: “Careers are not a ladder; they’re a jungle gym. Look for opportunities, look for growth, look for impact, look for mission. Move sideways, move down, move on, move off. Build your skills, not your resume.” Sheryl Sandberg, former COO of Facebook in a speech to Harvard Business School⁸³.

7.4.2 Learning and development activities

Learning and development could include a range of activities. Employees should be encouraged to strike a balance between formal training, informal learning, experiential learning, and developmental

relationships. The balance of learning types should be tailored to the learning preferences of the individual as well as their career stage (see Section 7.57.5).

7.4.3 Personal reflection

Personal reflection on progress towards the goals, and continued appropriateness of the goals could take place as part of the annual review process. However, it may also be appropriate to have more frequent reviews, depending on the circumstances (for example if there is a business need for rapid upskilling, for new starters during a probationary period etc.). As with the goal-setting process, the reflection could be carried out by the individual, in conjunction with the line-manager, a coach or mentor, or with a group of peers.

7.4.4 Support mechanisms

Academy learners should be provided with various options to support their learning. We have already noted some for goal setting. However, support should be available for learners throughout their whole learning journey. This should leverage existing schemes where possible. Some examples include:

- Communities of practice: the Met Office already has communities of practice in data science and for RSEs.
- Peer support groups: these could be created to support staff who are aiming for a specific professional society accreditation such as the Advanced Data Science Professional.
- Mentoring schemes: many MOAP Universities already have mentoring schemes for their staff and research students.
- Coaching: either one-to-one coaching or group coaching.
- Action learning sets.

(See also Table 1-3). It should be noted that these options have different financial and time implications.

7.5 Career stage specific options

This section describes the formal training, career development activities, accreditation and recognition, and support mechanisms required by each career stage. This can be used to help build the TDSA Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue (Section 7.4) so that it can be searchable by career stage. It also makes recommendations specific to a career stage that are not mentioned elsewhere. The scope of the TDSA does not specifically cover those who do not already have an undergraduate degree in a STEM subject. However, such people could be the EO practitioners of the future and the TDSA could encourage them into the EO career pipeline by raising awareness of these careers. We therefore include options for these stages. Examples of personas at different career stages are given in Section 2.

7.5.1 16 to 18 year olds

Figure 7-3: Summary of recommendations for options relating to 16 to 18 year olds.

7.5.1.1 Background to this career stage

Individuals at this stage of their career will be attending high school or college, likely with one or more GCSEs (or US equivalent) in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths) subjects. Their theoretical understanding of EO is expected to be low, with little to no technical skills or coding experience. Their major career goal is to be accepted onto an undergraduate degree program in a STEM subject, and they may face barriers (e.g. low social mobility, disadvantaged backgrounds) to achieve this. An individual at this stage of their career will have had no experience of a professional working environment and will be accustomed to a guided learning approach.

7.5.1.2 Training, development and support opportunities

Most of the formal training opportunities that we have considered so far are likely to be inappropriate at this level, being aimed at individuals with an undergraduate degree in a STEM subject at a minimum. It is possible that some of the training aimed at synthesising knowledge and skills across EO may be applicable to this age group as well as undergraduate/early career stages, however we recommend that the TDSA seek out formal training opportunities aimed specifically at this age range. One such example could be summer schools or placements, where individuals can learn in-person alongside their peers.

We recommend that TDSA partners/participants promote and engage in existing outreach and work experience schemes, such as Nuffield Research Placements and In2scienceUK (see Section 6), as well as providing diverse role model profiles for web pages (see Section 6). Industry organisations and

universities across the UK and USA take part in STEM outreach events for young people in schools. The TSDA could promote EO outreach within existing STEM outreach activities, and provide resources for appropriate activities linked to national curricula. More advanced members of the TSDA could be involved in delivering outreach and placement activities to help them reach their own personal development goals.

It is also important for individuals in this age range to be given the opportunity to broaden their understanding of the wider field in order to begin to explore potential future areas of specialism. The career framework recommendations in Section 7.2 would help to support this by outlining potential career progression for different job roles within the field of EO. Having access to a list of degree apprenticeships (see Sections 4 and 5) and undergraduate courses that can lead to EO career opportunities would be beneficial.

If possible, we recommend that both online and offline mechanisms of support be adopted, to account for individual learning requirements as well as provide opportunities to communicate with academy members on both sides of the Atlantic.

7.5.2 Undergraduates

Figure 7-4: Summary of recommendations for options relating to undergraduates.

7.5.2.1 Background to this career stage

This covers anyone who is studying for an undergraduate degree (STEM subjects in particular) as well as those who are taking a degree apprenticeship and working while studying. They may have already chosen a career in this sector, or they may not have chosen a career but be making decisions that will affect their career options. They may not have thought about or be aware of specific job roles they

would want to get in to. Compared to 16 to 18 year olds they should be beginning to do some self-guided learning, although are still dependent on guidance from their tutors and lecturers.

7.5.2.2 Formal training

The TDSA could promote undergraduate projects in EO through its partner universities to expose undergraduates to possible EO careers. These often include an element of professional transferable skills (such as written and oral communication and group work). The TDSA could provide suitable suggestions of formal courses/learning ideas for these skills in its learning catalogue.

7.5.2.3 Career development activities

Undergraduates may need guidance in choosing a career path and more exposure to possible EO careers to encourage them into the field or help them decide what their career goals might be. The TDSA could provide access to their EO career frameworks (Section 7.2) as well as providing access to databases of available MScs, PhDs, and jobs in the EO field. The TDSA could develop its own database or provide input to other websites such as spacecareers.uk.

People at this career stage could make use of a range of potential activities organised or supported through the TDSA such as: seminars, placements (e.g., summer or year-long “sandwich” placements), summer schools, bursaries for further study and degree apprenticeships.

7.5.2.4 Accreditation and recognition

Undergraduates will be accredited by gaining their undergraduate degree but can include on their CV any work experience gained.

7.5.2.5 Support mechanisms

For any work placements, support would be required from practitioners to come up with projects and for them to supervise and mentor the students while working on the project. Mentoring a work placement student would give more senior TDSA learners opportunities for their own career development. The TDSA could oversee the pairing of students and projects, although offering placements via existing schemes (see examples in Section 6.3) would reduce this overhead. Sources of funding for placement student stipends also need to be considered.

7.5.3 Early career stage 1

Figure 7-5: Summary of recommendations for options relating to early career stage 1 (new starter).

7.5.3.1 Background to this career stage

Individuals in this stage of their career are expected to arrive from one of three routes, each with distinct training requirements.

Firstly, they could have a STEM undergraduate degree. As such, their understanding of TDSA-relevant topics is likely to be highly theoretical. Individuals from this background are expected to lack significant practical experience handling “big” data as well as technical skills in data analysis, coding, version control and machine learning (ML). If they are employed in their first role outside the realm of higher education, they are also probably deficient in soft skills such as workload management and working effectively in collaborative environments. An individual at this stage of their career may lack knowledge of the different career roles and typical progression routes available within the field. Additionally, they will likely be accustomed to a guided learning approach and may find self-guided learning a new challenge.

Secondly, they could have completed an apprenticeship, and have gained workplace experience including practical use of technical skills, perhaps even in a weather and climate environment.

An alternative entry route would be an individual who has developed (some) useful technical skills and is now wanting to apply these to a weather/climate/EO situation for the first time.

Personas 1 and 2 in Section 2 provide examples of individuals at this career stage.

7.5.3.2 Formal training

Early career individuals may approach the TDSA from a variety of academic and technical backgrounds. A conversion course or courses could help to fill any gaps and bring people up-to-speed. Such courses should cover the fundamentals of EO as well as introducing the individual to technical skills such as data science and ML. We envisage the TDSA Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue would provide information about such courses (see Section 3.6). We also recommend that such a programme be made available more than once a year.

A lack of experience in technical skills such as coding and version control could also be addressed outside of a conversion course, through the provision of practical courses and hackathons. Again, we envisage the TDSA Learning and Development Ideas Catalogue would provide information about such courses (see Section 3.6).

Since there will be a strong focus on formal training for early career individuals, we recommend that a broad range of online learning be made available to take advantage of at their own pace. However, as they are just beginning their career in EO, individuals will have few (if any) connections to others within the field; we therefore recommend that there is an option for some formal training to also be provided in-person to help foster a sense of community.

7.5.3.3 Career development activities

At this stage of their career, it will be important for an individual to broaden their understanding of the wider field in order to determine potential future areas of specialism, and, if desired, routes to professional accreditation. The career framework recommendations in Section 7.2 would help to support this by outlining potential career progression for different job roles within the field of EO. A longer-term approach is to assist individuals to gain experience working in a variety of roles and across EO disciplines, which could be achieved through the introduction of mentorships (which also have the benefit of encouraging and empowering the mentee, especially if they are from disadvantaged or under-represented backgrounds) and/or shadowing schemes. This may be achievable within the confines of the individual's organisation, or it may require collaboration across multiple institutions. The TDSA could facilitate such an effort by virtue of its wide network, by communicating opportunities, or perhaps providing guidance on best practice.

We recommend that regular reviews take place between the individual and their line manager to continually review their progression and assess ongoing training needs (see Section 7.3).

7.5.3.4 Accreditation and recognition

Since an individual in this category is only just beginning to determine their future career trajectory, it is likely that accreditation and recognition are less important than for an individual at a more advanced career stage. However, it is important that learners are exposed to accreditation options, so that they can begin to build their CV towards accreditation if they wish to.

If training material or courses were marked as "TDSA-approved", it is likely that more people would take advantage of these, to gain credibility amongst their peers and bolster their CV. Such a label would need to amount to something; therefore this would require the TDSA to evaluate their list of training materials and courses and ensure that they hold up to a pre-determined standard, which would be a significant undertaking (see Section 5).

Another suggestion is that the TDSA recommend to training providers that they issue a form of recognition (e.g. a certificate) for any training that requires a level of assessment, as this is a way for individuals to prove new skills or knowledge learned (as opposed to having simply attended a training course) (see Section 5).

7.5.3.5 *Support mechanisms*

It should be recognised that training for these individuals will necessarily be front-loaded for the first year or two. In support of this, we recommend that a significant training budget be allocated and supported by the individual's line manager and re-assessed at regular intervals. Given this investment, retention of trained staff is an important consideration. Staff retention can be aided by provision of clear career pathways and opportunities for advancement, as well as supportive environments. In particular, we recommend that line managers recognise that self-driven learning is likely to be a new concept for many individuals, and should provide encouragement as needed.

Individuals could benefit from peer-mentoring through a "buddy system" i.e. from a person who is at the same stage of career but perhaps slightly further along in their professional development. We recommend that this is achieved within their workplace (we envisage that this would be organised by the individual's line manager, potentially with guidance and advice from the TDSA.)

Communities of practice (CoPs) can be a valuable resource for learning from peers and seniors alike. These can be established with a particular technical focus, for different EO roles, or to simply create a community of support for individuals at identical career stages or with similar protected characteristics. We recommend that the TDSA should collate and maintain a database of CoPs as resources for new members of the academy.

We recommend that both online and offline mechanisms of support be adopted, to account for individual learning requirements as well as provide opportunities to communicate with academy members on both sides of the Atlantic. For example, CoPs could be developed using social platforms such as Slack and Discord which both have free versions available.

7.5.4 Early career stage 2

Figure 7-6: Summary of recommendations for options relating to early career stage 2 (a few years' experience).

7.5.4.1 Background to this career stage

This stage refers to those likely to have a PhD and a number of years' experience in their field. They are likely to be considered knowledgeable (i.e. at least "practitioner", perhaps "expert", from the DDaT terminology) in at least one given technical field.

In an academic role, they may still be in a fixed-term contract and this may be the time when they consider whether to apply for a permanent academic contract, or to leave academia. In both non-academic and academic roles, an individual at this stage has valuable experience, is more employable than those at earlier stages and, therefore, may be considering moving on. Thus, attrition is greater at this stage than at other stages in the career ladder.

At this stage they may have young families, so may have specific caring requirements / modified working hours.

Personas 3 and 4 in Section 2 provide examples of individuals at this career stage.

7.5.4.2 Formal training

Technical training at this stage can either take the form of deepening understanding of a topic they have some familiarity with (e.g. rapid expansion of knowledge in one topic), or a very rapid introduction to a new topic, with the understanding that many introductory underlying topics may not need to be covered because of pre-existing knowledge. The assumption is that focussed training from an expert is likely to be more time efficient than equivalent self-teaching.

Staff at this level may benefit from improving a range of professional and transferable skills. For example:

- **Communication and teaching:** many staff at this level will have benefitted from both formal and informal training throughout their career to date and may feel they would like to be involved in passing on their knowledge to less experienced staff. “Train-the-trainer” courses may not need to be domain specific.
- **Policy and influencing:** training in how to communicate complex ideas to a lay person and how to influence policy; and development of an understanding of the EO sector and the context they are working in.
- **Management and leadership training:** This is likely to be a key stage when they start being involved in management of junior staff, leadership of projects, and writing funding proposals – all of which will benefit from focussed training.

7.5.4.3 Career development activities

For individuals who are looking at increasing interdisciplinary work (e.g. collaborative opportunities outside of their team), development of secondment activities with academic, industrial and policy (either public or third sector) partners may be important. Less formal structures, e.g. creation of new relationships to work on applied projects may also be valuable in some contexts.

As has already been discussed, there is anecdotal evidence that at this career stage there is a relatively high attrition rate, compared to other career stages. Ways to mitigate this could be:

- Ensure there are clear career paths up to a senior level (see Section 7.2).
- There should be career paths for individuals who are following both technical and management pathways.
- Provide support for individuals who need guidance about which path to take.
- Involve staff at this stage in developing project proposals so that they have buy-in to the projects that they work on.
- For those with precarious fixed-term contracts, set goals so that there are clear targets which will help them apply for permanent positions (e.g. in academia these could be with either lectureship or technical positions).
- Consider remote working or other options for staff with the “two-body problem” (where life partners find it difficult to obtain jobs within reasonable commuting distance of each other).

It should be recognised that some individuals will be keen to leave the TDSA fields at this stage, and some support could be given to them to help transition into alternative industries/roles.

Networking opportunities may help individuals to determine next steps by understanding what opportunities are available in other organisations, and/or creation of new collaborations/relationships.

7.5.4.4 Accreditation and recognition

As discussed in Section 5, individuals are likely to view accreditation, certification, and recognition with differing value depending on their job role, employer, and short-to-medium career goals. Individuals who are keen and likely to stay in a similar field are less likely to value accreditation than those who are open to moving job sector. For those who have progressed via a slightly more technical, rather than research, focussed career-path, then undertaking a part-time PhD may be of some use, particularly if there is an industrial or knowledge-exchange component.

Conversely, commercial and third-sector employees may wish to undertake an upskilling credit-bearing course (e.g. a diploma in Data Science), or work towards a professional accreditation such as Chartership or the Advanced Data Science Professional, which may help promotion prospects.

7.5.4.5 Support mechanisms

As with other career cohorts, peer-led (or peer-to-peer) sessions can be seen as valuable and can help create new networks.

However, a technical mentor is likely to be useful where the goal is upskilling in a key technology, and this could either be 1:1 or in a small group setting. This can help highlight growth areas that the individual wants to focus on, and direct new opportunities that the mentor may be aware of.

However, as noted earlier, this career stage may also have a disproportionately high number involved in caring needs, and so there is likely to be a requirement for flexible learning for courses (both online and in-person).

Where appropriate, we suggest that a budget to help support training needs (to either fund attending a course, or to provide mentoring) is provided, to ensure that employees feel valued, and that the employer understands the needs of external training, mentoring, and coaching.

7.5.5 Mid-career

Figure 7-7: Summary of recommendations for options relating to mid-career.

7.5.5.1 Background to this career stage

A mid-career is typically one which is well-established. An individual at this stage of their career may have or begin to have various job responsibilities (including managerial beyond technical), although

may have chosen a technical specialist career path without significant management responsibilities. They will typically also have various other responsibilities such as family. A mid-career individual may wish to develop their technical skills further to specialise in specific areas within their job-domain, develop their leadership and managerial skills in order to set the stage for promotion to more senior roles, and potentially switch to adjacent job roles (e.g. from a DE role to a DS one). A mid-career individual may face various barriers preventing them from undertaking a training & development programme, such as:

- Their current role may not allow the flexibility to undertake a significant upskilling programme on a full-time basis, due to day-to-day and managerial responsibilities, although part-time programmes can be possible where aligned with their job role (e.g., 50% FTE MSc or PhD, part-time leadership programme).
- Other personal or family responsibilities (e.g. childcare ones) may also prevent the mid-career to find time to upskill further.

Personas 5 and 6 in Section 2 provide examples of individuals at this career stage.

7.5.5.2 Formal training

Mid-career individuals will likely require specialised support within their chosen domain (e.g. data science, data engineering) in order to progress into more advanced technical role, or possibly in adjacent domains in order to support the transition from one role to another. It may be relevant for formal training programmes to provide individuals with the flexibility to undertake development, despite various professional or personal responsibilities – for example part-time programmes, aligned with their work, may enable the mid-career staff member to achieve their objectives.

7.5.5.3 Career development activities

Individuals at this career stage could benefit from leadership and managerial training in order to support their transition to more senior roles (e.g. head of technical teams). It may be necessary for career development programmes to be delivered in a flexible way.

7.5.5.4 Accreditation and recognition

The mid-career individual may benefit from some form of certification to enable them to transition to other adjacent roles or roles with added responsibilities.

7.5.5.5 Support mechanisms

A mid-career individual may also benefit from dedicated mentoring from more senior colleagues, such as advice about how to shape their career going forward, or to receive career coaching to help them reach their goals.

7.5.6 Late career (senior roles)

Figure 7-8: Summary of recommendations for options relating to late career/senior roles.

7.5.6.1 Background to this career stage

This section discusses those in a late career stage and in senior roles, as managers and/or in strategic leadership positions. Learners who are late in their career in the sense that they are nearing their retirement, but who are not in roles with senior responsibilities are covered by the mid-career section.

People in senior roles are often busy juggling many distinct responsibilities. Although they may be more confident in asking for support for learning and career development, they often have less time to dedicate to training activities. Many senior roles involve management of a team, and it would not be unusual for someone to be managing a team working outside their own specialisation. For example, data science teams may be led by someone who is not a DS. In these cases, the manager needs to have sufficient understanding of what their team is doing in order to direct them effectively, without necessarily knowing all the details of the work involved; breadth of knowledge is more important than depth.

Personas 7 and 8 in Section 2 provide examples of individuals at this career stage.

7.5.6.2 Formal training

The development of tailored, online training modules for specific skills or for an overview of a specific topic would be useful for people in senior roles, to allow them to rapidly get up to speed on a topic at a time which suits them. For more essential skills, short, focussed training events away from

their day job would be most effective. This could include one-day practical workshops or masterclasses demonstrating new tools or technologies, as well as longer (up to a week) retreats to focus on intensive learning. The TDSA Learning and Ideas Catalogue would provide a list of suitable courses.

7.5.6.3 *Career development activities*

A useful career development activity for people in senior roles is to take up a secondment or to have a sabbatical, to gain experience working elsewhere and in a different environment. This could include experience in the public or private sectors and, in the context of the TDSA, could be with institutes in the USA. We recommend that the TDSA has a person whose role it is to facilitate secondments, including looking for new opportunities and dealing with practical issues such as travel and work visas. Potential opportunities for secondments or other collaborations could be collated and held in a central database for staff to consult.

7.5.6.4 *Accreditation and recognition*

At a senior level, recognition is usually more important than accreditation. Such recognition could include things such as prizes, honorary positions or degrees. The TDSA could help facilitate honorary visiting positions at other institutes for appropriate staff. It may be useful to find a mechanism to recognise when someone has gained basic skills in a certain area, for example when someone moves into managing an area they are not familiar with. However, at a senior level it may be that experience is more widely recognised than any certification.

7.5.6.5 *Support mechanisms*

We recommend that a peer-to-peer mentoring scheme is put in place to support people in senior roles. In some cases, it can be helpful if the mentor is from a different organisation from the mentee, and is able to act as a “critical friend”.

It is essential that people perceive their training as something that is valued by their employer, and so it is useful if they have a dedicated budget for training in terms of both the financial cost and time (for example, a certain number of days per year set aside for formal training).

In order to free up some time and achieve their goals, people in senior roles require funding for appropriate support staff, whether this be to carry out administrative tasks, or to take forward research projects (e.g. PhD or postdoc positions in academia).

7.6 Conclusion

Addressing the identified gaps in learning, development, and career framework provision for TDSA roles requires a collaborative effort involving academia, research institutions, professional organisations, and funding bodies.

By providing learners with ideas for personal development, signposting existing courses, developing specialised training programmes, improving accessibility, improving learner support mechanisms and establishing clearer career pathways, we can empower a diverse group of current and future TDSA professionals with the skills and knowledge necessary to excel in their fields and contribute to advancements in atmospheric science and EO.

⁸² Researcher Development Framework Planner <https://rdfplanner.vitae.ac.uk/> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

⁸³ Georgina Pacor (2023) Why employees are choosing the “jungle gym” over the “career ladder” <https://www.aigroup.com.au/resourcecentre/resource-centre-blogs/hr-blogs/Why-employees-are-choosing-the-jungle-gym-over-the-career-ladder> (last accessed 26/02/2024)

Annexes

A1 Participant data protection

A1.1 Gathering personal data

During the TDSA Scoping study, the project team collected information from a range of stakeholders, as well as from secondary sources. Some of the information collected was personal data including “special category” data such as ethnicity.

In this section we lay out the policies and procedures that the project team used to facilitate informed consent, protection of personal data and interview good practice.

A1.2 TDSA Data Protection Policy

This document sets out the requirements for the collection, handling, storage and destruction of personal data used in research activities for the Transatlantic Data Science Academy.

A1.2.1 Legal obligations

Data of UK residents is subject to the UK GDPR the law that sets out the requirements for the protection of personal data. As both the EU and UK versions of the GDPR are currently aligned, statements that refer to the ‘GDPR’ will serve to cover both regimes.

The Data Protection Act 2018 contains additional provisions and requirements for the processing of data in the UK as well as the powers of our Data Protection Authority (regulator).

The TDSA Scoping project must meet the requirements of both the ‘GDPR’ and the ‘Data Protection Act 2018’

A1.2.2 Data protection principles

Under data protection law we are required to ensure and demonstrate that personal data is:

1. used fairly, lawfully and transparently;
2. collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes;
3. adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for the purposes;
4. accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date;
5. kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes;
6. kept secure with appropriate technical and organisational measures

Further specific discussion of these principles is available in the document “Data Protection for Researchers” available from the University of Reading.

A1.2.3 Data Protection Procedures in this Project

1. **Obtain informed consent from study participants** Please use the template interview information sheet and ensure that each interviewee is given a copy. Interview consent forms should be digitised and placed on file in the relevant folder in the MS Team

Information should be provided for workshop participants on the purposes of the study, and consent obtained at registration.

2. **Access to personal data** Access to personal data is on a need-to-know basis. Our legal collaboration agreements specify that we will exchange personal data between members of the project team. However, **our agreement with the Met Office says that no personal information will be exchanged with them.** For

example, if there is discussion at a meeting with the Met Office involving personally identifiable information, then we will need to ask any Met Office participants to step out of the room.

3. **Data controllers** Each partner in the team will be a “data controller”, meaning that you can collect, store and process the personal information.
4. **Specificity of personal data to be collected.** Collect the minimum amount of personal data in order to fulfil the goals of the project. Given the aims of the project around diversity, this may include special category data as defined by GPDR (e.g., race, gender) and this will need to be made clear to participants.
5. **Data collection and storage.** Information is likely to be collected and stored using different media. You should map your own data workflow and identify measures for securing the personal data in its hold locations and in transit between them.

Files that include special category data should be password protected.

If you take paper notes from a meeting then these should be shredded when no longer needed.

The central repository for files is the MS Team.

Files containing notes from interviews and personally identifiable information should be carefully stored for the duration of the project. Once the research is completed and the results published, an anonymised archive will be kept and all files with personally identifiable information deleted.

[A1.3 Stakeholder workshop registration form](#)

Help us shape the Transatlantic Data Science Academy for Weather and Climate

The UK Met Office is establishing a Transatlantic Data Science Academy, working in partnership with the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA).

The Academy aims to address a shortage of skills in:

- data science
- data engineering
- data assimilation and
- research software engineering

Such skills increasingly underpin weather and climate science and the exploitation of Earth observation data. A consortium of Universities from the Met Office Academic Partnership is helping to shape the Academy and provide a blueprint for its implementation.

Online Workshop 12 December 1400-1600 (UTC)

We are holding an online workshop to gather views from the community on training, learning and career development gaps. Please fill in this form to register your attendance

What if I am unable to attend the workshop but would like to give my views or be kept informed about outcomes?

Please fill in this form to indicate your interest. There will be other opportunities to participate, for example through surveys and interviews. We will publish a report on the findings of the project.

What about protection of my personal information?

The data gathered in the workshop will be analysed as part of the project. Anonymised results will be published. No personally identifiable information will be published. We will always have in place appropriate safeguards to protect your personal data.

Should you wish to be removed from the register at a later date, you should contact Prof Sarah L Dance (s.l.dance@reading.ac.uk).

Queries regarding data protection and your rights should be directed to the University of Reading Data Protection Officer at imps@reading.ac.uk, or in writing to: University of Reading, Information Management & Policy Services, Whiteknights House, Pepper Lane, Whiteknights, Reading , RG6 6UR, UK.

* Required

1. First name *

2. Last name *

3. Email address *

4. Affiliation (Employer/University etc.) *

5. Interest in the project: please select any of the following options that apply to you *

- I would like to attend the workshop on 12th December 2023
- I am unable to attend the workshop but would be interested in giving my input to the project team
- I would like to be informed about project publications

6. To which gender identity do you most identify? (We are collecting this data to ensure we reach a diverse group of participants) *

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say
- Other

7. Which race or ethnicity best describes you? Please choose only one. (We are collecting this data to ensure we reach a diverse group of participants). *

- White
- Black / African / Caribbean / Black British
- Asian / Asian British
- Mixed / Multiple ethnic groups
- Other
- Prefer not to say

8. Where are you based? *

- UK
- USA
- Prefer not to say
- Other

9. About you: Do you or have you previously worked in any of these roles? Please select all that apply. *

- Data Scientist
- Data Assimilation Scientist
- Data Engineer
- Research Software Engineer
- Training/Learning and Development Professional

- Employee or Representative of a Professional Society
- Prefer not to say
- Other

10. About you: Who is your current employer? *

- Unemployed
- Student
- Researcher/Academic employed in a University or Research Institute
- National or regional meteorological centre
- Commercial sector
- Prefer not to say
- Other

9. What is your career stage? *

- Early career (within 10 years of your highest degree)
- Mid-career (10+ years after your highest degree but not holding a senior role)
- Senior (holding a senior role in your organisation)
- Prefer not to say

A1.4 Interview preparation checklist

A1.4.1 Before the interview

Stakeholder management and data protection

- Inform TDSA team at biweekly meeting who you plan to interview or contact for feedback/other planned contact
- Allow for co-planning with other tasks
- Check name is not already in stakeholder management spreadsheet
- Record name, email, contact/interview date, interviewer and consent status for future contact in stakeholder management spreadsheet
- Create unique pseudonymisation key and record in same stakeholder management spreadsheet
- Provide the interviewee with the interview information sheet and interview consent form

Logistics

- Make polite contact with the interviewee
- Ensure that the interviewee is informed of time and place of the interview, interview duration
- Consider sending the interview questions in advance
- Make sure you know how you are going to record information from the interview and any microphones and recording equipment work. If you are using teams you may want to check that transcription is turned on.
- Do you have a backup plan if the interviewee does not want to be directly recorded?
- Write yourself an interview guide that you can use through the interview

A1.4.2 During the interview

Stakeholder management and data protection

- At the beginning of the interview Ensure that you explain the purpose of the interview and how the data will be used
- Ensure that the participant consent form is completed

Interview good practice

- Begin the interview with easy to answer questions about noncontroversial topics
- Ask follow-up questions as appropriate, for greater depth, detail and clarity.
- Save the socio-demographic questions (gender, race etc.) for the end or space them strategically throughout the interview. Some information may be needed to make sense of the rest of the interview. Avoid beginning an interview with a long list of routine demographic questions.
- Observe and build rapport by conveying empathy and understanding without judgement. Be mindful that too much rapport may result in the interview overrunning.
- Listen actively, show interest and offer encouragement through giving appropriate feedback to the interviewees, such as head nodding, taking notes. If responses are getting off the track, it is your responsibility to interrupt politely with respect and sensitivity.
- Make smooth transitions between sections of the interview or topics. Questions prefaced by transition statements help smooth the flow of an interview, alert the interviewees to the nature of the upcoming question, and give them a few seconds to organise their thoughts before responding.
- Take notes during an interview to track questions asked and answer received, and to locate important quotations. However, be mindful that taking notes affects the process of interviewing. You may have a difficult time responding appropriately to interviewee needs and cues.
- If you find that the person to be interviewed is unwilling to cooperate or needs to leave, it is helpful to have a single, one-short question in mind to ask before they leave.
- Provide an opportunity for the interviewee to have the final say at the end of the interview. It can also be helpful to leave interviewees with a way to contact you in case they want to add something that they forgot to mention or clarify some points.

A1.4.3 After the interview

Interview good practice

- Check the recording to make sure it worked immediately after a recorded interview.
- If for some reason, a malfunction occurred, you should immediately make extensive note of everything that you can remember.
- Even if the recorder functioned properly, you should go over the interview notes to ensure that they make sense. This also allows you to uncover areas of ambiguity or uncertainty
- If you find things that do not quite make sense, as soon as possible check back with the interviewee for clarification.
- Reflect on the quality of information received, new ideas jumped up, weakness and problems such as poorly worded questions, wrong topics, poor rapport and disruptive settings.
- Make notes on the interview process while the experience is still fresh in your mind.
- Initiate analysis early and this allows you to become more aware of emerging categories and themes.
- Prepare the data for analysis and move data into a format that is easy to manipulate. A good starting point is to make transcripts. You then can read through and re-read the transcripts, make notes and memos, focusing on what participants said.
- When transcribing your data, you should anonymise as you go and make sure participants are not identifiable from transcriptions.
- Write a note to thank the interviewee for their time

Stakeholder management and data protection

- Files that include special category data should be password protected (in your own file system).
- If you take paper notes from a meeting then these should be shredded when no longer needed.

- Create pseudonymised version of interview data collected for upload to group repository on the MS Team. This means that the interview data file itself does not contain personally identifiable information – but can be linked back to the individual using the pseudonymisation key. The pseudonymised data does not need to be password protected.

A1.5 Interview guide script

Preliminaries

- Interviewer introduces themselves (to be recorded in interview notes)
- Note date and time of recording for interview notes
- Note name of interviewee for interview notes
- Note affiliation (employer/university) for interview notes

Interview procedure

You are being asked to participate in a scoping study for the Transatlantic Data Science Academy. The UK Met Office is establishing a Transatlantic Data Science Academy, working in partnership with the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA).

The Academy aims to address skills shortages in: data science, data engineering, data assimilation and research software engineering for weather and climate applications, and to increase diversity in the skills pipeline. A consortium of Universities from the Met Office Academic Partnership is helping to shape the Academy and provide a blueprint for its implementation. We want to gather your views on training, learning and career development gaps.

During the interview, you will be asked questions in terms of your experiences and perceptions. You may choose not to answer any or all of the questions. The procedure will be recorded and transcribed verbatim. Your answers will be confidential to the project team, and you will not be identified individually.

Informed consent

Make sure that you have a copy of the signed informed consent form. If you do not then you need to take the interviewee verbally through the questions on the consent form and obtained verbal consent to be backed up by a signed copy later.

Questions

1. What is your current role? How long have you been working in this role? [This should make it clear whether they are early, mid- or late career if not then ask]

Technical expertise

2. Can you talk about the learning path you took to get to your current level of technical expertise?
3. What were the barriers that you faced or face currently? Did you ever feel that you were unable to access the training that you needed?
4. From your experience, what do you believe are the crucial components or skills that should be covered in comprehensive technical courses or programs in this area? Do you prefer to learn through courses or by on-the-job training or other methods?
5. At your current level of expertise, are you aware of learning or continuing professional development opportunities (online / in-person, self-guided / taught, workshops, conferences, peer to peer learning)

etc.) that are available to improve your technical knowledge and skills? Are there specific gaps that you would like to see filled, and how?

6. What time and budget is generally made available for staff to attend training or to participate in development activities (secondments, workshops, conferences etc.)?

Career development and frameworks, personal development & accreditation

7. For your own career development, what are your aspirations?
8. What is the career framework in your organisation, and do you feel that there is support in place to help you get to the next level? (Are you able to share any information with us about job descriptions or career frameworks?)
9. Are there specific transferable (non-technical) skills that you need to develop or experience that you need to have to help you reach your aspirations? What opportunities are you aware of that can help you meet your aspirations?
10. Do you have any professional accreditations (e.g., chartered meteorologist, advanced data science professional)? Do you feel these have been/would be useful in your career?

Opportunities

11. Are you aware of any opportunities that the academy should take advantage of in terms of funding, partnerships, UK or international connections? Are there specific types of activities that would be beneficial (internships, secondments, exchanges)?
12. Demographic information: (explain that we are collecting demographic information to ensure that we collect information from a diverse group of participants)
 - a. To which gender identity do you most identify? (male, female, non-binary, prefer not to say)
 - b. Which race or ethnicity best describes you?

Wrap up question

13. Is there anything else you would like to tell us about yourself, or that you think it would be useful for the academy to take on board?

Closing

Thank you for participating in this interview. We appreciate you taking the time to do this. May we contact you in the future if we have any more queries to follow up? Again, let me assure you of the confidentiality of your responses and our protection of your personal data. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me by email.

A2 Skills matrix

An assessment of the typical, key technical skills for each of the TDSA roles. 0 for not relevant, 1 for awareness, 2 for working, 3 for practitioner and 4 for expert. See further details in Section 3.

Earth Observation skills	Data scientist	Data engineer	Research software engineer	Data assimilation scientist
Satellite platforms	3	2	0	4
Radiative transfer	1	1	0	3
Retrieval (<i>also intended to encompass other related techniques</i>)	2	1	0	4
Other observation platforms (weather radar, ground-based remote sensing, and other commonly used observing systems)	3	2	0	4
Atmospheric physics	1	1	0	2
Dynamical meteorology/oceanography	1	1	0	2
Land surface dynamics	1	1	0	2
NWP, NWP parametrizations	2	1	1	3
Ensemble forecasting	2	1	0	3

Mathematical and statistical skills	Data scientist	Data engineer	Research software engineer	Data assimilation scientist
Uncertainty quantification	2	2	2	4
Bayesian statistics	2	1	0	3
Design of experiments	2	1	1	1
Regression, classification, clustering	4	2	1	2
Deep-learning/transformer models	4	2	1	1
Graph neural networks	4	1	2	1
Normalising flows	4	3	0	0
Generative models (e.g. large-language models (LLMs), diffusion models)	4	1	0	0
Computer vision	4	1	3	0
Natural language processing (NLP)	4	1	2	0
Data assimilation theory	1	1	0	4
Numerical linear algebra	2	3	2	4
Spatial grid generation	1	1	1	2
Numerical methods for partial differential equations (PDEs)	1	1	1	2
Numerical optimisation of functions	1	1	1	3
Nonlinear dynamical systems	1	1	1	2
Computational fluid dynamics	1	1	1	2

Computer and data science skills	Data scientist	Data engineer	Research software engineer	Data assimilation scientist
Database management	1	4	1	1
Database querying (SQL/noSQL)	2	4	2	2

Data transfer; extract, transform, load (ETL)	1	4	1	2
Data linkage	1	4	1	1
Building data pipelines	2	4	2	1
Data preprocessing/wrangling	4	4	2	2
Data understanding/exploration	4	4	1	3
Data visualisation	4	2	1	3
Statistical modelling	4	1	2	2
Training machine learning models	4	1	1	2
Deploying machine learning models (MLOps)	4	2	3	2
High-performance computing (HPC)	3	3	3	3
Cloud infrastructure	3	3	2	1
Shell scripting	3	3	3	3
Preparing code for GPU/machine learning (ML) - stack porting	3	2	4	1
Developing user interfaces	1	1	4	0
Develop, maintain, extend research software	2	1	4	3

Technology	Data scientist	Data engineer	Research software engineer	Data assimilation scientist
SQL/noSQL/graph databases	2	4	2	0
Hierarchical Data Format version 5 (HDF5) and other compressed file types	1	3	1	1
Google Colab/Jupyter notebooks	4	4	1	3
Integrated development environments (IDEs) (e.g., Visual Studio (VS), Eclips, etc.)	4	2	4	2
Java	1	2	4	0
JavaScript	1	1	4	0
Python	4	4	3	3
Julia	2	2	2	0
C	2	2	2	0
C++	4	2	3	3
R	4	2	0	0
Fortran	0	2	3	3
Unix/Linux	2	3	3	3
Scaling/acceleration on CPU, GPU	2	2	3	1
Message Passing Interface (MPI)	0	1	2	2

A3 Existing training provision

This table includes training known to the project team and there may be relevant provision that has been omitted.

Title of training/development opportunity	Brief description	Links	Provider	Level ¹	Role	Style/method of delivery	Cost, if known
Introduction to Linux		https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/research/arc/bear/training/intro-linux.aspx	University of Birmingham	B	RSE		
Introduction to BlueBEAR (HPC)		https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/research/arc/bear/training/necessities.aspx		B	RSE	Online, face-to-face/virtual self-enrol	
BEAR Carpentries	Foundational coding and data science skills.	https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/research/arc/bear/training/the-carpentries-courses.aspx		B	RSE		
AI and Deep Learning	Fundamentals of deep learning, training and deploying neural networks.	https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/research/arc/bear/training/ai-and-deep-learning.aspx		B	DS		
Data Engineering	GPU, data pipelines, advanced data engineering tools and techniques, performance acceleration.	https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/research/arc/bear/training/data-engineering.aspx		B	DE		
MSc Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning	Principles of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning.	https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/postgraduate/courses/taught/computer-science/artificial-intelligence.aspx		I	DS	In person	
MSc Data Science	Data science.	https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/postgraduate/courses/taught/computer-science/data-science.aspx		I	DS	In person	
<i>Examples of Space4Climate courses</i>							
<i>Space4Climate</i>		https://space4climate.com/free-training-courses-for-earth-observation-skills/	Space4Climate				Free

¹ Level: B=basic, I=intermediate, A=advanced.

Learn to harness the power of space data	Understanding Copernicus data and services.	https://www.copernicus.eu/en/opportunities/education/copernicus-mooc	Copernicus	B		Online, any time	Free
Monitoring climate from space	Satellite Earth Observation technology.	https://www.imperativemoocs.com/courses/monitoring-climate-from-space	ESA	B		Online, any time	Free
<i>Examples courses through OnlineTutorials:</i> 100s of "data" related courses. "Online Tutorials is a website sharing online courses, and online tutorials for free on a daily basis. You can find the best free online courses and thousands of free online courses with certificates to take your knowledge to the next level with the free courses." It's a free portal so need to be patient with all the ads. Examples below (all provided by Udemey) https://www.onlinetutorials.org/?s=data&post_type=post							
2023 Master class on Data Science using Python A-Z™ : for ML		https://www.udemy.com/course/master-class-on-datascience	Udemey	B		Online, any time	£20
Python Numpy Data Analysis for Data Scientist		https://www.udemy.com/course/python-numpy-data-analysis-for-data-scientist-ai-ml-dl	Udemey	B		Online, any time	£40
Python Data Science Fundamentals: Getting Started		https://www.udemy.com/course/python-data-science-fundamentals-getting-started	Udemey	B		Online, any time	£40
Python for Scientific Research: From Beginner to Advanced		https://www.udemy.com/course/python-for-researchers	Udemey	B		Online, any time	£35
<i>Example of courses through Reed</i> https://www.reed.co.uk/courses/data-science							
MSc Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (Online)	Conversion degree is designed for students from a non-computer science background.	https://www.reed.co.uk/courses/msc-data-science-and-artificial-intelligence-online/311472#/courses/data-science	University of Liverpool	I		Online	
Training for Earth Observation skills.		https://earth-space/services/training/	Earth-i Ltd				
Skills Bootcamp in Data Science	Coding in Python (+ libraries), Machine Learning models, Natural Language Processing (NLP), Data visualisation & storytelling	https://skills.cogrammar.com/	CoGrammar	B		Online, fixed start dates	DofE funded
SENSE 'Big Data & Satellites' Training	Part of SENSE (Centre for Satellite Data in Environmental Science) CDT	https://eo-cdt.org/sense-big-data-satellites-training/	University of Leeds	I		In person, Leeds (one week)	Free to first or second year

							PhD students
Artificial Intelligence for Agriculture Technology and Climate Change (online)	For professionals in the agriculture, agtech, sustainability/climate change and food value chain sectors.	https://www.conted.ox.ac.uk/courses/artificial-intelligence-for-agriculture-technology-and-climate-change-online?code=O23C110H6Y	University of Oxford	I		Online, fixed start dates	£875
Infectious Disease Modelling: Applied Methods in R	Implementing and summarising models of infectious disease in the statistical programming language R.	https://www.conted.ox.ac.uk/courses/infectious-disease-modelling-applied-methods-in-r?code=O23P719COW	University of Oxford			Online, fixed start dates	£280
An Introduction to Earth Observation	Environmental Applications of EO & Very High-resolution Imagery; Operational Use of Remote Sensing in Natural Resources Wales	https://www.youtube.com/@JNCC_UK	JNCC's EO training	B		YouTube	Free
Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation: the use of ERA Interim Data	Learn how to use ERA Interim Data in the operational oceanography framework.	https://www.youtube.com/@CopernicusEU/search	Copernicus	B		YouTube	Free
Applied Data Science Program: Leveraging AI for Effective Decision-Making		https://professional-education-gl.mit.edu/mit-applied-data-science-course	MIT			Live virtual sessions	
Introduction to Earth Observation Data Science	Data extraction, manipulation, and visualisation techniques.	https://www.cranfield.ac.uk/Home/Courses/Short/Environment/Introduction-to-Earth-Observation-Data-Science	Cranfield			In person, Cranfield (one week)	£1,400
Analysing Earth Observation Data Using Open Source Tools	Master the Art of Analysing Satellite Earth Observation Data Using R, QGIS and Others	https://www.geo.university/collections/earth-observation	Geo University			Online	€30
Massive Earth Observation Data Processing with the Sentinel-Hub Platform	Go from Algorithm to EO Service within an hour using the Sentinel-Hub platform	https://www.geo.university/collections/earth-observation	Geo University			Online	€30
Various NASA training in use of Earth Observations		https://appliedsciences.nasa.gov/get-involved/training?search_api_fulltext=dat a	NASA				

Earth Observation Remote Sensing Workshop 2024	Basics of Remote Sensing (RS), overview of ESA's EO satellite missions, science of radar and optical remote sensing, data fusion.	https://www.esa.int/Education/ESA_Academy/TLP_Future_opportunities	ESA			In person, Belgium (one week)	
Satellite Remote Sensing Data Bootcamp With Opensource Tools	Pre-process and Analyze Satellite Remote Sensing Data		Udemy	B		Online, any time	£50
<i>Portals Portals for (mainly) online "data science" courses, tutorials and other learning resources</i>							
Various		https://www.udemy.com/topic/data-science/	Udemy				
Various		https://www.edx.org/learn/data-science	EdX (IBM, Harvard, MIT, ...)				
Various		https://www.datacamp.com/search?q=data%20science	DataCamp				
Various		https://www.udacity.com/catalog/all/any-price/data%20science/any-skill/any-difficulty/any-duration/any-type/most-popular/page-1	Udacity				
Various		https://www.linkedin.com/learning/topics/data-science	LinkedIn Learning				
Various		https://www.codecademy.com/catalog/subject/data-science	Codecademy				
Various		https://www.kaggle.com/learn	Kaggle				
Various		https://isda-online.univie.ac.at/community-tool/	University of Vienna				
Various		https://www.ametsoc.org/index.cfm/ams/education-careers/careers/professional-development/short-courses/	AMS				
Various		https://www.futurelearn.com/subjects/science-engineering-and-maths-courses/data-science	FutureLearn				

Essential Scientific Computing for Environmental Scientists (Novice)		https://forms.office.com/e/XmwiCpMK38	University of Edinburgh	B		In-person/ online	Free
Essential Scientific Computing for Environmental Scientists (Intermediate)	Core data skills for efficient, shareable, and reproducible research practices.	https://forms.office.com/e/XmwiCpMK38	University of Edinburgh	I		In-person/ online	Free
Essential Scientific Computing for Environmental Scientists (Advanced)	Core data skills for efficient, shareable, and reproducible research practices.	https://forms.office.com/e/XmwiCpMK38	University of Edinburgh	A		In-person/ online	Free
Data Carpentry	Programming, shell scripting, or command line tools.	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	B		In person or online	Free
Software Carpentry	Basic computing skills like program design, version control, testing, and task automation.	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	B	RSE	In person or online	Free
HPC Carpentry	Introduction to High Performance Computing (HPC).	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	B	RSE	In person or online	Free
ARCHER2 for Package Users	Efficient use of research software packages.	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	B	DS	In person or online	Free
ARCHER2 for SW developers		https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	B	RSE	In person or online	Free
ARCHER2 for Data Scientists	Core data science packages (e.g., R, Pandas), and data handling best practice.	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	B	DS	In person or online	Free
Data Analysis and Visualisation in Python	Introduction to Python	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	B	DS	In person or online	Free
Introduction to Modern Fortran	Introduction to basics of writing Fortran.	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	I	RSE	In person or online	Free
Scientific Programming with Python		https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	B	RSE	In person or online	Free
Message Passing Programming with MPI	Basics of how to write parallel programs.	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	I	RSE	In person or online	Free
Shared Memory Programming with OpenMP	.	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	I	RSE	In person or online	Free

Advanced MPI		https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	A	RSE	In person or online	Free
Advanced OpenMP	Deepen understanding of OpenMP.	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	A	RSE	In person or online	Free
Parallel Performance Analysis using Scalasca		https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	A	RSE	In person or online	Free
Single Node Optimisation	System-specific features of the ARCHER2 processing units.	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	A	RSE	In person or online	Free
Efficient Use of the HPE Cray EX System	Advanced tools on the new Cray EX architecture.	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	A	RSE	In person or online	Free
Understanding Package Performance	Productivity on large-scale HPC systems.	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	B	DS	In person or online	Free
Modern C++ for Computational Scientists	Aimed at experienced non-C++ programmer.	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	I	RSE	In person or online	Free
Reproducible computational environments using containers		https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/	ARCHER2	I	DS	In person or online	Free
Introduction to Data Science and Machine Learning		https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/		I	DS	In person or online	Free
Python for data analysis and visualisation	Short course for professionals.	https://www.st-andrews.ac.uk/study/online-short-courses/short-course/?page=view&course-title=python-for-data-analysis-and-visualisation	University of St Andrews	I	DS	Self paced	£1,250
Data Carpentry	Data Cleaning and Organising with Python or R.	https://www.ed.ac.uk/bayes/skills-and-talent/dusc/courses	Bayes Centre, UoE	B	DS	Online	£240
Earth Observation for Sustainable Development Goals		https://www.ed.ac.uk/bayes/skills-and-talent/dusc/courses/earth-observation-sustainable-development-goals	Bayes Centre, UoE	B	DS	Sync / Async	£1,065
Introduction to Python Programming for Data Science	Aimed at learners with no prior experience of programming.	https://www.ed.ac.uk/bayes/skills-and-talent/dusc/courses/introduction-to-python-programming	Bayes Centre, UoE	B	DS		£1,065

Practical Introduction to Data Science	Broad rather than deep.	https://www.ed.ac.uk/bayes/skills-and-talent/dusc/courses/practical-intro-data-science	Bayes Centre, UoE	I	DS		£1,010
Programming Skills	Best practices, operating systems, compilers and batch systems.	https://www.ed.ac.uk/bayes/skills-and-talent/dusc/courses/programing-skills	Bayes Centre, UoE	I	RSE		£1,065
Software Development	Learn - high-quality, efficient, robust, portable, usable software products.	https://www.ed.ac.uk/bayes/skills-and-talent/dusc/courses/software-development	Bayes Centre, UoE	B	RSE	Online	£1,065
Performance Analysis	Assess the performance behaviour of code.	https://dirac.ac.uk/performance-analysis-workshop/	DiRAC	I	RSE	Taught and Self-service	Free
Foundation HPC Skills		https://dirac.ac.uk/foundation-hpc-skills-course/	DiRAC	B	RSE	Taught and Self-service	Free
Atmospheric Measurement & Modelling Summer School		https://ncas.ac.uk/study-with-us/atmospheric-measurement-summer-school/	NCAS				
Climate Modelling Summer School		https://ncas.ac.uk/study-with-us/climate-modelling-summer-school/	NCAS				
Data Analysis Tools		https://ncas.ac.uk/study-with-us/data-analysis-tools/	NCAS				
Introduction to Atmospheric Radar		https://ncas.ac.uk/study-with-us/introduction-to-atmospheric-science/	NCAS				
Introduction to Atmospheric Science		https://ncas.ac.uk/study-with-us/introduction-to-scientific-computing/	NCAS				
Introduction to UKCA		https://ncas.ac.uk/study-with-us/introduction-to-ukca/					
Introduction to Unified Model	Introduction to Met Office Unified Model.	https://ncas.ac.uk/study-with-us/introduction-to-unified-model/	NCAS	B	DS	In person	£431
JASMIN Workshop		https://ncas.ac.uk/study-with-us/jasmin-workshop/	NCAS				

MPAS Tutorials		https://ncas.ac.uk/study-with-us/mpas-tutorials/	NCAS				
Practical Aerosol Science		https://ncas.ac.uk/study-with-us/practical-aerosol-science-course/	NCAS				
Data Assimilation Minus the Maths		https://discoverda.org/	University of Reading	B	DA	Online	Free
Short-course on Data Assimilation [ICL and INPE, 2022]	Theory/methods and applications	https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLc36z78U8WUTcpKQJJBgY1J7wEuZAihQk	Imperial College London & INPE Brazil		DA	YouTube video series	Free
An introduction to data assimilation	Part of ESA's Earth observation summer school covering remote sensing, Earth system science, modelling and monitoring.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TmBEryh2OXY	ESA	B	DA	YouTube video	Free
Data Assimilation: variational data assimilation and the ensemble Kalman filter		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8niWYsM2akg	ESA	I	DA	YouTube video	Free
Data Assimilation: applications of data assimilation and current challenges		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=P4eQBB44sfo	ESA		DA	YouTube video	Free
Data assimilation training @ Univ. of Reading 2024	Introduces common data assimilation algorithms.	https://research.reading.ac.uk/met-darc/training/training-courses/	DARC, University of Reading, NCEO		DA	In person	
Data assimilation	DA methods. Implementation for weather prediction (NWP).	https://events.ecmwf.int/event/376/	ECMWF		DA	In person	£980
EUMETSAT/ECMWF NWP-SAF satellite data assimilation	EO for operational numerical weather prediction (NWP).	https://events.ecmwf.int/event/375/	ECMWF		DA	In person	Free
Machine learning for weather prediction		https://events.ecmwf.int/event/377/	ECMWF			In person	£780
DART LAB	Principles of ensemble data assimilation.	https://dart.ucar.edu/tutorials/dart-lab/	NCAR		DA		
Intro to data assimilation (DA) and the EnKF	An interactive (Jupyter notebook) tutorial.	https://github.com/nanscenter/DA-tutorials	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center		DA	GitHub	Free
DA_Tutorial	Experimentation with data assimilation methods.	https://github.com/UMD-AOSC/DA_Tutorial	University of Maryland		DA	GitHub	Free
Data assimilation	Theory and practice of data assimilation.		CERFACS		DA	In person	448 €

	https://cerfacs.fr/en/event/data-assimilation-7/?start=1717977600&end=1718236800					
Hartree Centre Training Portal	Data Science, Artificial Intelligence and Modelling, High Performance and Exascale Computing, Software Engineering , Emerging Technologies https://hartreetraining.stfc.ac.uk/moodle/local/hartree/index.php	Hartree Center				
Matrices and Optimisation	Aimed specifically at Data Assimilation.	University of Exeter (delivered to to Met Office College)	I	DA	Hybrid.	
MSc programmes in a range of Data Science related topics, including: Applied Data Science and Statistics Data Science Data Science with Artificial Intelligence Environmental Intelligence	https://www.exeter.ac.uk/study/postgraduate/courses/datascience/	University of Exeter	B	DS	Face to face.	
Visits and secondments	We are happy to host visits from early career (and later career!) researchers, which can combine research with peer-to-peer and “on-the-job” learning. Typically arranged on an ad hoc basis with host. Free for visiting PhD students for up to three months	University of Exeter	B			Free
Part time PhD study	Students can study for a PhD part time while based with their employer the rest of the time. We typically have a small number Met Office staff taking advantage of this at any given time.	University of Exeter	A			
Research Scientist (Data Science Professional) Apprenticeship	Industry-focused programme designed to shape the strategic development of data science within your organisation https://www.exeter.ac.uk/study/degreeapprenticeships/programmes/researchscientist/	University of Exeter	A	DS	In person/live stream/online resources	£1,8000 for full programme
MSc Climate Change and Artificial Intelligence	Suited to graduates from a wide range of disciplines – including science, technology, engineering and mathematical (STEM) subjects. https://www.reading.ac.uk/ready-to-study/study/subject-area/meteorology-and-climate-pg/msc-climate-change-and-artificial-intelligence	University of Reading	I		Mixed.	
MSc Environmental Data Science and Machine Learning	Key aspects of data science including: cloud computing, remote sensing, environmental monitoring, modelling and computer code.	Imperial College	I	other	Mixed.	

	https://www.imperial.ac.uk/study/courses/postgraduate-taught/environmental-data-science-machine-learning/						
Cambridge Data Science Career Accelerator	<p>Become a data scientist that drives and affects business results. Statistical concepts, data science principles, and machine learning methods, time series analysis and natural language processing (NLP). Moral, legal, and ethical aspects of data and technology generative AI.</p> <p>https://onlinecareeraccelerators.ice.cam.ac.uk/cambridge-data-science-career-accelerator</p>		Cambridge University Institute of Continuing Education	I	DS	Online + weekly live sessions, project.	£8,000
Python Institute	Various	https://pythoninstitute.org/					
Pluralsight	Various	https://www.pluralsight.com/					
Coursera	Various	https://www.coursera.org/					

A4 Professional bodies accreditation/certification schemes

Institution	Location	Links
Alliance for Data Science Professionals	UK	Member organisations: https://alliancefordatascienceprofessionals.co.uk/memberorganisations Accreditation and certification standards: https://alliancefordatascienceprofessionals.co.uk/standards
Institute of Mathematics and its Applications	UK	Membership: https://ima.org.uk/membership/membership-grades/ Chartership: https://ima.org.uk/becoming-chartered/ Advanced Data Science Professional: https://ima.org.uk/membership/afdsp-advanced-data-science-professional/ Degree course accreditation: https://ima.org.uk/university-degree-programme-accreditation/
Royal Statistical Society	UK	Membership: https://rss.org.uk/member-benefits/ Professional accreditation: https://rss.org.uk/membership/professional-development/ Degree course accreditation: https://rss.org.uk/membership/professional-development/accreditation-scheme/
BCS (The Chartered Institute for IT)	UK	Membership: https://www.bcs.org/membership-and-registrations/become-a-member/ Professional accreditation: https://www.bcs.org/membership-and-registrations/get-registered/ Degree course accreditation: https://www.bcs.org/deliver-and-teach-qualifications/academic-accreditation/
Royal Meteorological Society	UK	Membership: https://www.rmets.org/membership Professional Accreditation: https://www.rmets.org/professional-development
Institute of Physics	UK	Membership: https://www.iop.org/membership Professional accreditation: https://www.iop.org/membership/professional-registration Degree course accreditation: https://www.iop.org/education/support-work-higher-education/degree-accreditation-recognition#gref
Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics	USA International	Membership: https://www.siam.org/membership/join-siam/individual-members
American Meteorological Society	USA	Membership: https://www.ametsoc.org/index.cfm/ams/membership/ Professional accreditation: https://www.ametsoc.org/index.cfm/ams/education-careers/careers/professional-development/
IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers)	USA	Membership: https://www.ieee.org/membership/index.html Credentialling service: https://www.ieee.org/education/credentialing/index.html
The Science Council	UK	Professional accreditation: https://sciencecouncil.org/scientists-science-technicians/
Institute for Marine Engineering,	UK	Membership: https://www.imarest.org/membership.html

Science, and Technology		Professional accreditation: https://www.imarest.org/membership/professional-registration.html Training course and provider accreditation: https://www.imarest.org/education-and-training/training-events-providers.html Degree accreditation: https://www.imarest.org/our-partners/for-academia.html
Royal Society of Chemistry	UK	Membership: https://www.rsc.org/membership-and-community/ Professional registration: https://www.rsc.org/careers/cpd/practising-scientists/ Degree accreditation: https://www.rsc.org/membership-and-community/degree-accreditation/
Royal Society of Biology	UK	Membership: https://www.rsb.org.uk/membership Professional accreditation: https://www.rsb.org.uk/careers-and-cpd/registers Degree accreditation: https://www.rsb.org.uk/education/accreditation
Advance HE	UK	Membership (for organisations): https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/membership Professional accreditation: https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/fellowship

A5 Partnerships and collaborations

The following tables list existing and potential/proposed collaborations. The information was gathered from stakeholder consultation and from the project team. We recognise that this information may be incomplete and could become outdated.

A5.1 Well-established collaborations with multiple partners

Collaboration & partners		Purpose	Opportunities to TDSA
Met Office Academic Partnership (MOAP) UK Met Office and various UK universities	UK	Formal partnerships with established routes for CASE PhDs, PhDs for Met Office staff, and secondments. They also facilitate exchanges, Met Office co-supervision of MSc/PhDs, shared seminars and communities of practice in data science and research software engineering (made up of both internal and external members, offering materials and advice for training and development).	Use and expansion of all MOAP mechanisms by TDSA, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student exchanges • Staff secondments • Joint PhDs / PhDs by publication • Expert training courses • Graduate-level courses in various topics (some already online/modular) <p>Exploit and build on existing transatlantic partnerships of MOAP members – for example, University of Reading has a joint MMet degree with the University of Oklahoma.</p>
Momentum Partnership (formerly known as the UM partnership) UK Met Office, and international meteorological agencies, including the US Air Force	UK	This partnership collaborates on the use and development of the Met Office numerical weather prediction systems (such as the Unified Model or the next generation model LFRic), as well as providing model support and training activities.	TDSA members could benefit from training and learning activities and could become actively involved in joint project work/science exchanges. <p>The TDSA involvement could be through provision of funding (e.g. for travel to workshops) which would allow the expansion of TDSA learners' networks.</p>
UK National Climate Science Partnership (UKNCSP) UK Met Office and NERC research centres (BAS, BGS, NCAS, NCEO, PML, NOC, UKCEH).	UK	To integrate observational capabilities with climate models to more effectively monitor, model and predict the evolving UK and global climate, and emerging impacts of climate change.	Each NERC centre has a training budget and delivers courses for early career researchers that could become part of the TDSA's offering. <p>Since the partnership involves NERC staff from a wide range of scientific disciplines, their staff could also become potential users of a TDSA in order to bridge any knowledge gaps.</p>

EUMETNET UK Met Office and various European national Met Services	UK/EU	Provide a framework to help members develop and share their individual and joint meteorological capabilities. They provide training and support through their education and training network Eumetcal.	Potential provider of training.
EUMETSAT UK Met Office and various European national Met Services	UK/EU	EUMETSAT is the European operational satellite agency for monitoring weather, climate and the environment.	EUMETSAT provide training courses and provide funding for fellowships.

A5.2 Centres of excellence

Centre & partners		Purpose	Opportunities to TDSA
Joint Centre for Excellence in Environmental Intelligence (JCEEI) UK Met Office, University of Exeter	UK	To pioneer the development of environmental research using AI and deliver innovative, interdisciplinary education and training.	Potential provider of training and mentors; opportunities for joint project work; potential member of a CoP. JCEEI has a pre-established collaboration agreement for linking with partner organisations.
Cooperative Institute for Marine and Atmospheric Studies (CIMAS) University of Miami (UoM), UCL and NOAA	US	The institute exists to bring together research and educational resources to increase scientific understanding of Earth's oceans and atmosphere. They support students at the UoM via grants and through co-chairing student committees. UCL has research collaboration with CIMAS. NOAA also collaborates with UC San Diego (including SIO, CW3E) and UC Santa Cruz.	Potential to expand research collaborations with CIMAS/NOAA to other institutions and TDSA members
Institute for Data Science and Computing (IDSC) University of Miami and various universities	US	Support both internal and globally external research initiatives through their resources in data science and computing. The institute is comprised of several research centres focusing on topics such as Earth Systems and AI + Machine Learning.	The IDSC hosts workshops, internships and year-long fellowships which could be utilised by members of the TDSA. The IDSC also take part in outreach activities and could be a useful networking partner for promoting TDSA opportunities to high school students

Center for Western Weather and Water Extremes (CW3E) University of California San Diego and various universities	US	Their mission is to provide “water cycle science, technology and outreach to support effective policies and practices that address the impacts of extreme weather and water events on the environment, people and the economy of Western North America.”	TDSA members could access CW3E’s summer colloquiums for training next-generation atmospheric scientists and hydrologists. It was noted during the stakeholder meeting that CW3E would consider hosting workshops and provide funding for postdoctoral researchers (PDRs) visiting UK universities and/or the Met Office
Data Intensive Studies Center (DISC) Tufts University	US	DISC provides courses and workshops and data-thons on data science topics, student DISC Internships, and faculty SEED Grant & Study Group program and DISC Fellowships.	DISC currently offers training, internships and events to Tufts University staff and students only. We suggest that a TDSA seek to collaborate with DISC to share these resources with a wider audience. There is an additional benefit in a two-way partnership in that students and staff at Tufts University and DISC may also benefit from the resources of the TDSA.
Institute for Computational and Mathematical Engineering (ICME) Stanford University	US	ICME are a diverse, interdisciplinary group, with interests and research conducted at the intersection of applied math, statistics, computer science and applications.	Staff and students of the ICME could become potential members of a TDSA

A5.3 Centres for doctoral training / doctoral training programmes

Centres for doctoral training (CDT) are formed by a group of research organisations who combine their skills and resource to support and train PhD students in practical skills as well as acquiring academic knowledge. It should be noted here that CDTs have finite lifetimes; although materials may continue to exist after this time, CDT courses will not continue to run routinely.

Centre & partners		Purpose	Opportunities to TDSA
SENSE Earth Observation CDT University of Leeds, University of Edinburgh, BAS and NOC	UK	CDT with a focus on satellite data in environmental science. They co-supervise PhD students who benefit from bespoke training in Earth Observation, AI/ML and soft skills.	Potential opportunity to use and expand SENSE training in Earth Observation and ML, as well as soft skills (relevant for early/mid-career), across the TDSA. CDT students are potential users of a TDSA.
Leeds Institute for Fluid Dynamics (LIFD) CDT University of Leeds, UK Met Office, NCAS and ~25 non-academic partners	UK	A well-established CDT with a focus on fluid dynamics (environmental or otherwise) offering a four-year integrated MSc and PhD programme.	This CDT may develop relevant data science training for fluid dynamics which could be utilised by members of the TDSA.

			Private sector partners and CDT students are potential users of TDSA.
Environmental Intelligence (EI) CDT University of Exeter and various industry partners (e.g. UK Met Office, Microsoft, IBM)	UK/INT	Founded in 2018, the CDT has an interdisciplinary focus on data science and statistics as well as the ethics, governance, and responsible innovation principles related to the use of big data and AI within the field of environmental and sustainability research.	The CDT provide expertise in interdisciplinary training across a wide range of environmental topics which could be utilised by members of a TDSA. CDT students are potential users of a TDSA.
Advancing the Frontiers of Earth System Prediction (AFESP) University of Reading, UK Met Office, ECMWF and NCAS	UK/EUR	AFESP is a 15-year long Doctoral Training Programme launched in 2023, aimed at tackling research challenges in global Earth System Prediction. It additionally funds 5-year postdoctoral fellowships.	AFESP are looking to develop training and are therefore potential users (as well as providers) of training through a TDSA.
Mathematics for our Future Climate (MFC) CDT University of Reading, Imperial College London, Southampton University (and industry/research organisation partners e.g. UK Met Office, ECMWF, NOC, NCEO)	UK	An new EPSRC CDT launching in 2024, that harnesses the power of mathematics to address the issues presented by climate change	This doctoral training programme will equip students with skills in theory for climate science, (geo)physical sciences, scientific computing, statistics and data analysis, thus MFC may be both users and providers of training for TDSA.

A5.4 National and multinational research centres and services

Centre & partners		Purpose	Opportunities to TDSA
Alan Turing Institute Several UK universities (including all MOAP universities)	UK	The UK national institute for data science and AI. Several universities have Alan Turing Fellows.	The institute provides PhD enrichment schemes and hackathons which could be used by members of a TDSA. The Turing University Network provides an opportunity for UK universities to engage and collaborate, which the TDSA could promote to its members in order to encourage further collaboration.
National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS) Various universities have embedded NCAS staff, with the Directorate based	UK	NCAS runs a number of workshops and summer schools in topics such as atmospheric science, scientific computing and climate modelling (amongst others)	Potential provider of training for a TDSA NCAS staff could become potential users of a TDSA

at the University of Leeds			
National Centre for Earth Observation (NCEO) Universities of Leeds, Reading and Edinburgh (and many other non-MOAP institutes)	UK	NCEO has staff employed at several MOAP Universities and oversees NEODAAS (the NERC Earth Observation Data Acquisition and Analysis Service, see below). NCEO carries out research in data assimilation and provides support and training in this area (used already by the Met Office).	Staff could contribute to a TDSA through potential project collaboration and as a provider of training, and are prospective users of a TDSA
Joint Center for Satellite Data Assimilation (JCSDA) A multi-agency research centre, including both NOAA and NASA	US	To improve the use of satellite data for analysing and predicting weather, ocean, climate and environment through the use of data assimilation.	Potential provider of training e.g. their JEDI Academies (week-long training workshops aimed at engaging members of affiliated partner institutions, scientific, academic, private sector, and public communities) JCSDA also provide research exchanges – for example the Met Office have already been exchanging staff with JCSDA through TDSA funding.
JASMIN Designed, integrated and operated by STFC on behalf of NERC	UK	Provide HPC storage and compute facilities as well as some training courses across various universities	Potential provider of training. Provider of computing resources including GPUs for practicing skills (but needs project specific funding).
ARCHER2 Provided by UKRI, EPCC, University of Edinburgh and Cray	UK	Provide HPC resource as well as some training courses across various universities.	Potential provider of training. Provider of computing resources (may need project specific funding). There is an online assessment tool to test knowledge of using HPC and free access to use HPC resources for 12 months (“ARCHER2 Driving Test”).
European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) An independent intergovernmental organisation supported by 35 states	EUR	A research institute and 24/7 operational forecasting service for its member states. They have their own supercomputer facility and data archive. ECMWF deliver various in-person training courses in Earth Observation at their base in Reading (UK), hold annual workshops and seminars (many of which have a hybrid delivery approach) and work	Potential provider of training and computing resources. Potential for collaboration through joint project work and staff secondments.

		collaboratively with scientists across the world.	
European Space Agency (ESA) Phi-lab	EUR	The Phi-lab, established in 2017, is an open, collaborative laboratory that promotes innovation and AI within the field of Earth Observation.	<p>Potential to build on the organisation's existing activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • host short- and long-term (up to two years) internships, • workshops and summer schools, aimed at those within academia and industry; • co-fund PhDs and PDRAs (either short term or up to two years). <p>Potential provider of training.</p>
NERC Earth Observation Data Acquisition and Analysis Service (NEODAAS)	UK	NEODAAS offers training in a wide range of topics related to Earth Observation, AI and data science more widely.	<p>Potential to build on existing activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • training on introduction to EO, practical use of EO data in research, atmospheric correction of satellite and airborne data, and sessions on machine learning and AI for EO. • videos and other online training (some publicly available, others for NCEO members only)
NERC's Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI)	UK	NERC strategic theme intended to connect researchers, policymakers and innovators to the hardware, data, tools and skills required for research in environmental sciences.	Potential to make use of DRI's large-scale computing and data storage facilities, as well as software, shared code libraries and mechanisms for access. Potential funder for TDSA courses.
National Centre for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) Established by the National Science Foundation	US	<p>Provide the atmospheric and related Earth system science community with resources including supercomputers, research aircraft, computer models and datasets.</p> <p>NCAR also provide education and outreach opportunities including internships, early career fellowships and scientific workshops.</p>	<p>Potential provider of training through tutorials, workshops and summer schools.</p> <p>Opportunities for collaborative work and sabbaticals.</p>
Hartree Centre Part of STFC within UKRI. Has strategic partnerships with academic and industry leaders.	UK	To help UK businesses and organisations to explore and adopt supercomputing, data science and AI technologies. They also collaborate with academic institutions, providing training courses and mentoring schemes to students.	<p>Potential provider of training (live training events, self-learning activities, webinars) and HPC resources.</p> <p>Opportunities for research collaborations.</p> <p>Opportunities for mentor schemes.</p>
World Meteorological Organization	INT	A specialised agency responsible for promoting international cooperation on atmospheric science,	<p>Potential provider of training through workshops and training courses.</p> <p>Wider international engagement with TDSA activities.</p>

Part of the United Nations (UN), with members across the world		climatology, hydrology and geophysics.	Connection with WMO Global Campus initiatives, promoting open use and access to learning resources among WMO Members. Provision of scholarship funding for learners from the global south to achieve training goals.
Royal Meteorological Society (RMetS)	UK	RMetS has its own education, professional accreditation and EDI programmes, a Masterclasses CPD activity, as well as a DA Special Interest Group.	Many opportunities to build RMetS activities into our training catalogue/personal development ideas list. Potential to explore whether the RMetS could join Alliance for Data Science Professionals and start issuing Data Science certifications alongside RMet and CMet.
International Symposium on Data Assimilation (ISDA) and ISDA-online	INT	Annual data assimilation conference and monthly focussed webinar programme.	Conference and webinars could provide valuable CPD for TDSA learners in the DA role (as listeners and contributors).

A5.5 Cross-university collaborations

Collaboration		Opportunities to TDSA
University of California Santa Cruz	US	It was noted during the stakeholder meeting that this institute may be able to contribute to teaching and provide ocean-specific educational materials.
Oklahoma University and University of Reading	US & UK	Joint degree programme with a year in Oklahoma.
Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) and University of Leeds (Institute for Climate and Atmospheric Science)	GER & UK	Potential to build on existing research collaborations and exchange opportunities for undergraduate students, postgraduates, and staff.
University of the Philippines Diliman and the University of Reading	Philippines and UK	Dual PhD Programme in Meteorology with time spent at each University.
NOAA funded Data Assimilation Research Consortium	US & UK	At the time of writing, the winners of this funded opportunity have not been announced. However, it is expected to lead to transatlantic research exchanges.

